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D4.4 Gender Equality Plans

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Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

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Table of Contents

Version history	2
List of Tables.....	5
List of Figures.....	5
Acronyms and Abbreviations	6
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1 Purpose and scope	8
1.2 Document structure.....	9
2. The ATHENA process.....	9
3. Institutional approval status of the ATHENA GEPs.....	11
4. JSI Gender Equality Plan.....	13
4.1 Introduction	13
4.2 Development process and GEP management.....	15
4.3 Diagnosis	17
4.4 Objectives	21
4.5 Actions	22
4.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	32
4.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP.....	38
4.8 References	40
4.9 Annex	41
Training plans.....	41
5. UJK Gender Equality Plan.....	45
5.1 Introduction	45
5.2 Development process and GEP management.....	48
5.3 Diagnosis	50
5.4 Objectives	59
5.5 Actions.....	59
5.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	64
5.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP	66
6. UB Gender Equality Plan.....	68
6.1 Introduction	68
6.2 Development process and GEP management.....	71
6.3 Diagnosis	72
6.4 Objectives	74
6.5 Actions.....	77
6.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	87
6.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP.....	87
6.8 Annex	88
7. ULPGC Gender Equality Plan	90
7.1 Introduction	90
7.2 Development process and GEP management.....	91
7.3 Diagnosis	93

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

7.4	Objectives	96
7.5	Actions	97
7.6	GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	120
7.7	Dissemination strategy of the GEP	120
8.	SAS Gender Equality Plan	122
8.1	Introduction	122
8.2	Development process and GEP management	123
8.3	Diagnosis	125
8.4	Objectives	138
8.5	Actions	139
8.6	GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	145
8.7	Dissemination strategy of the GEP	146
8.8	Annex: Lists of international and national policies	146
9.	URAK Gender Equality Plan	149
9.1	Introduction	149
9.2	Development process and GEP management	149
9.3	Diagnosis	150
9.4	Objectives	150
9.5	Actions	150
9.6	GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	161
9.7	Dissemination strategy of the GEP	161
9.8	Annex	161
10.	ACIISI - GOBCAN Gender Equality Plan	163
10.1	Introduction	163
10.2	Development process and GEP management	173
10.3	Diagnosis	175
10.4	Objectives	191
10.5	Actions	203
10.6	GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	209
10.7	Dissemination strategy of the GEP	209
11.	FRCT Gender Equality Plan	211
11.1	Introduction	211
11.2	Development process and GEP management	212
11.3	Diagnosis	213
11.4	Objectives	215
11.5	Actions	216
11.6	GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment	222
11.7	Dissemination strategy of the GEP	224

List of Tables

Table 1. Overview of institutional approval status of the ATHENA GEPs	11
Table 2. Actions for JSI GEP - Work-life balance and organisational culture.....	25
Table 3. Actions for JSI GEP - Gender balance in leadership and decision-making.....	27
Table 4. Actions for JSI GEP - Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.....	28
Table 5. Actions for JSI GEP - Integrating gender dimension into research and teaching content	30
Table 6. Actions for JSI GEP - Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	31
Table 7. Number of UJK employees, including women and men (as of the end of 2020)	51
Table 8. Gender balance characteristics in decision-making positions at UJK [%]	52
Table 9. Academic staff by degree, academic title at UJK	53
Table 10. Actions for UJK GEP.....	60
Table 11. Actions for UB GEP	78
Table 12. Actions implemented in the ULPGC GEP	110
Table 13: SAS organizations	130
Table 14: 'Unadjusted' gender income gap in SAV (% , 2020)	134
Table 15: Ratio of first authorship to authorship of men and women in the SAS.....	136
Table 16: Selected examples of qualitative indicators in talent management	137
Table 17. Actions implemented for SAS' GEP	140
Table 18. SAS GEP Monitoring	145
Table 19. Actions for URAK GEP	152
Table 20. Updated dashboard of the Management Center	177
Table 21. Organizational structure of the Management Centre (ACIISI-GOBCAN)	179
Table 22. Age structure of the management center staff (ACIISI-GOBCAN).....	180
Table 23. Diagnostic and actions for each specific objective - ACIISI-GOBCAN GEP.....	193
Table 24. Actions for ACIISI - GOBCAN GEP.....	203
Table 25. Actions for the FRCT's GEP	219

List of Figures

Figure 1. Showing the absolute number of female (light blue) and male (dark blue) a) researchers at JSI in 2020; b) members in decision-making bodies in 2020	16
Figure 2. The proportion of women and men among academic staff by degree/title at UJK....	54
Figure 3 Women among research and research and teaching staff by age and grade/title at UJK.....	54
Figure 4. Male research and research and teaching staff by age and rank/title at UJK	55
Figure 5. Intervention areas within the UB GEP.....	70
Figure 6: The so-called leaky pipeline: representation of women and men in different positions at the.....	127

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research potential

Figure 7: Comparison of the representation of PhD graduates and currently employed researchers at the SAS	127
Figure 8: Representation of women and men in the Presidium of the SAS	128
Figure 9: Representation of women and men in the Scientific Council of the SAS	129
Figure 10: Representation of women and men in the position of director of the SAS organisations.....	129
Figure 11: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Natural sciences at SAS	131
Figure 12: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Technology at SAS.....	131
Figure 13: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Medical sciences at SAS	132
Figure 14: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Agriculture at SAS	132
Figure 15: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Social sciences at SAS	133
Figure 16: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation - Humanities at SAS	133
Figure 17. Content areas within the UVSK SAV GEP	139

Acronyms and Abbreviations

ANES	National Agency for Equality between Women and Men
D	Deliverable
ERA	European Research Area
EHEA	European Higher Education Area
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GE	Gender equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI	Gender Equality Plan Implementation
JSI	Jozef Stefan Institute
M&E	Monitoring and evaluation
RPO	Research performing organization
RFO	Research funding organization
T	Task
WP	Work package

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present document, entitled ‘Gender Equality Plans’ reports the individual Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) that 6 RPOs and 2 RFOs project partners institutions, i.e. JSI, UJK, UB, ULPGC, UBSK SAV, URAK, ACIISI-GOBCAN and FRCT, will implement to achieve systemic institutional change within their institutions. These GEPs will be implemented and monitored during the GEP implementation (M16 – M38) and monitoring (M16 – M48) phases of the ATHENA project.

This deliverable particularly presents each GEP in detail. Each institution provides an overview and essential information about the GEP adopted in the institution, addressing the institution’s commitment to gender equality as well as how this last is integrated institutionally. Each GEP also introduces the whole process undertaken for GEP development, negotiation, adoption and implementation as well as the main conclusions of the diagnosis of the situation of gender equality in the institution. Within the diagnosis section, main results of the quantitative and qualitative assessment carried out under ‘WP2 – Gender equality audit and assessment of procedures and practices at organizational and national level’ are presented. Additionally, main gender bias and interventions/priority areas are identified.

Then, each institution lists the objectives that will be pursued and the actions that will be implemented throughout the implementation of the GEP, showing the connection of each objective with the results of the diagnosis. The objectives and intervention areas set by each institution follow a common ATHENA approach, included within the ‘ATHENA gender and diversity standards’ (see D4.2 for further information on the project standards for the development and implementation of the GEPs).

Finally, the GEPs include guidance for periodical monitoring as well as its dissemination strategy.

It is worth noting that when drafting and developing the GEPs, particular emphasis has been placed on following the guidelines on the mandatory and recommended process and content-related requirements of the *Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans*² from the EC.

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans*, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/876509>

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable describes:

- The process carried out so far by the ATHENA consortium to develop and implement the 8 GEPs in the ATHENA institutions (**section 2**) as well as the institutional approval status of each GEP (**section 3**).
- Each of the GEPs that have been developed under the ATHENA framework (**sections 4 – 11**).

2. The ATHENA process

The ATHENA project started in February 2021 aimed at supporting 6 RPOs and 2 RFOs in Europe to develop and implement their Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The ATHENA GEPs, that are presented in detail in the next sections, were drafted and developed following a common and robust project approach. In order to develop and implement the GEPs, the ATHENA institutions participated in research and participatory activities which started under the umbrella of WP2 activities. Under this WP, quantitative and qualitative gender audits (D2.1 – Common database for gender equality audit) and assessment of existing provisions at national level (D2.2 – Report on national status in gender equality in each partner country) were developed to understand the state-of-the-art of gender equality (GE) in the research institutions. Additionally, surveys, storytelling interviews and focus groups involving the institutional staff were carried out to assess their experiences of GE and identify existing gender bias. These outcomes are summarized in the project ‘Gender Equality Reports’ (D2.3 – Gender Equality Reports), which includes recommendations for the development of the GEPs.

Parallely, the ATHENA institutions established their Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees, key actors to facilitate the institutional change and promote GE within their institutions. These GEPI Committee members participated in a capacity building programme (D3.1 – Programme and material of the training for GEPI Committees) aimed at making them more aware of the relevance of gender in their work and to help them identify and leverage the appropriate tools and resources to implement the institutional gender strategies. A second training programme devoted to the whole institutional community is currently being implemented by each ATHENA institution implementing a GEP (D3.2 – Programme and material of the Gender Training Programme).

Three mutual learning workshops will be also developed throughout the project for the consortium to exchange experiences and feedback on topics related to the development, adoption, implementation, monitoring and assessment of the GEPs (D3.3 and D3.4 – Reports on learning activities).

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Based on the outputs of the WP2 and the capacity building programmes, activities under WP4 are aimed at advising and guiding ATHENA institutions in the development of their tailored and adapted GEPs. For this purpose, a GEPs best practices analysis (D4.1 – GEPs best practices compendium) among GEPs implemented in European RPOs and RFOs was performed so project partners could identify successful practices that might be replicated and adapted in accordance with their own needs and challenges. At the same time, a project Toolkit (D4.3 – Toolkit for transforming the institutional culture in terms of gender aspects) offering an array of tools and resources was developed to assist project institutions with examples, guidance and inspiration for tailoring their institutional plans.

All the GEPs has been developed following a common project approach which consisted of defining common targets that the ATHENA institutions designing their GEPs should include within their plans (D4.2 – Gender and diversity standards). As abovementioned, this common approach was based on the requirements and recommendations stated in the *Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans* from the EC.

The GEPs implemented will be closely monitored and assessed following the ATHENA Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) system (D5.1 – Guidelines on monitoring and evaluation). The ATHENA institutions have developed indicators for the monitoring and evaluation of the GEPs following the project guidelines for monitoring and evaluation.

ATHENA has put in place a sustainability strategy to ensure replication of the GEPs and the project results by involving stakeholders within the project activities. These activities include the organization of two local public events per partner, two webinars and a series of video interviews with research organizations representing best practices.

An e-platform for action (www.gender-equality.eu) has been also developed as central means together with the project website to publicly share the project material, advances and results. Specifically, the e-platform includes tools and resources that contribute to achieve gender equality in science and research, i.e trainings developed under the project framework; compendium of women researchers at EU level to make them more visible; inclusion of the ATHENA toolkit abovementioned; and an interactive forum for women and men to freely discuss the issues of GE in research and science (for more information, see D6.4 – ATHENA e-platform for Action).

The GEPs will be disseminated following the project ‘Dissemination and communication strategy’ (D7.1).

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3. Institutional approval status of the ATHENA GEPs

This document presents the GEPs that have been developed in the framework of ATHENA. All the GEPs of the 8 ATHENA institutions that develop and implement their GEPs within the project framework have been drafted.

At the time of drafting this deliverable, many of the GEPs are already officially approved by the appropriate level of the institution to which the GEP applies. Anyway, it is planned formal approval for the rest of the GEPs that are not officially approved at institutional level yet.

The table below shows an overview of the institutional approval status of the project GEPs:

Table 1. Overview of institutional approval status of the ATHENA GEPs

ATHENA institution	GEP formally approved at institutional level
Jozef Stefan Institute (JSI)	No
Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (UJK)	Yes
Universitatea din Bucuresti (UB)	Yes
Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)	Yes
Ustav Viskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Akademie VIED (UVSK SAV) Institute for Research in Social Communication (SAS)	Yes
University of Ruse Angel Kanchev (URAK)	Yes
Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información del Gobierno de Canarias (ACIISI-GOBCAN)	No
Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)	No

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Gender Equality Plan

Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI)

4. JSI Gender Equality Plan

4.1 Introduction

Aligned with EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020 - 2023, on the 20th of May 2021 Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) has adopted a decision on the Action plan for gender equality [14].

Activities of the Jožef Stefan Institute were initiated and accelerated by the Athena project financed by the European Commission from the Horizon 2020 budget [15]. JSI as a partner in the Athena project is committed to strive towards gender equality, mitigating barriers to the recruitment, retention, and career progression of female researchers, and addressing gender imbalances in decision-making processes through delivering and implementation of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP). In the framework of the project, the Gender Equality Plan Implementation (GEPI) Committee has been established, which acts as a driver for the developing and monitoring of the implementation of the GEP. The committee is composed of the Institute employees representing different target groups including leadership and management, researchers, administration, PhD students.

To put these activities in the national context, Slovenia emphasizes freedom of work as one of the fundamental freedoms defined by the Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia including the freedom to choose a job and the accessibility of any job by anyone under the same conditions regardless of gender or any other personal circumstance. Employment of citizens is the most common way to ensure social security and the right to a retirement pension. The main legislation of gender equality is disclosed in the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act (Zakon o enakih možnostih žensk in moških) (Uradni list RS, št. 59/02, 61/07 – ZUNEO-A, 33/16 – ZVarD in 59/19) [1], which defines general and special measures for the creation of equal opportunities, determines the holders of tasks, their competencies and obligations, introduces special informal treatment of cases of alleged unequal treatment of any gender and the advocate of equal opportunities as an authorized person and the obligations of the entities involved in these cases. An unbalanced gender representation in the sense of the previous paragraph is defined as the representation of one sex in an individual area of social life or its part lower than 40%.

Resolution on the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men 2015-2020 (Resolucija o nacionalnem programu za enake možnosti žensk in moških 2015-2020 (ReNPEMŽM15-2) (Uradni list RS, št. 84/15) [2] sets out general priority areas for improving the situation of women and men and ensuring the sustainable development of gender equality in the Republic of Slovenia, and identifies key challenges and issues for the period 2015-2020. According to this document, the relation between gender equality and science/education is currently not balanced and different types of gender inequalities have been recognized.

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The Protection against discrimination Act (Zakon o varstvu pred diskriminacijo (ZVarD) (Uradni list: 33/2016, 21/2018-ZNOrg); Active since: 23. 5. 2016 [3], provides for the protection of every individual against discrimination regardless of gender, nationality, race or ethnic origin, language, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression, social status, economic status, education or any other personal circumstance.

Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities of Republic Slovenia is responsible for the gender equality (GE) policies and their implementation, monitoring and evaluation. In 2016, the Ministry implemented a pre-defined project entitled “Towards Equalizing Power Relations between Women and Men“ [4]. The overall aim of the project was to better understand equal and unequal power relations between women and men, to identify adequate responses to persistent imbalances in gender-based power structures in Slovenian society.

Gender equality in research is regulated in the document Strategy of work and development of Research Agency of Republic Slovenia (ARRS) 2016-2020 [5], where the Agency as one of the fields to monitor includes the number of women working on research projects and number of women among project leaders. Gender balance in decision-making and the enhancement of women’s participation in research are regulated by the Rules on the Procedures of the (co)financing and Assessment of Research Activities and on Monitoring the Implementation of Research Activities [6].

The area of Research and Innovation is regulated by the Resolution on Research and Innovation strategy 2011-2020 [7]. Measure 34 foresees an Action Plan for Improving Career Opportunities for Researchers in all Career Periods and for Ensuring the Gender Equality Principle. To increase the participation of women in science, for improving scientific excellence, connections with European Research Area (ERA) and its goals, the Slovenian Strategy for Strengthening the European Research Area 2016-2020 (Slovenian ERA Roadmap 2016-2020) [8] was put into force in 2016. One of the priorities was gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research (priority area 4).

The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport is responsible for implementation of Research and innovation strategy of Slovenia (RISS) 2011-2020 [9], as well as for the UNESCO L’Oreal Scholarship. Under the Ministry, there is also a Commission for Equal Opportunities in Science [10], which is very active in the area (research and data collection; suggestion of legal changes, including changes in order to create action plan to improve career possibilities of women; awareness-raising; dissemination of research findings; promotion of gender equality...).

In Nov. 2021, The Act on Scientific Research and Innovation [11] has been adopted by the Parliament of the Republic of Slovenia. It regulates funding in a way that enables the stability and autonomous development of scientific research activities and their performers. The adopted law, with the establishment of the National Council for Ethics and Integrity in Science, also addresses ethics and integrity in science and gender equality.

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The rest of this document presents the development process of GEP including the diagnoses of the current situations at JSI, the objectives to achieve, the proposed actions and the proposed ways for monitoring and assessment. The report concludes with a description of the dissemination strategy.

4.2 Development process and GEP management

The process of GEP negotiation at JSI has been initiated a few years before the official start of the ATHENA project in February 2021. The project is funded in the frame of the H2020 program. It is noted that ATHENA's main objective is to support the partners, i.e., research organizations, in the development and implementation of GEPs to enable cultural and institutional change and equal participation of the staff in these organizations.

4.2.1 Action Plan

The first step was to propose the action plan for the implementation of gender equality which would serve as a guideline in the creation of GEP. This document was reviewed by the heads of research departments and centers of the institute and signed by the Director of the Institute on May 20, 2021, available at the webpage <https://ijs.si/ijsw/EnakeMoznosti?action=AttachFile&do=get&target=EnakeMoznosti.pdf>. The document describes the steps towards the creation of GEP planned to take place in 2022. In 2021, the focus was on the analysis of the current situation of gender equality on the institutional level.

4.2.2 GEPI Committee

As support in capacity building for systemic institutional change, the Gender Equality Plan Implementation (GEPI) committee was established on August 17, 2021. The committee consists of representatives of High and middle management, Researchers, and Professors. It was noted that our institute does not have a Human Resources (HR) manager or unit and the need for such a person was recognized. Thus, the Administrative staff and a small personnel unit were merged into one target group (Business Administration (BA)+Human Resources (HR)). On the other hand, Young researchers (i.e., Ph.D. students) who represent about 10 % of the total number of employees, were included as an autonomous target group in the GEPI committee. The committee consists of female and male members of all generations of employees and represents all target groups. It is noted that the membership of the committee increased from 11 at the kick-off to 16 at the end of 2021. The GEPI committee members participated in three training modules. The first two modules of training were organized by the coordinator of the ATHENA project for the whole ATHENA project consortium and took place in November 2021. These modules entitled Change management for gender equality, and Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe, and consisted of lectures and study materials. The third training was organized on January 14, 2022 in-house with help of the external expert. The module included a lecture entitled *How to resist unconscious bias in the academic field?* and an interactive discussion related to the topic of the lecture.

4.2.3 Diagnoses

To obtain quantitative data on gender equality at the institutional level, three data collection methods were used: online surveys, story-telling interviews, and discussions with the focus groups. An online staff survey implemented by a standardized questionnaire comprising 47 closed and open questions was distributed via an online data collection system. In total, 324 responders (39% of the employees) were included in the analysis.

Quantitative data

In 2020, the proportion of women in total employment (1119) was 36.5 %. Among 856 researchers, 30.1 % were women. 75 % of these women were employed in Natural sciences and 25 % in Engineering and technology. 46 % of female researchers are young (25-34 years), 37 % in age period (35-44 years), 13 % in age period (45-54), and 13 % older than 55 years (Fig. 1a). The JSI has never had a female director since it was established in 1949. Since 2020, we have a male director and for the first time a female deputy-director. Among Heads of departments, only 16 % are women. In Scientific Council, 27 % are women. In the year 2000, in average around 15 % of women were in decision-making bodies (Fig.1b).

Figure 1. Showing the absolute number of female (light blue) and male (dark blue) a) researchers at JSI in 2020; b) members in decision-making bodies in 2020.

The objective of the story-telling interviews was to search for the diversity of typical facilitators and inhibitors of gender awareness in the life-course of scholars. Based on the pre-defined scenario, the ATHENA team implemented 12 interviews with researchers (female and male, different age groups, with and without children or family obligations, different positions). Interviews with five focus groups were organized: GEPI committee, Young researchers, Researchers, BA+HR, and Management. Using the standardized script, the recorded discussions were

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transcribed and the data were analyzed by simple content analysis without coding. The results of the surveys are summarized in the Gender Equality Report (D2.3).

4.2.4 GEP Management

The ATHENA framework is aimed at removing women and men's inequalities and facilitating institutional change. The GEPI Committee together with the ATHENA project partners is the key institutional actor for the transmission of co-produced knowledge and the facilitation and promotion of the needed transformations through the development and implementation of the GEP. The mission is to remove barriers to the recruitment, retention, and career progression of female researchers, address gender imbalances in decision-making processes, and generate the institutional cultural change needed to avoid future gender bias and discriminatory practices. The activities include monitoring the implementation of GEP, dissemination, planning, and organization of training of the employees.

The external expert has advised on various activities of ATHENA team and provided professional support in training of the GEPI committee. The support of the external expert is funded by the ATHENA project budget.

The responsibility for the implementation and monitoring of GEP is upon the Director of JSI and within his office the Advisor to the Director. The need to establish a Human Resources (HR) manager or unit has become evident. We expect a new professional to be employed at the JSI in this year with responsibilities in the fields of gender equality (implementation and monitoring of GEP, analytical work, upgrade of the GEP), ethical aspects, and conflict solving.

Financial resources: All initial tasks including gender equality assessment, data base, gender training programs, the definition of gender and equality standards (GEP), and monitoring of GEP is financed from the Athena project budget. The expert for the gender equality is planned to be paid from the JSI integral budget, part for administration and services. All future activities beyond the Athena project will be financed via institutional funding, implemented after June 30, 2022 (following adoption of the new law on November 18, 2021 with the date of application January 1, 2022).

4.3 Diagnosis

The presented diagnosis is based on the data analyses of the data collection composed from the JSI general gender indicators for the year 2020, the 12 storytelling interviews, the discussions carried out in five focus groups with 49 participants, and on the data collected from the survey answers where 40% of the JSI total staff took part. We have structured the findings following the main content areas as proposed by the Athena project.

4.3.1 Work-life balance and organizational culture

Work-life balance represents the most important challenge for female researchers in their careers and promotion. Children care and parents care are not equally

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distributed between male and female researchers and most of the domestic work is still done by women. In 2020, maternity leave was used by 11% of female researchers of the age 25-44 years but only 5 % of male researchers of the same age have used paternal leave. A sharp competition among the researchers for research grants on a basis of number of publications and other relevant references contributes to the number of young fathers, who do not use the possibility of parental leave due to a risk to be less successful in project applications. The period when a woman has small children is witnessed by number of women researchers – mothers too difficult for their scientific advancement and promotion. Young mothers are overwhelmed, more tired, and more absent from work. The additional drawback for young parents is the request for spending at least one academic year (9-months) at a post-doctoral position in academic institution abroad before obtaining a senior researcher position. This is one of the crucial steps for getting a permanent position in the organization. The period of the post-doctoral stage overlaps with time, in which many people choose to have children. A widely held opinion is that men usually get much ahead in their research carrier in the period when women have small children. Moreover, a great decrease in the number of female researchers older than 45 years has been observed at the JSI in the last years. This decrease might be explained by employment in industry, public administration, or at universities, where the workplace is more secure [12].

The employees of the JSI have the possibility to arrange a flexible working time and to use telework (i.e. working remotely, home office, etc.). They can work also part-time. In 2020, 151 researchers worked part-time, of these 25 % of women and 75 % of men. These numbers are explained by the existence of complementary employment, where many researchers (majority are men) are 100 % employed at university in a pedagogical process and 20 % at the JSI.

Maternity/paternity institutional policy at the JSI does not exist and respective support measures are following the national policy that applies to all type of employment. The JSI does not provide internal childcare services or on-demand/flexible childcare support for the employees/PhD students. The JSI does not provide formal support for caring for employees' elders and/or dependent family members, but provides an informal support based on the agreement/consent with the head of a group.

4.3.2 Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

In the last three years, the percentage of women in decision-making bodies decreased in comparison with the time slot between 2006-2018, when it was gradually increasing toward the 30 % ratio. [13] There are no specific leadership education or other programs provided to support women in the decision-making positions. There is also no gender training for managers provided, which would help in increasing the gender competencies in the management. Targets/quotas for gender balance in decision bodies like boards and committees are not considered neither even openly discussed. The majority of the survey responders agree that men are preferred for appointing people to top managerial positions in research or academia as well as the project applicants at the national level. The majority of the survey responders also disagree that it is natural men are in the leading position and women do service/support.

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4.3.3 Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

The proportion of women among PhD candidates in 2020 was 39 %, while among the selected new PhD students 31 % were women. Among all active PhD students, 36 % were women. The 60 % of all graduations in 2016 were obtained by women, while in 2020 it was only 38 % female graduates, which is a big drop that needs to be considered. The “brain drain” did contribute to this decrease as well as the overall climate in the society, which is pushing women to more family life and to have more children.

According to national provisions, the age limit (28 years) for candidates for young researcher position is extended for parents (mother or father) who have taken leave for parental care. Researchers-parents have a possibility for part-time work, which is considered as well in the extension of the period of PhD stage. The right to work part-time can be exercised by one of the parents who cares for and protects the child until the age of three. In a case of two children, part-time is extended to the age of 6 years of the youngest child. But due to the career challenges this possibility is rarely used.

It can be concluded that the criteria for career development and promotion are in practice applied equally for both genders, but are not gender sensitive. Moreover, there is no gender sensitive mentoring process in place.

4.3.4 Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

At the JSI, no gender lectures to assist departments on how to mainstream gender equality were held. Gender issues were discussed sporadically when single members of the staff participated in projects that addressed gender issues, but they are very rare. The gender disaggregated data on research funds are not incorporated in the data collection system and not regularly collected, processed or being publicly available. The gender disaggregated data on students (applicants, enrolled, in bachelor/master/PhD study programs and graduates) are also not incorporated in the data collection system neither the gender-segregated data on staff and occupation and gender disaggregated data on the authorship of research articles. The same applies to the membership in decision-making bodies, Promotion commission and head positions.

The JSI does not provide any mentoring programs for female employees corresponding to the gender imbalances among the researchers neither offers training on gender dimension in research. The JSI assures only that both men and women have equal access to internal training, e.g., the adequate timing and form of the training, financial support, etc. There is no specific sabbatical for women scientists and neither for male scientists.

4.3.5 Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

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At the JSI, there is no dedicated organizational arrangement (office, contact person, etc.) for change towards gender equality or any formal institutional background to support gender equality in the organization and research. The responsible bodies with the mandate to objectively and independently monitor the discrimination on gender have not been established so far. A dedicated committee responsible for harassment at the institutional level is not set yet. Protocol on how to proceed in case of sexual harassment and gender-based violence cases is not fully in place at IJS.

Currently, an act from 2014 on gender-based violence exists at JSI, however, it is not easily found in the JSI acts (stored under the topic; protection of personal data) [17]. Promotion of awareness measures to prevent harassment and sexist attitudes is not in place, while a contact point for reporting mobbing cases and getting legal information as help to a victim regardless of gender was established recently.

4.3.6 Needs identified for GEP actions

Based on the described situation above the following needs are presented as diagnosis for GEP actions.

1. Need to redesign the mandatory promotion criteria with flexible performance method

The main problem for the advancement and promotion of female researchers and their continuation of scientific careers is the 9-month mandatory visit to the academic institution abroad in the period soon after PhD graduation. This strict rule causes many women and also some men leave the JSI and find jobs in environments, even academic ones, without this kind of requirement. The essence of postdoc training is based on the need for acquiring knowledge and skills that are not available at the home institution and in establishing of international contacts. Therefore, parents with small children who cannot travel to postdoc abroad are already in unequal position. Even more, the rule of the obligatory postdoc stage abroad is set for the period when researchers do not have a permanent position at the JSI and they cannot get security or contract that they will be reemployed at the JSI after the return. The flexible promotion criteria for younger researchers and flexibility in performance at a more senior stage (as for example breaking the visit to a foreign academic institution in smaller chunks) seems to be appropriate solutions.

2. Need for more flexible daily work time

Flexible working hours with work from home/teleworking and use of surplus hours for absence from work is still not widely desired/supported by JSI work documents and the decision makers, although these measures would contribute to easier harmonization of work and family obligations, especially in the period when researchers have small children. It would also have an overall beneficial effect on work-life balance and well-being of all employees. This needs a re-design of the JSI work documents.

3. Need to establish a Human resources (HR) unit

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Currently, JSI has no HR unit to handle different aspects of the employees life cycle. Heads of departments and units decide on the employment of the new staff only according to the needs they have identified through their vision, available financial resources, and work needs. There is also no institutional policy on gender balancing when hiring new staff, gender balance in recruitment, career progression, and promotion of underrepresented gender. There are no specific leadership programs or sets of rules for assuring gender balance in the bodies where decision-making processes are run. Researchers and other staff applications for the decision-making positions are not supported or encouraged. HR unit is necessary to be set as it will provide all necessary information for promotion, career progression and the possible flexibility of the required method for promotion after PhD graduation. HR is expected to provide services not only for researchers but also for other employees. There is a strong need for career development plan to be set for the technical and administrative staff at JSI as well. The HR unit will serve as a contact point as well for reporting mobbing or sexual harassment, preparing preventive measures and rules of behavior (what is appropriate and what is not in regard to gender equality) for the heads, researchers and other employees.

4. Need for taking mandatory actions and setting rules for balanced composition of the decision-making bodies by age and gender, and withdrawal of the practice of unlimited duration of mandates

Gender composition of decision-making bodies does not reflect the ratio of female researchers at the JSI and gradually decreases with time in contrary to the increasing number of female researchers in the previous periods. The number of mandates in the Scientific Council and as Head of department or a JSI unit is not limited. The number of mandates in the Commission for academic promotion is also not limited and sometimes retired researchers are still long-time members and they influence the promotions policy. Alternation is not implemented in any position. A strong concentration of power built by the occupation of a few powerful decision-making positions by the same person(s) is still a problem present for decades. A large majority of the staff is pushed away from leading regardless of their abilities and competence. A few people who occupy triple or in some cases quadruple decision-making positions for years are extremely busy. Therefore, such a position is not attractive for women or parents at an age when they have to take care of children and simultaneously advancing their scientific career. When they are older, a lack of references in leading positions prevents them to apply for such a position and usually, they lack support from their surrounding. Introducing measures/rules in electing people considering a balanced gender ratio will lead to the desired gender equality in composition of the decision-making bodies. Both genders can and should contribute equally to the work of the JSI decision-making bodies, thus influencing the development of the JSI's working environment.

4.4 Objectives

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Based on the detailed diagnoses of the current situation regarding gender equality at the institute and the identified needs, we have defined the main objectives of the JSI GEP.

Work-life balance has been identified as the most important challenge for female researchers and young parents in their career development. The general objective is to propose changes on the organizational level to improve work-life balance including the revision of the promotion process, help with childcare and regulations for flexible working hours and remote work.

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making is another important area that needs attention, not only due to the low proportion of women in leadership positions but also due to a lack of training and coaching programs for academic leadership. The objective is to encourage women to take a leadership role on different boards at the Institute.

Recruitment and career progression currently lack systematic internal support. The objective is to establish human resources unit and provide trainings on career progression. Obtaining a permanent position at the Institute is very much dependent on having a senior research position, which in the current regulations requires post-doctoral placement abroad. The specific objective is to support career progression of women by providing a possibility of female advisor and relaxing the requirement of post-doctoral placement abroad to be more friendly for young parents while still maintaining high research quality standards in the promotion process.

Integrating the gender perspective and gender dimensions into research is left to each researcher, there is no training or other kinds of support to assist researchers in recognizing different ways to integrate gender perspective and dimensions in their research. Today many research problems involving users, data analysis of users generated data, development of user interfaces, human-computer interaction, IoT etc. have potential for including the gender dimension. The objective is to offer a seminar or training on the topic of gender perspective and dimensions in research accompanied by written guidelines.

Measures against gender-based violence, sexual harassment and mobbing are not established. There is no organizational arrangement or assigned responsible person for handling any misconduct. The objective is to establish guidelines or dealing with this issues and establish a responsible body (trusted persons) to objectively and independently monitor, give advice, report and deal with gender-based discrimination.

4.5 Actions

We have organized the actions according to the five areas addressed in the project. In Table 2 through Table 6 we describe the actions for these five areas:

- 1.) work-life balance and organizational culture,
- 2.) gender balance in leadership and decision-making,

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- 3.) gender balance in recruitment and career progression,
- 4.) integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content and
- 5.) measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

For easier understanding of tables, the important parts of columns are explained. The column “Action” present the actions that have to be taken during the implementation of GEP that address specific issues. The column “Impact assessment” presents the plan to assess the impact which is linked with specific indicators. The column “Success stories” refers to any aspects of success about the action, while the column “Problems encountered” refers to any issue/problem that may arise during the GEP implementation.

To propose changes at the organizational level to improve [work-life balance](#), we will be considering topics such as, internal regulations on research position progression, flexible working hours and remote working, help with childcare etc. In this part, we will also focus on family friendly workplace and we will start with the annual evaluation of gender equality, we will also measure gender disaggregated HR data. To increase awareness of gender balance at the workplace we will promote gender equality and organize seminars, workshops and trainings.

To propose a change of institutional acts toward [equal representation of gender in leadership](#) we will seek support from the director and board members. In this part we will consider equal representation regarding gender, age and limited number of mandates within different boards. We will promote the visibility of women in research and encourage nomination of women for awards, as our data show that we have a low number of women that are nominated for research awards. In addition, we will plan mentoring programs, where rapid skill transfer from the mentor to the mentee will be achieved. In this part, women interested in managerial positions will work tightly with top management representatives (man or woman). We will also organize training and coaching programs for leaders of research groups.

We will seek support from director’s office to establish a HR unit that will also help with [gender balance in recruitment and career progression](#). Part of this process is currently open new employment position for dedicated person on gender equality. We will organize seminars and mentorships for career progression. We will also propose transparent and objective career development, which is partially linked with JSI internal acts.

In this part we propose a strict policy of:

- (a) setting transparent selection criteria for the decision-making bodies at the Institute;
- (b) defining a process of making the openings in any of the decision-making bodies published internally or publicly (depending on the type of the decision-making body) well in advance;
- (c) setting and following a policy of attracting at least 40% of one-gender candidates to the application process in accordance with the national legislation;

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(d) introducing an internal or public (depending on the type of the decision-making body) presentation of candidates and their vision/goals in the decision-making body;

Which should be set in place and followed to incite and develop such a cultural change.

To **integrate gender dimension into research and teaching content** we will organize seminars to educate on the topics of gender equality and equity and we will develop training package on gender sensitive research proposal design to overcome the traditional gender-blind ways of research. We will also promote gender balance for awards, grants, recruitment, where we will provide financial initiatives and recognition to women in research by setting up grants, scholarships, awards, which will be complemented with the proposed mentoring programs. In this part we will also develop guidelines and promote gender-sensitive language in internal documents and acts, and we will propose rules for properly representing gender equality in documents.

Looking broadly at the topic of **measures against gender-based violence** we will develop and adopt internal acts on gender-based violence, increase awareness on this topic by organizing seminars and establish a contact person to whom gender based violence and sexual harassment can be reported. In this part we will also make anonymous sexual harassment surveys to evaluate the situation at JSI regarding this sensitive issue.

Table 2. Actions for JSI GEP - Work-life balance and organisational culture

Action No.	Action	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Propose changes of internal acts	Flexible working hours (childcare / caretaker remote work etc.) Career development criteria for young parents (maternity leave, parental leave) Flexibility regarding postdoc Gender sensitive language in internal acts	2022-2023	Director Secretariat Scientific council HR dedicated person ³	Implement institutional changes Indicators [1-3, 12-15]	Support from director's office Support to implementation of gender inclusive language in internal acts	Acceptance of the proposed changes by different boards at JSI	Discussions and spreading awareness by educational seminars, workshops -Lobbying for changes with the director Formulating proposals for changes in the internal acts and submitting them for consideration to JSI's Scientific Council
2	Annual gender equality assessment	No established assessment system of gender equality No measures for evaluating gender equality and future planning	2022-	Director's office HR dedicated person	Publishing of annual gender equality report including appropriate database All indicators	Reports on increased number of women in research, positions etc.	Lack of human resources	Increase awareness on gender equality by discussion
3	Measure gender disaggregated HR data	No measured disaggregated data at JSI	2022-2023	Director's office Secretariat Service for Business Informatics International	Awareness of gender equality at JSI All indicators	Design of appropriate strategy/action plan	Weak collaboration between different units collecting data	Increase awareness of gender equality and importance of appropriate data by seminars, workshops, successful stories of mixed teams

³ HR dedicated person will start with activity when established by JSI

				Project Office HR dedicated person				
4	Transformation of JSI policy to become family friendly workplace	No support system for young parents	2023-	Director's office HR dedicated person	Implemented family friendly grants/ support Indicators [1-3, 15]	Childcare support services established Flexible working hours established Possibility to use surplus hours for absence from work	Lack of resources Lack of financial resources	
5	Promotion of gender equality at JSI	Limited awareness on gender equality Unconscious bias	2021-	Director's office Athena members ⁴ GEPI committee HR dedicated person	General awareness at JSI on gender equality issues- measured by interviews, surveys Indicators [4-7]	Use of gender sensitive language Increased number of women in research	Low interest on this topic	Increasing awareness by organizing workshops, promotion on webpage, providing yearly data about gender equality in JSI yearly reports
6	Seminars for employees at JSI	Limited awareness on gender equality Unconscious bias	2022-2025	Director's office Athena members GEPI committee HR- dedicated person	Participation of members of different boards Indicator [16]	Educational seminars on JSI web page	Low interest for attending	Encouraging employees to attend by director, heads of departments, and GEPI members Engaging JSI's director for promotion among heads of departments

⁴ Committed to work on the activity for the duration of Athena project

Table 3. Actions for JSI GEP - Gender balance in leadership and decision-making.

Action No.	Action	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Changes of JSI acts for balanced representation regarding gender, age, limited number of mandates at different boards	Low gender balance in leadership positions and decision-making Long-term appointments	2022-	Director Secretariat Scientific council Heads of units HR dedicated person	New institutional internal rules to improve gender balance Increased dynamics of boards members Indicators [17-23]	Increased number of women in different boards and committees /commissions	Acceptance of proposed changes by different boards at JSI	Discussions and spreading awareness also by educational seminars
2	Promote visibility of women in research	Low number of women researchers in the age above 40 Low visibility of women	2023-	Director's office JSI PR office Head of units HR dedicated person	Awareness on successful women at JSI Indicators [8, 24-36]			Promotion of women researchers on JSI's web-page Promote gender-balanced reporting in media
3	Promote nomination of women for awards	Low number of women for awards Unconscious bias	2023-	Director Heads of units HR dedicated person	Number of women receiving awards Indicators [24-36]			Encourage research group leaders to nominate men and women researchers Encourage women researchers to apply for awards

4	Introducing and organizing mentoring programs	Low number of woman leaders, managers No instrument to transfer managing/leadership skills Low number of young leaders	2024	Director's office HR unit ⁵	Rapid skill, knowledge transfer from mentor-mentee and building social networks Indicators [37-44]	Lack of time of potential mentors		Recruiting senior researchers at JSI for mentoring
5	Training and coaching programs for leaders of research groups and other leaders of units at JSI	Lack of skills in leadership	2024-	Director's office HR unit	Indicator [44]	Educational seminars, including on JSI web page Participation of heads of departments and leaders of research groups	Lack of interest	Raising awareness and promotion among unit leaders, especially newly appointed ones

Table 4. Actions for JSI GEP - Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Action No.	Action	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Establish HR unit	Lack of institutional support in career development No support for PhD recruitment	2023	Director	Operational HR unit Indicators [45-47]	New employment of HR dedicated person on gender equality. This is a first step towards	Time to arrange new position for HR, lack of resources	Increase awareness for the need of HR unit Interpersonal support between JSI Athena and GEPI members

⁵ HR unit will start working on the activity, when it will be established at JS

		No system for career progression No support system for young parents and senior women researchers Lack of information regarding career development No support regarding tax system in Slovenia				establishment of the HR unit.		
2	Establishing transparent and objective career development plans	Lack of transparent and objective rules for career development	2024-	Director's office Scientific Council Secretariat HR unit	Clear rules to be published transparently for all JSI staff Indicators [48-55]			Raising awareness on the importance of career planning Formulation of proposal for transparent and objective career development rules
3	Establish a stimulating internal award system	Lack of established system of stimulation for additional tasks Improve visibility of administrative and research responsibilities in units/departments	2025-	Director HR unit	Monitoring of workload (all focus groups) Indicators [59-64]		Lack of skills to develop such system	
4	Organize seminars and mentorships for career progression	No mechanisms for promoting career progression	2023-	Director's office Athena members HR unit	Indicator [44]			
5	Promotion of gender balance for awards, grants,	Low number of women applying and receiving awards Lack of mentoring	2023-	Director's office Heads of units HR dedicated person	Monitoring the number of women who applied and received grants/	Increasing visibility of excellent research of women	Obtaining funds for sponsorship, grants, awards Low interest at JSI for this	Collaboration with other institutions on this topic (Awards for women in engineering etc.)

	recruitment	programs that build skills and increase confidence of women No guidelines to evaluate research projects from gender sensitive perspective			awards indicators [16, 24, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34, 44, 59-64, 66].			
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Table 5. Actions for JSI GEP - Integrating gender dimension into research and teaching content.

Action No.	Action	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Organize trainings for using gender in research and teaching	Limited awareness on gender dimension in research	2024-	Director's office Athena members HR dedicated person	Seminars, workshops, publication on webpage, at JSI news Indicators [65, 66]	Increasing awareness	Low awareness of gender dimension in research, not applicable in all fields of research	Promoting gender dimension in research by organizing workshops and trainings and discussion
2	Use of gender sensitive language at JSI internal acts	Unconscious bias Lack of gender sensitive language in JSI internal acts	2022	See action No. 1.	See action No. 1.	See action No. 1.	See action No. 1.	See action No. 1.
3	Promote the use of gender sensitive language	Unconscious bias Low use of gender sensitive language at public events organized at JSI	2022-	Director's office JSI PR office HR dedicated person				Promote the use of gender sensitive language when organizing events, workshops, lectures...

Table 6. Actions for JSI GEP - Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

Action No.	Action	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Develop and adopt internal acts on gender based violence	Lack of transparent procedures and no broad information for JSI employees about this issue	2023	Director's office Athena members HR dedicated person	Increasing awareness on this topic Change of institutional acts Indicator [69]	Internal acts include issues regarding gender based violence and sexual harassment	Low interest for changes of internal acts No human resources available No data base on gender based violence	Establish evidence/data base on gender based violence at JSI Organizing workshops on gender based violence to increase awareness Visibly published internal rules on gender based violence on JSI's web-page Employment of person for gender equality issues
2	Establish a contact person for handling gender-based violence, mobbing, sexual harassment	No support or contact person available for reporting gender-based violence, sexual harassment	2023-	Director's office HR dedicated person	Establish contact person responsible for handling gender-based violence at JSI Indicators [67, 68]			
3	Workshops on gender based violence	Limited use of gender sensitive language Gender equality not properly represented in JSI internal acts	2022-	Director's office Athena members HR dedicated person	Increasing awareness by organizing workshops Indicator [16]		Low awareness about this issue at JSI	Increase awareness by discussions and organized workshops
4	Anonymous sexual harassment surveys	Lack of information regarding gender based violence and sexual harassment	2023-	Director's office HR dedicated person	Yearly surveys	Available data regarding gender based violence	Lack of personnel for analyzing data and preparation of surveys No support from other units	Raising awareness among JSI's employees Surveys conducted by the person appointed for gender equality

4.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

JSI commits to annual monitoring and reporting on the status of GEP implementation. The GEP will be monitored with the help of indicators and sex/gender disaggregated data and other personal circumstances where possible or accessible. Targets are set according to proposed EU GEP guidelines [16]. Within each area, we have identified several issues that we hope to overcome through implementation of the GEP. The status and progress in the five areas of the EU GEP Guidance will be monitored each calendar year using measurable indicators. The indicators are carefully selected based on the goals we want to achieve through GEP implementation and the issues we want to address.

The main monitoring method is the collection of data (indicators) that form the basis for evaluating both implementation and tracking of changes related to gender equality. They will be collected, reviewed, and reported annually. A majority of the data will be collected primarily by the Secretariat and the HR unit. The heads of these departments are responsible for collecting the necessary information for the periodical monitoring. The GEPVISION program developed within Athena project (or other appropriate software) will be used to analyse and present the collected information. The collected data will be closely reviewed by Athena members during the project period and the GEPI committee. The criteria for the selected indicators are closely related to the assessment of the current situation and GEP actions to become an organization with equal opportunities for all employees regardless of gender. The reports prepared by HR team will be also submitted to the JSI Annual Report, web page and the Scientific Council.

Assessment of the data (status of gender equality at JSI, based on the data) and update of the GEP is responsibility of the Director, Director's Office, GEPI Committee and the dedicated person for gender equality. The responsibility for adoption of the new GEP is on the director and the Scientific Council of the JSI.

JSI is committed for annual monitoring and reporting on the implementation status of the GEP. During the Athena project, the Athena members will be responsible to monitor the entire planning and implementation of the GEP, and later the main responsibility will be transferred to the HR unit which will be established during the project duration. GEP will be monitored with the help of indicators and data disaggregated by gender and other personal circumstances, where this is possible or accessible. The targets are set according to the proposed EU GEP guidelines. Inside each area, we have identified different issues we want to overcome by implementing GEP. The status and progress of the five areas in the EU GEP Guidance will be monitored using measurable indicators each calendar year. The indicators are carefully selected based on the goals we want to achieve by GEP implementation and the issues we want to address.

4.6.1 Work-life balance and organizational culture

To improve work-life balance and organizational culture, we identified 6 main actions which cover different issues identified in WP2 and WP3 as follows. The indicators that

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address work-life balance and organizational culture are numbered and listed below. Some of the indicators can give us useful information in different actions and will be evaluated accordingly.

The status of Action no. 1: **Propose changes of internal acts** will be monitored by the indicators [1-3, 12-15]. Particularly, to monitor if an environment with flexible working hours was established will be monitored by indicators [1, 2, 3], friendly and appropriate career development criteria for young parents (maternity leave, parental leave) will be monitored by indicators [2, 12-15], while adequate flexibility regarding postdoc will be monitored by indicators [15].

The status of Action no. 2: **Annual gender equality assessment** will be monitored by the indicators [1-70][1-72] and GEPI committee. Particularly, to monitor, if an assessment system of gender equality was established, indicators [5-12] will be used, while to monitor if there are adequate measures for evaluating gender equality and future planning will be assessed by GEPI committee.

The status of Action no. 3: **Measure gender disaggregated HR data** will be monitored by the indicators [1-70][1-72]. Particularly, an issue of low number of women researchers in the age 40+ will be monitored by indicator [8], while an issue of measured disaggregated data at JSI will be monitored by indicators [4-7,9-11].

The status of Action no. 4: **Transformation of JSI policy to become family friendly workplace** will be monitored by the indicators [1-3, 15].

The status of Action no. 5: **Promotion of gender equality at JSI** will be monitored by the indicators [4-7]. Particularly, the status of an issue of limited awareness of gender equality will be monitored by GEPI committee, while unconscious bias will be monitored by indicators [4, 5, 7].

The status of Action no. 6: **Educational seminar for employees at JSI** will be monitored by the indicator [16]. Particularly, awareness of gender equality will be monitored by GEPI committee, while how skilled are employees in gender bias (unconscious bias) will be monitored by indicator [16].

4.6.2 Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making is a very important area that needs attention and will be addressed through 5 main actions. Indicators used for this section are listed below.

The status of Action no. 1: **Additional request for JSI acts for balanced representation regarding gender, age, limited mandates at different boards** will be monitored by indicators [17-23]. Gender balance in leadership position and the decision-making bodies is easily monitored by the proportion of women at these positions. The issue of long-term memberships will be monitored by indicators [71, 72].

The status of Action no. 2: **Promote visibility of women in research** will be assessed by the annual monitoring of indicators [8, 24-36].

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The status of Action no. 3: **Nomination of women for research awards** will be monitored by the indicators [24-36].

The status of Action no. 4: **Introducing and organizing mentoring programs** will be monitored by the indicators [37-44]. The issue of low number of women leaders and managers will be monitored by the indicators [38-41, 43]. An assessment if there is an appropriate instrument to transfer managing will be monitored by [GEPI committee], while an assessment if employees have gained leadership skills will be monitored by the indicator [44]. The issue of low number of young leaders will be monitored by the indicators [37, 39, 42, 43].

The status of Action no. 5: **Training and coaching programs for leaders of research groups** will be monitored by the indicator [44].

4.6.3 Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Action no. 1: **Establish HR unit** is planned to be realized in 2023-2024. Its performance will be assessed based on how it faces the issues identified in the GEP. HR unit will be able to monitor specific data (indicators) that are important for the identification of the progress or lack of it [45-47]. Training and coaching actions can be provided for individuals or specific target groups [16].

The status of Action no. 2: **Development of transparent and objective career development** will be monitored by the indicators [48-55]. We will monitor gender dimension in different research fields [52-58] to establish as much as possible gender-balanced teams.

The status of Action no. 3: **Establish stimulating internal award system** that will be monitored by indicators [59-64]. Providing additional financing and/or educational seminars to stimulate employees who do extra work and who are eager to progress in their careers (administration, researchers, technicians, accounting etc.). This data will be carefully monitored to prevent any conscious or unconscious gender biases.

The status of Action no. 4: **Organize educational seminars and mentorships for career progression** will be monitored by the indicator [44].

The status of Action no. 5: **Promotion of gender balance for awards, grants, and recruitment** will be monitored by the indicators [16, 24, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34, 44, 59-64, 66]. The number of women applying and receiving awards will be monitored by indicators [24, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34]. An issue of lack of mentoring programs that build skills and increase confidence of women will be monitored by the indicators [16, 44]. Trainings for using gender in research and teaching will help to set some guidelines to evaluate research projects from gender sensitive perspective [66].

4.6.4 Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

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The status of Action no. 1: **Organize trainings for using gender in research and teaching** will be monitored by the indicators [65, 66]. Limited awareness on gender dimension in research will hopefully increase with the trainings organized at JSI. The number of projects that have at least partially gender dimension will be monitored by indicator [65].

The status of Action no. 2: **Use of gender sensitive language at JSI** will be the responsibility of Directors office, Legal office, JSI PR office and HR unit and will be monitored by indicators [65, 66], by GEPI committee and HR unit. The use of gender sensitive language in JSI internal acts and the use of gender sensitive language at public events organized at JSI will be addressed and recommendations will be given by GEPI committee, who already proposed the use of gender sensitive language in JSI internal acts and documents.

The status of Action no. 3: **Promotion of the use of gender sensitive language** will be monitored by GEPI committee and HR unit, while this will primarily be the responsibility of Directors office, JSI PR office who promote the use of appropriate language. The institute will promote the use of gender sensitive language at public events organized at JSI as well as on its web pages. HR unit, when established will also organize workshops on this topic to promote the use of gender sensitive language.

4.6.5 Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

The status of Action no. 1: **Develop and adopt internal acts on gender-based violence** will be monitored by the indicators [69]. Lack of transparent routes and no broad information for JSI employees about this issue will be regulated by internal acts related to the gender-based violence.

The status of Action no. 2: **Establishment of a contact person for handling gender-based violence, mobbing, sexual harassment** will be monitored by the indicators [67, 68].

The status of Action no. 3: **Workshops on gender-based violence** will be monitored by the indicator [16]. Workshops will address topics on use of gender sensitive language and raise awareness of the presence of gender equality topics in JSI internal acts.

The status of Action no. 4: **Anonymous sexual harassment surveys** will be monitored by the indicators [70]. Information regarding gender based violence and sexual harassment will be transmitted during the seminars and via JSI webpage “IJS za enake možnosti”.

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List of indicators to monitor the GEP actions:

- [1] Annual number and percentage of researchers on maternity/paternity or parental leave in the given year, by gender
- [2] Number of researchers working part-time due to the childcare, by gender
- [3] Number of working days researchers used for care on an annual basis, by gender
- [4] Proportion (%) of women among total number of employees in the organisation (all types of contracts)
- [5] Number of women and men in the administration and support units
- [6] Proportion (%) of persons employed part-time among researchers by gender
- [7] Distribution (%) of researchers employed, by gender
- [8] Distribution (%) of researchers employed across age groups, by gender; (Age cohorts: <25, 25-34; 35-44; 45-54; 55- 64; 65 and over)
- [9] Distribution (%) of researchers in the field of Electronics and Information Technology, by gender
- [10] Distribution (%) of researchers in the field of Physics and Reactor Engineering, by gender
- [11] Distribution (%) of researchers in the field of Chemistry, Biology, Materials and Environmental Sciences, by gender
- [12] Number of female and male researchers (Ph.D.) who left JSI in a calendar year, by gender
- [13] Number of researchers (Ph.D.) who went abroad for postdoctoral training in a calendar year, by gender
- [14] Number of researchers (Ph.D.) who returned from postdoctoral training abroad in a calendar year and (re) employed at JSI, by gender
- [15] Number of applicants who applied for national funding within two years after maternity or parental leave
- [16] Number of seminars and trainings on gender equality organized at JSI in a calendar year
- [17] Women among Directors in previous term and current year
- [18] Proportion (%) of women among Vice-Directors (board of vice-directors) in the previous term and current term
- [19] Proportion (%) of women in the JSI Scientific Council
- [20] Proportion (%) of women among Heads of Departments and Centres
- [21] Members of the Election Committee, by gender
- [22] Members of the JSI Director's Expert Committees: Expert Council, Expert Councils of Research and Infrastructure Areas, Investment Commission, Nuclear and Radiation Commission, Reactor Safety Committee, by gender
- [23] Number of women and men nominated (by JSI) to the Commissions or committees of institutions operating in the field of science (Slovenian Research Agency (SRA), Ministry for Education, Science and Sports, SPIRIT and elsewhere where JSI is invited to nominate candidates)
- [24] Number of women and men nominated by JSI for the Zois Award
- [25] Number of women and men among Zois Award winners
- [26] Number of women and men nominated by JSI for Zois recognition
- [27] Number of women and men among Zois Recognition winners

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- [28] Number of women and men nominated by JSI for the Puh Award
- [29] Number of women and men among the winners of Puh awards
- [30] Number of women and men nominated for the JSI Golden Emblem Prize
- [31] Number of women and men among the winners of the JSI Golden Emblem Prize
- [32] Number of women and men nominated for the Blinc Award
- [33] Number of women and men among the winners of the Blinc award
- [34] Number of women and men nominated for the Blinc Recognition
- [35] Number of women and men among Blinc Recognition winners
- [36] Number of women and men who received JSI awards for the best innovation
- [37] Number of applicants - principal investigators of research funding for a given year in national funds, by gender
- [38] Success rate (by gender) in funding national research projects for JSI researchers as principal investigators in the past year. Difference in success rate in obtaining funding of national research project between men and women as principal investigators from JSI applying for national research funds for the given year
- [39] Number of women and men selected to fund the Early Career Researchers program
- [40] Number of researchers leading an industrial project, by gender
- [41] Number of researchers leading a national research (SRA) program, by gender
- [42] Number of women and men among the proposals for the JSI Director's Fund
- [43] Number of women and men among the winners of the JSI Director's Fund.
- [44] Number of seminars and trainings on leadership skills and career mentorship organized at JSI in a calendar year.
- [45] Average gross monthly earnings of employees of the organisation paid in the given year including additional functions and success factors, by gender
- [46] Average gross monthly earnings of researchers paid in the given year, by gender and habilitation level
- [47] Number of years between first and full-time employment - for female and male researchers
- [48] Distribution (%) of R&D staff by level of education and gender
- [49] Proportion (%) of women among academic staff, by academic grade
- [50] Proportion (%) of A grade women (professors) among all A grade staff by the main fields of Research and Development
- [51] Number of applicants for Young Researchers grants, by gender
- [52] Proportion (%) of women among PhD applicants
- [53] Proportion (%) of women among new PhD students in the given year
- [54] Proportion (%) of women among all PhD students
- [55] Proportion (%) of women among PhD graduates in calendar year
- [56] Proportion (%) of women among new doctors in a calendar year in the field of Electronics and Information Technology
- [57] Proportion (%) of women among new doctors in a calendar year in the field of Physics and Reactor Engineering

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- [58] Proportion (%) of women among new doctors in a calendar year in the field of Chemistry, Biology, Materials and Environmental Sciences
- [59] Number of all doctors who were employed at JSI in a calendar year, by gender
- [60] The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects conducted by men and women - principal investigators from national research funds at the level of organisation for a given year (EUR)
- [61] The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects conducted by men and women - principal investigators (international research funds) (at the level of organisation) for a given year (EUR)
- [62] Number of applicants - national coordinators within an international consortium of research funding for a given year in international funds, by gender
- [63] Number of applicants within an international consortium of research funding for a given year in international funds, by gender
- [64] Number of beneficiaries - national coordinators within international consortium of research funding for a given year in international funds, by gender
- [65] Number of projects involving the gender dimension in the calendar year
- [66] Number of trainings for using gender in research and teaching.
- [67] Number of people involved in violence and sexual harassment at JSI
- [68] Number of cases considered
- [69] Internal acts on gender-based violence,
- [70] Yearly survey.
- [71] The number of researchers (by gender) who have taken on a new role or membership on one of the decision-making JSI bodies in the last year
- [72] The number of researchers (by gender) who have taken on a new role or membership on one of the decision-making bodies in the past year, and for whom this is the first role on a body.

4.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

Dissemination strategy is of high importance for successful implementation of GEP. Basically, dissemination is planned through; i.) JSI webpage (webpage for gender equality is created), ii.) workshops and trainings organized by GEPI committee for JSI, ii.b) emails which will advertise these educational activities, sent to all JSI employees, iii.) publication of articles in JSI news and other relevant publications, iv.) increasing awareness at JSI by proposing institutional changes regarding gender equality and v.) active participation of our members at different events organized on this topic outside JSI.

The main strategy for dissemination is to provide as much as possible information regarding gender equality at [JSI on its webpage](#) and by this increase awareness on this topic at JSI. We have established website "IJS za enakost spolov" or in English "JSI for gender equality" (<https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakeMoznosti>), which is created on the institutional (JSI) webpage. This page provides short information about the Athena project with the link to Athena webpage and current news on this topic. The page also includes information regarding gender equality at JSI: i.) decision on the action plan

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for GEP signed by the director, ii.) the proposed use of gender sensitive language at JSI and its internal acts, iii.) education, where educational seminars are available for all employees, iv.) news, where we publish relevant events regarding gender balance (International women's day, international day of women in engineering etc.), v.) the GEPi committee, which is available only for the GEPI members.

One of the primary dissemination strategies is also to **deliver trainings** (also part of WP3) on gender equality to all employees at JSI. Five trainings are planned, which will be organized by the GEPI committee in collaboration with the external expert. We plan to organize trainings on 5 relevant topics for JSI; i.) Unconscious bias, which is already available online on our institutional website and it will still be further disseminated by organizing workshop on this topic, ii.) Work-life balance and organizational culture, iii.) Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making, iv.) Gender equality in career progression and recruitment, and v.) Ethics and integrity in research. The trainings will be organized online or live, depending on the Covid situation. In both cases the trainings will be recorded and used for further dissemination at our institute- they will be made available on our website.

Another important tool for dissemination at JSI is also the **JSI news** which is published every 3 months. In this newsletter, which is printed as well as available online, we plan to publish different articles and posts on this topic to present the current status and increase awareness on gender equality. So far, we have published an article about forming GEP at JSI within Athena project [18], which was followed by two articles on the current situation at JSI regarding gender equality; i.) the article by Prof.Dr. Maja Remškar about gender equality at JSI [12] and ii.) the article about the ratio of women in leadership positions (heads of departments) by Prof.Dr. Miha Čekada [13]. We also published an article to mark International Women in Engineering Day [19]. Other relevant publication will follow and if possible, they will be disseminated also in other relevant publications to increase recognition also outside the JSI.

Dissemination is foreseen also by **proposing institutional changes by the GEPI committee** to different boards and commissions at JSI. The proposed changes will increase awareness and initiate discussions on this topic also at higher management and decision-making bodies at JSI, which are partially also already included in the Athena project. Just recently the GEPI committee proposed the new rules for the use of gender sensitive language in JSI internal acts and it will be evaluated at different levels at JSI for its use. In this part not only researchers but also other employees will become more aware about the gender equality and further discussions, ideas regarding institutional changes will follow.

Dissemination outside JSI is also planned, we have already collaborated in different meetings and round tables regarding gender equality, which were organized outside JSI. For example, i.) Round table on Gender Equality University of the future, ii.) Commission for equality in science: Where are women candidates for promotion and awards, decision makers and academics? iii.) Horizon Europe presentation on gender

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equality plan for JSI. We plan to continue with this type of dissemination also in the future.

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4.9 Annex

Training plans

Module 1: Unconscious bias (mandatory topic addressing the staff and decision-makers)

- 1.) *Examine the arguments that support the value of gender equality and diversity in RPOs/RFOs.*
- 2.) *Outline the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making.*
- 3.) *Explore examples and case studies of unconscious bias.*

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- 4.) *Examine cases in research where the inclusion of gender issues led to successful outcomes.*
- 5.) *Explore how the gender dimension can be considered at each phase of the research.*

Module 2: Work-life balance and organizational culture

- 1.) *Understand the relations between gender equality, organizational culture in research and academic environments and work-life balance.*
- 2.) *Learn and discuss about the inspiring practices for possible interventions and policies.*

Module 3: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making

- 1.) *Understand the main concepts and concerns regarding gender equality in leadership positions.*
- 2.) *Understand the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making.*
- 3.) *Become familiar with tools to improve institutional gender balance in leadership positions and decision-making.*
- 4.) *Learn about successful implemented measures to improve gender balance on leading positions.*

Module 4: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment

- 1.) *Learning about positive practices to overcome inequalities in recruitment and promotion.*
- 2.) *Understand and recognize the existing gender imbalances and bias in research organizations in career progression and recruitment.*

Module 5: Ethics and integrity in research

- 1.) *Importance of ethics and integrity in research. Examples of omitting ethical principles.*
- 2.) *Understand and recognize existing problems in research organizations. Propose solutions.*

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Additional modules- for discussion and approval by the GEPI members and Athena:

Module 6: The gender dimension in research

- 1.) *Examine how gender considerations are incorporated into research and the importance of these throughout the research process.*
- 2.) *Introduce participants to gender mainstreaming: Commitment to including gender issues at research in Europe.*

* Module 7: How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment

- 1.) *Understand the concepts of gender-based violence and sexual harassment and related debates*
- 2.) *Raise awareness about the importance of policies to fight gender-based violence*
- 3.) *Understand gender-based violence in research institutions and the gender bias that exists within institutional cultures*
- 4.) *Learn about practices to improve policies to fight against sexual harassment at work, with focus on RPOs/RFOs*

* Module 8: Tools for an inclusive language (topic proposal from FRCT)

- 1.) *Know the main international and national legal and political instruments on equality between men and women.*
- 2.) *Use inclusive language, either in a gender-neutral way or referring to both sexes.*
- 3.) *Acquire tools to apply inclusive language.*
- 4.) *Reflect on misogynistic machismo strategies designed to interfere in women's power of speech, focusing on the concepts: maninterrupting, bropropriating and mansplaining.*
- 5.) *Practice and reflect on inclusive language application exercises.*

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Gender Equality Plan

Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
(UJK)

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5. UJK Gender Equality Plan

5.1 Introduction

One of the most important challenges facing European society is the elimination of all types of discrimination. Therefore, Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce joins other European institutions that have set the goal of equalizing opportunities in research career development and takes action to create a safe place to work, which gives the opportunity for development based on equality and diversity of employees, students and doctoral students.

Building a work environment that ensures the harmonious development and interaction employees, is one of the University's priorities.

Equality of opportunity means a state in which women and men have equal social value, equal rights and responsibilities, as well as equal access to social resources (e.g. public services, labour market).

It is a situation in which everyone, regardless of gender, can develop freely in the family and professionally, and to make decisions based on their needs, dreams and ambitions.

The Gender Equality Plan is not only the realization of the idea of equality, but also a set of solutions created based on EU and national legislation.

The Treaty of the European Union in Article 2 states that the European Union is founded on the values of respect for dignity of all human beings, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, as well as respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common Member States in a society founded on pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance justice, solidarity and equality between women and men.

The European Commission in its Communication on Strengthening the European Research Area recommends the removal of all legal and organisational obstacles which constitute barriers to the recruitment.

The European Commission, in its Communication on Strengthening the European Research Area, recommends the removal of all legal and organisational barriers to the recruitment or development of researchers.

According to the Anti-discrimination Standard developed by the General Council for Science and Higher Education (...) matters related to the phenomenon of discrimination deserve great attention from the academic community academic community (...), academic space should be free from any form of discrimination (...) academic space should be free from any form of discrimination, and any manifestation of discrimination should be strongly counteracted. (...) it is worth considering enriching the statutes of universities with relevant provisions, as the most important internal documents regulating (...) it is worth considering enriching the statutes of universities with relevant provisions, as the most important internal acts regulating their operation".

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Provisions concerning the problem in question are reflected, among others, in such acts of law European Union law, such:

- Council conclusions of 7 March 2011. - European Pact for Gender Equality(2011-2020) (OJ EU C 155, 25.05.2011, p. 10);
- Europe 2020: A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth inclusive growth (COM(2010) 2020 final);
- Directive 75/117/EEC on the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women (OJ L 204, 21.7.1975, p. 37) and women;
- Directive 76/207/EEC on equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions (as amended in 2002);
- Directive 86/378/EEC on equal treatment in occupational social security schemes social security schemes (as amended in 1996);
- Directive 92/85/EEC on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding and pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding;
- Directive 96/34/EC on the framework agreement on parental leave;
- Directive 2006/54 EC on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation.

As indicated above, the creation of the Gender Equality Plan for Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce for 2022-2025 was also based on national legislation.

Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland indicates that a man and a woman in Poland have equal rights in family, political, social and economic life, in particular the equal right to education, employment and promotion, to equal pay for work of equal value, to social security and to occupy positions, perform functions and obtain public dignities and distinctions.

In the Act of 26 June 1974. - Labour Code (Journal of Laws of 2020, item 1320 as amended) has a chapter entirely devoted to equal treatment in employment. The provision Article 183a(1) introduces the obligation not to discriminate on the basis of sex in employment.

The Act of 3 December 2010 on Implementation of Certain Provisions of the European Union on Equal of equal treatment (Journal of Laws of 2020, item 2156) contains definitions of direct discrimination, indirect

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harassment and sexual harassment, and furthermore sets out standards for equal treatment of women and men in relation to public services.

Gender Equality Plan for Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce for 2022-2025 is a guide for the whole academic community in the area of equalising opportunities for women and men and creating opportunities for professional development,

Designed and developed as part of the Horizon 2020 - Athena project "Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of research performing organizations (RPOs) and research funding organizations (RFOs) in Europe".

The plan is an integral part of the policy of Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce concerning the development of University as a socially responsible institution and complements the already implemented institutional solutions institutional solutions based on the following internal legal acts:

- Resolution No. 39/2018 of the Senate of the Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce of 24 May 2018 on the adoption of the Code of Ethics for Academic Teachers at the Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce;
- Order No. 83/2020 of the Rector of Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce of 7 April 2020 on introducing the Work Regulations at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce (amended by Order No. 274/2020 of November 9, 2020);
- Order No. 160/2020 of the Rector of Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce of 11 August 2020 on granting the Regulations on remuneration of employees of the Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce;
- Decree No. 80/2021 of the Rector of Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce of 7 June 2021 on introducing the Regulations for counteracting mobbing and discrimination at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce;
- Circular letter No. 1/2022 of the Rector of Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce of 22 February 2022 on the introduction of guidelines for the application of the principles of Open, Transparent and Substantive Recruitment of OTM-R Researchers at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce.

The Gender Equality Plan for Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce is an action strategy planned for four years, which foresees an annual internal evaluation.

The Gender Equality Plan for UJK includes:

- ✓ a diagnosis taking into account the results of the analysis of the existing state and the most important conclusions from the research conducted so far as part of the Horizon 2020 Athena project in the year 2021 at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce;

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- ✓ main objective of the Plan foreseen for the first four years with indication of detailed objectives specific actions and indicators needed for their monitoring.

5.2 Development process and GEP management

The plan was developed and will be implemented in accordance with the methodology of the Gender Equality in Academia and Research Tool (GEAR Tool)⁶ methodology.

Gender Equality Plans Implementation Committee (GEPI Committee), hereafter referred to as the Committee, was established to develop the Plan. Members of Committee members represent different areas and functions within the academic community and are also representatives of the target groups of the Plan: senior and middle management, academic staff and administration. The establishment of the Committee was necessary in order to create an equal opportunity policy that takes into account the needs of all groups in the UJK academic community. Involving direct beneficiaries in strategy development is a participatory approach that increases the chances of success of the developed solutions in the long term.

In developing the Gender Equity Plan, Committee members and representatives of faculty and administration and administration were able to participate in discussions during focus groups and training (focus groups and training on how to plan and implement this document at research institutions, as well as courses on unconscious research institutions, as well as courses on unconscious bias and inclusive language. inclusive. Committee members are involved in each phase of the work of developing, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the Plan. This is critical to ensuring that the measures and actions proposed in the document lead to systematic change at the institutional level.

An audit and assessment of gender equality at the organizational level is the first of the steps of data collection for the development of Gender Equality Plans.

The diagnostic is the result of research conducted from March to December 2021 by a dedicated team. It was developed based on the following elements:

- analysis of statistical data (as of the end of 2020) obtained in cooperation with, among others, the Department of Human Resources Department, Payroll Department, Education Department, Science Department, Doctoral School, Project Management Centre Projects;
- analysis of qualitative data on institutional arrangements in the area of gender equality;

⁶ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

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- analysis of data from 20 in-depth interviews (story telling) conducted among research, research and teaching staff; data analysis of 20 in-depth interviews conducted among research, research and teaching staff with different age, gender and function;
- analysis of data obtained during four focus group interviews with employees representing various functions and positions (managerial staff, administrative academic staff) and students;
- data analysis from the survey (CAWI); the survey questionnaire was addressed to the entire University academic community in order to obtain the opinions of employees with regard to working conditions, opportunities and barriers to professional development, and discriminatory practices;

The data were grouped into six dimensions⁷:

- 1) the pool of graduate talent - refers to the gender balance pool of graduate talent - refers to the gender balance of doctoral students, candidates, undergraduates and graduates, representing the supply of future researchers; qualitative assessment indicators in this dimension evaluate actions encouraging women and men to pursue research careers;
- 2) gender balance in research - refers to the distribution of staff by gender, including academic staff by degree and other characteristics, as well as the gender equality policies implemented in the university;
- 3) gender balanced career advancement - assesses the programmes and instruments used in the organization evaluates the programmes and instruments used in an organisation that promote women and men in their professional development;
- 4) gender balance in decision making - shows the distribution of women and men in decision-making positions at all levels of the organisation;
- 5) gender balanced working conditions - examines the organisation's instruments and policies to support work-life balance, as well as the instruments and policies that support work-life balance examines the organisation's instruments and policies to support work-life balance as well as standards to prevent sexual harassment in the workplace;

⁷ EC (2019). She Figure 2018; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019; Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>; EC (2019). She Figures Handbook 2018; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019; Available at: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/09d777dc-447c-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>; EIGE (2016). Gender Equality In Academia And Research, Gear Tool; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016; Available at: https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/mh0716096enn_1.pdf; OECD (2015), Frascati Manual 2015; Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/frascati-manual.htm>

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6) gender balance in research output - shows the distribution of gender balance in research output - shows the distribution of women and men in research teams, the effectiveness of fundraising, projects, and approaches to gender issues in teaching and research undertaken.

Interviews (story telling) conducted among university teachers identified attributes of gender consciousness, factors allowing or disallowing career advancement academics, and factors facilitating or hindering the attainment of senior positions in the University.

During focus group interview meetings, information was gathered about challenges, barriers and needs in maintaining equal opportunities in science, as well as in the area of work organization at different levels among all UJK employees. Moreover, suggestions for the formulation of the Gender Equality Plan were also obtained.

Using the methods described above, information was collected in five areas:

- 1) organizational culture and work-life balance;
- 2) balance at the decision-making level;
- 3) balance in career development;
- 4) gender in research and teaching;
- 5) countering gender violence.

The methodology presented was developed among representatives of European research institutions, based on good practice and new knowledge, with the utmost care, reliability, and scientific standards.

5.3 Diagnosis

5.3.1 UJK employees by gender

The first step in analyzing the situation at the organizational level was to examine the current distribution of particular variables by gender among all persons employed in research, research and teaching positions, including degrees research, research and teaching positions, including academic degrees and administrative positions (Table 1). and administrative positions (Table 1). From the data collected on employees employed overall shows that women predominate in the organization (K: 60.3%; M: 39.7%). The disproportion gender disproportion is particularly visible in the group of teaching staff (F: 62.9%; M: 37.1%), in which majority are women, as well as in the group of other employees, i.e. administrative, technical employees (F: 70.2%; M: 29.8%). However, it is a common phenomenon in public units, where women prevail in supportive positions. It is worth noticing that in the group of research and research and didactic employees, the gender proportions are balanced (F: 51.2%; M: 48,8%).

Table 7. Number of UJK employees, including women and men (as of the end of 2020)

No	Title of the indicator	Total	Number of women	Number of men	Women [%]	Men [%]
1.	Employees in total	1533	924	609	60,3	39,7
2.	Research, research-didactic employees	713	365	348	51,2	48,8
3.	Didactic employees (inc. lectors)	243	153	89	62,9	37,1
4.	Other employees	577	405	172	70,2	29,8

Source: Athena project own study

Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the gender ratio in different groups of employees is necessary and the possible implementation of appropriate solutions at organisational level.

5.3.2 Organizational culture and work-life balance and private

5.3.2.1 Gender balanced working conditions

UJK has administrative arrangements in place to ensure transparent rules remuneration, including equal level of remuneration, as well as healthy, safe, and mobbing-free working environment, free from mobbing work environment. Nevertheless, the results of the research indicate discrepancies in remuneration of R & D employees - the remuneration of men is 12.1% higher than that of women. In the case of research and teaching employees by 8.9%, and exclusively teaching - by 3.1%.

Among support staff representatives, the difference is smaller at 1.6%. In contrast, the salaries of male professors are 1.7% lower than those of female professors with the same level of achievement.

On the other hand, the results of the in-depth interviews and the conclusions developed during the focus group interviews indicate that working conditions at the University do not put the respondents disadvantaged in comparison to other UJK employees, and the rules in force and the principles in force at the University apply to every employee regardless of gender.

Combining work and family life (work-life balance) is difficult from the point of view of both genders, especially in the case of especially for women who are mothers.

It is worth emphasizing that caring for organizational culture manifests itself, among others, in raising awareness of the academic community by combating stereotypes and prejudices and implementing solutions to create equal opportunities for scientific development.

The analysis leads to the conclusion that UJK lacks additional solutions, especially preventive ones, that go beyond the basic activities required by law.

This indicates the need to create such solutions, mainly concerning working conditions and salaries, but also the need to create a friendly environment in which negative behaviors will be met with a firm response.

One of the actions conducive to a culture that equalizes the chances of women and men for the development of scientific careers and facilitate supporting scientists-parents.

5.3.3 Balance at the decision-making level

5.3.3.1 Gender balance in decision making

The study found differences between women's and men's participation in university governance and individual departments and on committees and other bodies (Table 2). Despite the fact that on the highest position although there is a man on the highest position (it is worth mentioning that in the history of UJK the position of rector was held by a woman), the positions of vice-rectors, deans and vice-deans are significantly dominated by women.

Table 8. Gender balance characteristics in decision-making positions at UJK [%]

No.	Title of the indicator	Women [%]	Men [%]
1.	Rectors (proportion)		
1.1.	Previous term	0	100
1.2.	Year 2021	0	100
2.	Vice-rectors (proportion)		
2.1.	Previous term	50,0	50,0
2.2.	Year 2021	75,0	25,0
3.	Scientific boards	52,0	48,0
4.	Deans of faculties and directors of Institutes	62,5	37,5
5.	Vice-deans of faculties	68,8	31,2

Source: Athena project own study

At Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce there are regulations ensuring appropriate parities in the bodies. However, it is necessary to introduce measures aimed at improving the competences of staff in managerial positions in terms of equality and diversity. The following may serve as an example example is a training programme to improve competences in the area of gender-integrated leadership.

5.3.4 Gender balance in career development

5.3.4.1 Gender balance in research

When analyzing the gender balance in research, i.e., the proportions of women and men who are employees of research and research and teaching staff, the differences have leveled out over the four years. Indeed, in 2016, women in this group accounted for 42.3% and men for 57.7%. In 2020. on the other hand, the share of women was already 51.2% and of men - 48.8%. There are differences in the share of women and

men in scientific fields. The largest number, 40.3% of all female research and research and the majority, i.e. 40.3% of all female research and teaching staff, work in the social sciences, fewer in the humanities (23.0%) and medical sciences (19.2%), the least in natural sciences (17.5%). In the case of men, the largest representation is in the social sciences (34.2%), less in the humanities and arts (22.4%), life sciences (21.8%) and medical sciences (21.3%).

An analysis of applications to doctoral programs by gender (the pool of graduate talent) indicates an equal number of women and men (F: 51.8%; M: 48.2%). However, as far as the number of people graduating from doctoral studies in 2020 is concerned, a significantly higher share of women (70.4%) than men (29.6%).

Women and men have different shares in the groups of employees with the title of professor (K: 29.9%; M: 70.1%), with a post-doctoral degree (F: 46.1%; M: 53.9%). However, among persons with a doctoral degree and a master's degree (assistant professors, assistants, doctoral students) women significantly (Table 3).

Table 9. Academic staff by degree, academic title at UJK

Title of the indicator	Women	Men
Proportion of women and men among academic staff by academic grade (%)	[%]	[%]
Grade A professor	29,9	70,1
Grade B postdoctoral	46,1	53,9
Grade C doctor	61,5	38,5
Grade D master	59,4	40,6

Source: Athena project own study

The presented results (Figure 1) clearly indicate that the development of scientific careers and promotion paths of women and men are not identical. This means that UJK needs to take the necessary steps to necessary to eliminate these disproportions.

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Figure 2. The proportion of women and men among academic staff by degree/title at UJK

Source: Athena project own study

However, when analysing the number of research and research and teaching staff of both genders by by age groups and by academic degrees and titles (Figure 2), we can see a higher number of working female masters in the age group of 25-34 years (F: 39; M: 27) and the same difference in the PhDs (F: 33; M: 20).

Figure 3 Women among research and research and teaching staff by age and grade/title at UJK

Source: Athena project own study

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The 35-54 age range is significantly dominated by women with doctoral degrees. In contrast, considering the age range of 55-65 and above, the top professorial positions male predominate (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Male research and research and teaching staff by age and rank/title at UJK

Source: Athena project own study

The analysis of the data resulting from the application of the Gender balance in research outputs indicator shows, the number of women and men applying for external funding for research projects is similar.

However, a disproportion appears in the statistics on the effectiveness of obtaining a grant

The data indicate that during the surveyed period men were more often (three times) received grants. The projects received seven times more funding compared to those which were awarded to women.

Therefore, it is necessary to implement organizational solutions that will support the use of the staff and at the same time prevent the loss of human capital of the University (losing talents).

Already at the stage of recruiting new employees it is necessary to maintain high standards of transparency. The recruitment of new employees should be done with a high standard of transparency of job advertisements, taking care of the appropriate language of advertisements which will encourage both men and women to apply. It is advisable to support research teams in the recruitment process. It is recommended to support research teams which include young inexperienced staff, doctoral students.

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5.3.5 Gender in research and teaching

The study shows that the issue of gender as a leading theme appears quite rarely in scientific publications or research projects carried out at UJK (Gender balance in research outputs).

Therefore, actions should be taken to encourage research in this area in various scientific fields. It should be emphasised that such research does not only concern equality, but it is important to stress that such research is not only about equality, but can address various aspects with a gender perspective.

Conducting and disseminating research results is an important educational component as it contributes to raising awareness using scientific knowledge, which leads to the combating of established stereotypes or (sometimes unconscious) prejudices.

On the other hand, gender research in different disciplines can serve to develop the scientific and R & D potential of many disciplines, e.g. medical sciences, psychology, sociology, pedagogy, economics.

5.3.6 Addressing gender violence

Qualitative research indicates incidental situations of verbal aggression, as well as instances of incidents of verbal aggression as well as incidents of inappropriate behavior and the use of sexist hate speech between employees at different levels.

Both genders indicate the occurrence of negative language/activity/behavior, mainly towards women, especially those with less seniority, without degrees or titles and working in administration.

The Regulations for counteracting mobbing and discrimination at UJK clearly specify mobbing and discriminatory behaviours, including those referring to and discriminatory behaviors, including those related to gender and sexual behaviors.

It is recommended to promote awareness actions in this area to prevent harassment, sexist attitudes and to promote a culture of language through education and information campaigns for the entire academic community, including students and doctoral candidates.

5.3.7 Qualitative research findings

The results of the qualitative research revealed the following problems and needs:

- Barriers to academic career advancement affect both genders. These include the pressure of evaluation, obtaining many points for publications, constant evaluation according to different criteria, additional duties, which - according to the academic staff - are less appreciated and consume a large part of their time, such as organisational work, teaching load, project work. Academic work

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is often performed "after hours" in different home conditions and at different times, including holidays.

- In the case of women, there is a marked deceleration in career development after the stage of obtaining a PhD. A significant number of women do not continue their scientific path and do not start the stage habilitation stage. This is often due to family responsibilities.
- There are no institutional solutions in place at the University to level the playing field for women in their academic careers.
- Respondents emphasized that access to high positions is equal for both genders. High positions at the University are held by women and men. There are no differences in the responsibilities of those who hold specific functions. These responsibilities are based on the specifics of the positions and not on the fact of being a woman or a man.
- Among those in administrative positions, it is noted that the majority are women. This may reflect a (perhaps unconscious) cultural assignment of female and male roles to specific and male roles to specific positions or functions.
- One group also pointed out the possibility of adopting bylaws (or another document University) with principles supporting equal treatment of genders in various aspects of the University's activities: from employee-employer relations to rules applicable during interviews for job positions at the University. The attorney (coordinator, spokesperson) should be responsible for gender equality policies and should cooperate with the University authorities.
- There is a need to conduct training on gender equality among employees of the University. It also seems necessary to include this topic in the curricula of students (e.g. inclusion of equality and diversity content concerning, among others, gender in the Ethics course).
- Starting a family may inhibit the professional career of women, which relates to the possibility of using maternity and parental leaves, but it has been pointed out. However, it was pointed out that these leaves can also be used by male academics.
- The respondents agree that women, especially at the beginning of the decision on starting a family, are in the most difficult situation when it comes to further professional development and they lose the most.
- Women tend to be more involved in projects, organizational and administrative work than men - this is considered natural.

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- Women do not want to be favored, they do not expect special treatment, they expect to be treated and paid equally for the same work, although one of the areas where they need
- They do not expect special treatment, they expect equal treatment and remuneration for equal work, although one of the areas in which they need additional instruments is motherhood, but they do not treat it as favoring men, but as compensation for lost/deferred development opportunities.

5.3.8 Summary

Analysis of quantitative and qualitative data indicates equal proportions of women and men in the group of academic teachers at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce, with a slight predominance of women.

There is equal access for women and men to conduct scientific research at Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce.

Discrepancies in the development of the scientific career of women and men have been identified, consisting of its slowing down in women with a doctoral degree and problems with scientific promotion.

Gender differences in salaries were identified. They probably result from They are probably due to the different retirement age of women and men and the different gender ratio in the distribution of degrees and titles. scientific degrees and titles. Nevertheless, these discrepancies should be continuously monitored.

In all groups of employees surveyed, gender equality is understood as equal opportunities for development, but not as a balanced representation of women and men in decision-making positions, since the assumption of these positions is related to elections (rector, Senate members) or to scientific development, skills.

Women predominate among those in decision-making positions at the university.

Respondents stated that they have not encountered situations of gender-based favoritism, although one group stressed the need to monitor the observance of gender equality in the recruitment process to work at the University.

In the group of academics, it was stressed that interest in particular fields of study was due to cultural factors rather than institutional barriers. On the other hand, mutual relations among employees and between employees and faculty and University authorities are not determined by gender.

Both men and women do not experience discrimination based on Both men and women do not experience discrimination based on gender.

It is necessary to take action to support the development of scientific careers as well as greater women in research and in obtaining grants.

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Building a culture of gender equality awareness among the academic community is crucial to achieving improvements in this area.

Institutional change should be informed by research findings and reliable, systematically collected data that integrates an intersectional perspective into the management processes of the University.

5.4 Objectives

Considering the results of the diagnosis, UJK has focused its GEP on 7 objectives, in line with the requirements of the European Commission, which will bring it even closer to an organisation promoting an equal organisational culture.

OBJECTIVE: PROMOTING GENDER EQUALITY AWARENESS

OBJECTIVE: BALANCE BETWEEN PRIVATE AND PROFESSIONAL LIFE

OBJECTIVE: CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT OF THE UJK IN THE AREA OF GENDER EQUALITY

OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN ACCESS TO MANAGEMENT AND DECISION-MAKING POSITION

OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN THE RECRUITMENT PROCESS AND ACCESS TO SUPPORT FOR CAREER DEVELOPMENT

OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN TEACHING AND RESEARCH

OBJECTIVE: COUNTERACTING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

5.5 Actions

All actions under each objective are structured around the five thematic areas recommended by the European Commission. Specific objectives and actions are included in the **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 10. Actions for UJK GEP

Content area	General Objective	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	
Work-life balance and organisational culture	OBJECTIVE : PROMOTING GENDER EQUALITY AWARENESS	Objective 1.1. Provide institutional framework and necessary infrastructure for reconciliation of work and family life.	Action 1.1.1. Monitoring and increasing subsidies from the social insurance fund for children's stay in nurseries and preschools	2023-2025	Rector in consultation with the trade unions	Efficient financial support to childcare services for students and academic staff	
			Action 1.1.2. Cooperation with the company nursery/kindergarten	2023-2025	Chancellor	All students and academic/research staff whose children would like to join child care institution at the University have ability to do so	
			Action 1.1.3. Design and implementation of rules for flexible work arrangements and teleworking	2022	Department of Human Resources	All employees regardless of gender and family status have access to flexible work arrangements or ability to plan their work time according their needs	
	OBJECTIVE : BALANCE BETWEEN PRIVATE AND PROFESSIONAL LIFE	Objective 1.2. Improvement in the area of the gender equality	Action 1.2.1. Designing a monitoring system to indicate of changes among ujk community in the area of the gender equality	2023-2025	Athena project team, Gender Equality Ombudswoman, GEPI Committee	Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community	
			Action 1.2.2. Designing of rules/procedures to conducting an audit and preparing gender equality report	2023-2025	Gender Equality Ombudswoman, GEPI Committee, Internal auditor	Precise and accurate gender equality report	
			Action 1.2.3. Updating the plan based on the results of the review/audit conducted	2023-2025	Gender Equality Advocate, GEPI Committee	Up-to-date plans adapted to changes	
			Action 1.2.4. Preparation of annual reports on the implementation of the plan, based on achieved indicators	2023-2025	Athena project team, Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Reports that show changes in the analyzed areas	
	OBJECTIVE: CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT OF THE UJK IN THE AREA OF GENDER EQUALITY	Objective 1.2. Improvement in the area of the gender equality					

			Action 1.2.5. Preparation of Gender Pay Gap indicator every year	2023-2025	GEPI Committee, Payroll department	Changes in Gender Pay gap indicator
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN ACCESS TO MANAGEMENT AND DECISION-MAKING POSITION	Objective 2.1. Continue activities towards equal representation of men and women in the decision-making bodies of UJK	Action 2.1.1. Monitoring number of women and men in decision making bodies of UJK	2023-2025	GEPI Committee Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Percentage number of men and women in decision making bodies of UJK presented in a publicly available report
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN THE RECRUITMENT PROCESS AND ACCESS TO SUPPORT FOR CAREER DEVELOPMENT	Objective 3.1. Percentage number of men and women in decision making bodies of UJK presented in a publicly available report	Action 3.1.1. Maintaining rules of transparency in the recruitment process	by the end of 2022	Internal auditor, Department of Human Resources Department of Science	More women participate in recruitment processes
			Action 3.1.2. Ensuring a high standard of transparency in job advertisements	by the end of 2022	Deans of Faculties, Department of Human Resources	No discrimination in the recruitment process
			Action 3.1.3. Promoting and monitoring gender equality in the recruitment process	2023-2025	Deans of Faculties, Department of Human Resources, Gender Equality Advocate	Achieving a gender balance in employment decisions committees
			Action 3.1.4. Assess needs and develop solutions to facilitate return to work after maternity or paternity leave	2023	Employees' superiors, Department of Human Resources	There are procedures to facilitate return to work after maternity and parental leave More women develop their careers
			Action 3.1.5. Maintaining the transparency of the regulations and criteria for admission to university and doctoral schools	by the end of 2022	Internal auditor, Doctoral School, Department of education	No discrimination in admission process to university and doctoral schools

Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	OBJECTIVE: EQUALITY IN TEACHING AND RESEARCH	Objective 4.1. Ensure that sex and gender analysis is considered in the design and outputs of research and teaching	Action 4.1.1. Establishment of scientific club focused on equality	by the end of 2023; Annual reports	Science and Culture Center	Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community
			Action 4.1.2. Inclusion of the equal treatment thematic into the curricula of BA/MA studies and PhD School	2023-2025	Coordinators of Area Education Quality Teams, University Education Committee, Doctoral School Education Quality Committee	Increased interest in gender equality as a research topic
			Action 4.1.3. Support for research and academic staff as well as PhD candidates in performing research projects with focus on gender equality	2023-2025	Department of Science, Deans of Faculties, Doctoral School, University Library	Increased interest in gender equality as a research topic
		Objective 4.2. Promoting gender equality among members of UJK community	Action 4.2.1. Creation and update of the website or e-learning platform dedicated to gender equality	2023	Athena project team GEPI Committee Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Raised accessibility of information about gender equality among members of the UJK community . Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community.
			Action 4.2.2. Design of e-learning materials regarding gender equality	2022	Athena project team GEPI Committee Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Raised accessibility of information about gender equality among members of the UJK community . Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community.

			Action 4.2.3. Series of events presenting academic and research career pathway from the gender perspective	2023-2025	Athena project team GEPI Committee Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Increased interest in scientific work among women.
		Objective 4.3. Providing trainings on the topics related to gender equality among members of the UJK community	Action 4.3.1. Regular trainings for academic staff, students and PhD candidates, inlc the topic of unconscious bias	2023-2025	Athena project team GEPI Committee Gender Equality Ombudswoman	Raised accessibility of information about gender equality among members of the UJK community . Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community.
Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	OBJECTIVE: COUNTERACTING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE	Objective 5.1. Reduction in the incidence of gender-based violence and building a community free from gender-based violence	Action 5.1.1. Study on awareness of gender-based violence and sexual harassment	2023	Gender Equality Ombudswoman Athena project team	A community free of gender-based violence
			Action 5.1.2. Creation of a methodology for monitoring sexual harassment incidents	22	Gender Equality Advocate, GEPI Committee, University Anti-Bullying and Anti-Discrimination Committee, Disciplinary Ombudsman for Academic Staff	Reduction in the incidence of gender-based violence

5.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

The Gender Equality Plan for Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce is an action strategy planned for four years, which foresees an annual internal assessment.

Responsible person, team, body or department for the periodical monitoring, reporting and assessment are pointed in the GEP.

Appropriate team have been designated for regular data collection.

The monitoring and evaluation methodology of GEP at Jan Kochanowski University in years 2022 – 2024 will follow the methodology that has been workout and will be implemented within Athena Project.

The overall aim is the assessment of the implementation processes and the related practices within Jan Kochanowski University.

Main actions of monitoring and evaluation system will focus on:

- Assessment of progress made on reducing gender inequality
- Identifying implementation practices and their achievements
- Assessment of implemented activities and measures through combining an ex-ante and ex-post perspective
- Assessment target groups satisfaction
- Identifying organizational changes, institutional progress & benefits
- Identifying challenges and barriers

The general aim of **monitoring process** is that the project follows the described GEPs action plans.

In this step it will be investigated whether the way a measure is implemented corresponds to the respective goals and objectives, which factors promote or constrain its implementation, which practices contribute to successfully implemented measures and actions, what benefits they might provide for university and the influence they may have on other (local, regional, or national) RFOs and RPOs.

The main activities under this stage refer to:

- monitoring of the GEP's action plan and an effective on-time delivery of the outputs;
- comparing actual GEP's performance against the action plan;
- identifying, analyzing, tracking, and monitoring existing (and new) resistances;
- maintaining an accurate, timely information base concerning the GEP's outputs;
- monitoring implementation of approved changes as they will occur;
- providing appropriate reporting on the progress and status.

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3 internal monitoring reports in January of years 2023, 2024 and 2025 at the organizational level will be produced and will be used to assess the progress made and the potential improvement to be done.

Annual monitoring reports preparation and presentation to top management has been entrusted to the Gender Equality Ombudsman, Gender Plan Committee and Athena project team.

The aim of the reporting is to provide sufficiently detailed information to check the advancement of the GEP implementation considering its objectives and timetable.

The main objective of **the final assessment - evaluation research** is to **demonstrate to which extent the implementation of GEPs contribute to unlock the research potential of Jan Kochanowski University.**

The ultimate assessment for quality are target groups, and represents how close the outputs and achievements come to meeting the target groups requirements and expectations.

The Athena GEPs outputs and achievements analysis will be based on:

1. Desk research and data analysis on the database of quantitative and qualitative indicators
2. Internal Monitoring Reports analysis
3. On-line satisfaction survey to assess the qualitative satisfaction of the staff

The final impact report will be produced in January 2025 that will summarize the outcomes and the results achieved. Furthermore, it will draw conclusion and recommendations for a better implementation of gender equality interventions in future.

This report should highlight the improvement gained in terms of gender equality and research thanks to the implementation of the GEPs.

A final evaluation will compare the status quo before (ex-ante) and after (ex-post) the interventions have taken place.

Final evaluation will be based on:

- A combined analysis of quantitative and qualitative results
- Significant achievements and failures assessment
- Quality satisfaction survey of the staff.

As it was mentioned above **2 internal monitoring reports and 1 final evaluation report will be produced that will include the monitoring data.**

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The main purpose of reporting is providing information to ensure the implementation of the GEPs, to assist Jan Kochanowski University authorities, GEPI Committee and Ombudman with the implementation of GEPs.

5.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

This section includes a dissemination strategy of the GEP. Following the *Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans*⁸, the GEP should follow the following mandatory requirements:

- The Ombudswomen will be appointed to deal with GEP and disseminate the objectives, activities and monitor the progress.
- The special sub website on the main UJK web site for Gender Equality will be created and updated under the Excellence HR as a topic complementary to the subject matter. It will contain the main information about related activities, Athena project progress, good practices and announcements about training program.
- The GEP signed by the high management will be published in the institution's website and disseminate within the organization by internal channels.
- Awareness raising trainings will be implemented, addressing the topics of unconscious bias.
- The cycle of meetings, conferences will be planned to raise awareness of equality topic within different groups such as students, PhD candidates, research workers, administration staff, management.
- The database of external stakeholders will be provided and regular meeting will be organized to share the experiences and results of the implementation process of GEP in UJK.

⁸ Available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffc06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>

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Gender Equality Plan

University of Bucharest (UB)

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6. UB Gender Equality Plan

6.1 Introduction

The Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest is designed as a result of the institution's participation in the HORIZON 2020 project ATHENA -*"Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe"* (2021-2024). At the end of project, the partner institutions will have developed, implemented and gone through a first phase of monitoring their individual Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). Each plan is, in fact, a strategy adapted to the needs of the institution, based on a prior diagnosis of the current state of affairs, and publicly and transparently assumed by the institution's management.

In the spirit of European requirements, the document contains areas of interest, objectives, measures, activities, responsibilities, dedicated financial and human resources, monitoring tools and implementation deadlines.

The Implementation Committee of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest (GEPI-UB), together with the ATHENA implementation team, based on a documentation of the state of affairs and after a series of consultations with UB employees, proposes **this first Gender Equality Plan for the period 2022-2024**. Following the monitoring and evaluation process, the plan will be reviewed and improved.

The plan is a **strategic** document that articulates UB's institutional commitment to the promotion of gender equality and, implicitly, of inclusive policies in all activities within the institution. It is **realistic**, in that it responds to a prior diagnosis based on data and clearly defines tasks, procedures, resources and deadlines. Last, but not least, it is a **dynamic document** that allows for further changes and developments, based on ongoing dialogues with the entire community.

Gender equality is a fundamental value of the European Union. Universities and research institutions in the European Research Area (ERA) and the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) are strongly committed to establishing themselves as inclusive learning and research spaces, in which excellence is promoted simultaneously with a focus on equal chances and opportunities in general, and gender equality in particular. Excellence, efficiency, innovation, and quality go hand in hand with respect for the principles of equality, equity, and non-discrimination. Promoting measures in the field of gender equality has already proved to be a stimulus for the development of institutions that have adopted such strategies.

The mission assumed by UB is "to obtain the highest quality of educational services and research activity, adopting competitive international standards, and showing a continuous concern for quality assurance, interdisciplinary collaboration, leadership and excellence on the part of teachers and employees." Such a mission cannot be successfully achieved without promoting the principles of gender equality.

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UB started the process of elaborating and implementing its first gender equality plan in a tense global and European context related to the crisis in Ukraine, the effects of the pandemic period, but also to the appearance of more and more visible manifestations of resistance, or even hostility, towards gender equality policies (a phenomenon known as gender backlash).

As the European and Romanian society put into practice the principles of gender equality, institutionalized through various norms in multiple fields, new forms of reproduction of previous inequalities and discriminations have appeared, but also new forms of vulnerability. Despite these new challenges, a number of issues at the national level, related to the situation in higher education in Romania (e.g. favourable legislative framework, growing internationalization process, a historical tradition regarding the numerical balance between women and men in many fields of education and research, the existence of a community of experts on gender equality issues) provides an appropriate framework for launching such initiatives.

A number of premises also anticipate the support of the UB community for the introduction of such plans. From the point of view of members of the academic community, we see a gender representation that provides a beneficial framework for a strategy for gender equality: women constitute the numerical majority in the UB, and the number of those in leadership positions at Rectorship level is increasing compared to previous years. In terms of organizational knowledge, work is being done to improve the integrative database, which already contains, and will be able to further develop, a number of gender-sensitive indicators. Regarding the creation of specialists in the field, UB already has a master's program in the field and a series of courses in which teachers familiar with the fields, integrate the gender dimension. Annually, there are bachelor's, master's, as well as doctorate theses that pay attention to the theme of gender equality. In terms of membership in the global flow of reflection and action on gender equality, the university is engaged in international research networks and projects that also require attention to gender issues.

Documenting an organizational culture from the perspective of gender equality issues is a condition for access to the European research community, especially in terms of obtaining financial support from EU public funds. The formalization of this culture through a Gender Equality Plan signals the UB's orientation towards participation in the dialogic construction of European and national identity. From a procedural point of view, the adoption and implementation of the first Gender Equality Plan at the University of Bucharest will enable teachers and researchers to access European funds for education and research, funds conditioned in the future by the existence of such strategies. At the same time, through this approach, UB will contribute to a better application of the national legislation in force, more precisely of law no. 202/2002, according to which all public institutions in Romania have the obligation to initiate strategies for the sustainable promotion of gender equality, strategies that must be endorsed by the National Agency for Equality between Women and Men (ANES).

In terms of involvement at the institutional level, the Gender Equality Plan will mobilize the reflective and intellectual strength of the University in the service of establishing an open and empathetic academic community anchored in the imperative of treating human beings as a goal, and not as a means; a community sensitive to structural forces and systematic disadvantages starting from the social classification of gender that orders Romanian, European and global society.

By implementing this first Gender Equality Plan, UB will continue to develop an institutional culture based on respect for the values of human dignity, personal autonomy, community support, and moral and scientific integrity.

The document has been approved first by the Administrative Council of the University of Bucharest before being submitted for the final approval by the UB Senate. The University of Bucharest's Senate in the meeting on 20.04.2022 has approved the document.

In terms of areas identified, UB opted for an extended version than the ATHENA diversity and gender standards (see D4.2 – Gender and diversity standards for further information), in which the proposed actions targeted 8 such areas, out of which five were explicitly recommended for inclusion in EU documents. For this first GEP, based on all the preliminary stages of documentation, research and consultation, the following areas of intervention were proposed, as illustrated in the graphic:

Figure 5. Intervention areas within the UB GEP

6.2 Development process and GEP management

The plan was developed under the direct coordination of a UB Implementation Committee (GEPI-UB), a committee that is composed of decision-making representatives of academic and administrative management, teachers, researchers and students. The committee held regular meetings and consultations with UB management representatives from all sectors.

Between February 2021 and February 2022, the project implementation team, with the permanent support of the institution's management and the Gender Equality Plan Implementation Committee (GEPI-UB), provided the documentation, analysis, consultation and communication framework necessary for such a project.

Concretely, the following were considered:

- A Gender Equality Report for the University of Bucharest was prepared. The Report is a two-step analysis of the institutional data and information available in the UB on gender equality. Initially, an inventory was made of the data existing at the start of the project (March 2021). Subsequently, the final report was prepared, which, in addition to completing the data from the first stage, contains the results of a quantitative and qualitative research based on a methodology common to all ATHENA project partners: a thematic questionnaire was distributed to all UB employees, 20 interviews with employees were conducted, and 4 focus groups. This report on gender equality in UB provided a qualitative and quantitative indicative picture which, on the one hand, produced arguments for the need for such a plan, and, on the other hand, provided a first set of suggestions on useful strategies and activities in various areas that ought to be included in the Gender Equality Plan. The report is available on the UB website dedicated to the project (<https://gep.unibuc.ro/>).
- A Compendium of Good Practices at the European level regarding Gender Equality Plans already implemented in other countries was developed and made available to the UB Committee and the University's management. The material is meant to support GEP-UB with information on various common measures and strategies, or already successfully implemented practices by other academic institutions. A number of other reference documents were also provided as part of the Athena project (D4.3 Athena - Toolkit for Transforming the Institutional Cultures in terms of Gender Aspects), in similar projects (TARGET, CALIPER, etc.), or disseminated by the European Commission (Horizon. Europe Guidance on GEPs, EC, 2021). The material is available on the site dedicated to the project (<https://gep.unibuc.ro/>).
- GEPI-UB members participated in three rounds of training on the development of such tools for monitoring gender equality issues in the institution. Two dialogues took place at the Athena Consortium level with all committee representatives and the UB implementation team conducted a final session, specifically for UB.

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- A series of consultation activities were initiated and organized within the UB. Thus, an informal network of female teachers interested in promoting gender equality was initiated (people with expertise in the field, with an interest in and/or a desire to support). So far, two such consultations have taken place in which more than 40 people participated, and the results of the discussions have been forwarded to the Committee and to the Rectorship. The students were also consulted through one-off dialogues in various faculties, as well as through a meeting organized at the level of student associations. The consultation process is ongoing: the official page of the project on the UB website offers, in addition to information about the project, the possibility of collecting suggestions through a short confidential questionnaire (<https://gеп.unibuc.ro/>). A permanent dialogue of GEPI-UB members was also facilitated with the representatives of the Athena Advisory Board, especially with Prof. Univ. Dr. Adrian Curaj, Director of UEFISCDI, Romania's representative on the Board.

In terms of concrete responsibilities for the implementation of the GEP it is foreseen (under implementation of Objective 2/Governance and Gender Equality) a clear formalization of a coordination and supervision body for the promotion of gender equality at UB through a Committee for the Promotion of Gender Equality (GEPI). Its members will work voluntarily, and will be selected ensuring the representativeness of the professional categories in the UB and respecting the gender criterion in the delegation. The start-up team is GEPI-UB, which coordinated the implementation of the GEP. A Gender Equality Office will be also established in the first stage on GEP implementation. In this respect identification and implementation of a selection procedure for an administrative team that will coordinate and monitor the GEP implementation process will be designed.

6.3 Diagnosis

The University of Bucharest is the biggest university in Romania (34.000 students and over 1300 academic staff, 19 faculties⁹). in SWOT language, there are strengths and opportunities, as well as threats and worries in the area of promoting gender equality.

UB has a managerial team with an open interest for promoting gender equality. The number of women in power position at the level of Rectorate is the highest it has ever been; a project of establishing an integrative data base with predefined indicators (including good gender-sensitive ones) is under development; a master programme in Gender Studies (at the Faculty of Political Sciences) exists and a number of gender sensitive courses are taught in different faculties; many bachelor, master and doctoral

⁹ More information at: <https://unibuc.ro/?lang=en>

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theses have an implicit or even explicit gender dimension; some researchers from UB have been involved in a series of gender sensitive research projects; the university also recently launched a campaign “UB for Women in Science” to promote the scientific results of women academics and to open the dialogue about gender equality in the sciences. Last but not least, the increased internationalization process contributes to more contact for UB academics and students with progressive attitudes towards gender equality.

The documentation and research component of the ATHENA project outlined a series of aspects to be considered in the design and implementation of the GEP-UB.

Quantitative data available indicate at first glance an optimistic picture: there are more women than men as graduates across all levels of study at university level, teachers in humanities, social or exact sciences, young employees, as well as administrative staff. However, BA men graduates are more likely to be employed than women, whereas at the MA level the differences decrease. Research outcomes of women translated in professional achievements of higher positions are on average at lower levels and postponed (pipeline phenomenon).

The data from the **staff survey** indicate among other things that: 1) men are more satisfied than women with respect to their position in UB; 2) women have in general lower aspirations compared with men when it comes to managerial positions; 3) the higher women aspire, the less they succeed to top positions (glass-ceiling); 4) stereotypes about gender persists with regards to gender roles and relations and many women are trapped in the “meritocracy and “hard work” myth as key ingredients of academic success; 5) family responsibilities, specially having children, are perceived as impediments for women’s professional carriers (and men also recognize this); 6) the young staff is more affected in the carrier path knowledge advancement by insufficient child care support and administrative responsibilities. In the context of a poor knowledge about gender equality concepts and topics, opportunities for gender informative/sensitive trainings are almost not existing.

In **qualitative terms**, the research indicates that UB employees have diverse, often contradictory opinions about gender equality. This is why gender equality poses numerous dilemmas as a topic of institutional reflection and some of these perceptions will also guide the process and the obstacles around adopting and successfully implementing a GEP. There are at least 3 categories of employees: gender sensitive/knowledgeable, gender blind, and employees that are hostile to gender equality. Most often, the UB staff (including many women) equates gender equality with numerical/essentialist equality, and is rather reluctant to gender equality measures (using mostly arguments of meritocracy, fear of victimization, or claiming that gender equality has already been achieved).

A set of interrelated factors (such as position of power within UB, age, family status, family background) combined with gender proved to play an important role in understanding the differences in their perception and attitudes towards gender equality.

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Among the problems identified by many of the participants in the research process there are certain similarities, such as: reproduction of gender stereotypes present and persistent at societal level; the existence of informal (male) networks of influence and information; family care responsibilities (specially for employees with children) imposing constraints on career development and not being perceived as connected with gender equality topics (mainly work-life balance); low level of knowledge and information in the area of gender equality combined with few training opportunities in this respect; gender violence (in language, sexual and moral harassment) as an unreported phenomenon;

At the start of the implementation of the first GEP in UB (and after the initial diagnosis of gender equality within the university) a set of gender sensitive measures and actions have already been put in place.

- A number of offices within the UB have been mobilized and designated as co-responsible for implementing GEP actions. Some such structures are: The University of Bucharest Statistical Office, The Quality Assurance Committees within each Faculty and at UB level, the Ethics Committee of the University of Bucharest, the Ombudsman's Office.

A University of Bucharest Senate Decision (Decision No. 421/14.12.2021) revised the award criteria of a monetary benefit for teaching staff as to not discriminate against staff opting for parental leave.

6.4 Objectives

By implementing this first Gender Equality Plan, the University of Bucharest will continue to develop an institutional culture based on respect for the values of human dignity, personal autonomy, community support, and moral and scientific integrity.

6.4.1 Objective 1. Leadership for Gender Equality

The University of Bucharest (UB) did not have up until now, a strategic institutional approach to the issue of gender equality. According to the preliminary research upon which this policy has been designed, many of the University's employees consider that the official institutional discourse is rather neutral on this topic. While some employees consider that the customary approach that University has had on gender equality to be natural/ matter of factness, others consider that the University must align itself with the principles and values of gender equality. The University's public documents analyzed for this policy show that UB addresses gender equality indirectly subsumed to general principles and values related to respect for human rights, freedom and academic autonomy, and the quality of teaching and research. Performance and academic excellence, systematically emphasised in these documents, point to a gender-neutral culture of meritocracy and excellence. Measures under this objective aim to clearly state the University of Bucharest's commitment to gender equality both in its internal and external policies.

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6.4.2 Objective 2. Governance for Gender Equality

Preliminary research showed that, within the University of Bucharest, employees hold broadly three types of attitudes towards gender equality: some employees are informed and sensitive to gender equality issues (who believe in the need for gender equality policies), others are employees with neutral attitudes towards gender equality (who do not consider gender equality to be a real issue, but accepts "impositions" from outside), and thirdly, there are employees who are hostile to any initiatives in the field (even considering these initiatives to be dangerous). At this point in time, hypothetically, some issues related to gender equality can be addressed and resolved within existing University bodies such as the Ethics Committees of many Faculties, the general UB Ethics Commission, the UB's Ombudsman Office, the Bureau of Statistics, or within the Student Associations structures. However, day to day practice shows that these structures are inefficient and insufficient for the promotion of gender equality. There are many causes for these deficiencies: starting from a lack of adequate training and information, to poor communication between departments, to an organizational culture that discourages the reporting and sanctioning of gender discrimination cases. Measures under this objective propose finding the right functional institutional formula, improving the collection of quantitative and qualitative data relevant to gender equality, and establishing appropriate monitoring mechanisms for gender equality actions.

6.4.3 Objective 3. Human Resources – Recruitment, Promotion, Retention

The preliminary research report indicates that most employees of the University of Bucharest (especially in the administrative area) have never had contact with gender equality issues (in terms of trainings, information materials, discussions). The need to become familiar with such issues has been mentioned by many, especially after they had become acquainted with possible topics covered under the umbrella of gender equality. The research showed that more women, when compared to men, are less satisfied with their position within the institution. Women also talk about the existence of informal professional networks that support male colleagues in their career advancement, networks from which they often feel excluded. The evaluation/self-evaluation procedures of UB departments do not contain indicators related to the observance of the principles of gender equality and the promotion of initiatives in the field. Thus, measures under this objective look at improving the recruitment, promotion and retention policies in order to increase the quality and performance of employees while respecting and supporting the principles of equal opportunities and gender equality.

6.4.4 Objective 4. Integrating the Gender Dimension in Interdisciplinary Academic Research

The University of Bucharest has developed a series of research structures (research centers and groups, ICUB). In some, especially in the area of the social and political sciences, there is strong research interest in the field of gender studies (CPES -

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Center for Equal Opportunities Policies, FSP). UB is also part of various European and international research networks that pay attention to the gender dimension of research. The master's degree at FSP, or courses at various faculties (especially humanities and social sciences) also integrate research topics. On the other hand, the initial research showed the lack of interest in the area of interdisciplinary research (with reference especially to the fields of science) of gender issues.

It was also noted a lack of statistical and qualitative data on the gender dimension that would enable *de facto* knowledge of the situation in the UB regarding progress in the area of gender equality. The existing data collection system can be developed to gradually integrate more advanced indicators on gender issues (such as research data and information on the gender of researchers and their research results in articles and projects). In the context of a general underfunding of the research domain in Romania, an integration of gender issues in academic research can, of course, be done by identifying appropriate sources of funding.

6.4.5 Objective 5. Integrating the Gender Dimension in Academic Curriculum

Preliminary research underpinning this plan has shown a low presence of programs explicitly dedicated to gender studies (e.g., the Master's program in Equal Opportunities Policies at the Faculty of Political Science) or programs that integrate thematic issues (GM). In the area of natural and exact sciences, such interest is non-existent. At the same time, there are currently a significant number of academics with skills in the field. Sometimes challenged, but most often integrated into the curriculum of renowned European and international universities, the field of gender studies (either as separate programs or through integration in classical disciplines) has proven its credibility and added value as an interdisciplinary scientific field of analysis of social institutions and structures.

6.4.6 Objective 6. Work Life – Family Life Balance and Care Responsibilities

At the moment, UB does not have sufficiently clear policies aimed at balancing professional and personal/family life. It does not have a set of measures or an institutional policy adopted to support teachers with caregiving responsibilities. Existing UB commitments to support measures for reconciling work and family life are not communicated regularly, consistently, and clearly. Employees with care responsibilities (either for their own children or for elders) noted that they are most often helped by the job's flexibility and by support provided informally by colleagues and the administration, but that there are no formalized support arrangements. Faculties do not have clear policies in this regard; there are no schemes to make working hours more flexible for employees with care obligations. Also, students who have care responsibilities (young parents, students with younger siblings or other relatives in their care, etc.) do not receive institutional support from the university. Students benefit from general legal provisions, but UB does not have enough specific measures to help them.

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6.4.7 Objective 7. Preventing and Combatting Sexual Harassment and Gender Discrimination

The subject of sexual harassment and gender discrimination is rather a taboo within the UB. It is approached only informally, and is often seen by community members as a private issue rather than a public one. The University of Bucharest has a policy on combating sexual harassment as well as sanctioning discriminatory behavior, including on the basis of gender. However, this policy and the reporting procedures for such incidents are still ineffective and little known in the wider UB community. There is a lack of awareness campaigns on gender discrimination, but also on the nature and consequences of sexual harassment. There is also a lack of specific training tailored to each target group in the university on this subject. Ethics commissions, theoretically mandated to deal with such cases, do not have trained personnel to address such specific issues. These shortcomings discourage victims from making formal complaints or seeking help, and shape a rather indifferent/neutral organizational culture in relation to gender-based violence.

6.4.8 Objective 8. Institutional Communication for Gender Equality

Gender equality is an integral part of the principles and values found in the University of Bucharest's strategic documents, such as the mission and the University Charter. However, UB does not communicate enough on these commitments, it does not organize enough communication events about the activities it carries out in support of the promotion of gender equality among students and teachers. UB does not include communication on gender equality among topics of strategic interest. The proposed measures will support the improvement of the institutional communication on the matter, a communication which, in the medium and long term, will be able to reduce, through correct information, the unfavorable reactions to the implementation of the GEP.

6.5 Actions

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Table 11. Actions for UB GEP

Action No.	Content area	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1.1	Leadership for Gender Equality	Introduce gender among the key values of the University of Bucharest	1.1. Institutional commitment to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest.	2022-2024	GEPI Committee and UB Rector's Office	Number of strategic documents amended to include a gender sensitive perspective	n/a	n/a	n/a
1.2	Leadership for Gender Equality	Introduce gender among the key values of the University of Bucharest	1.2. Institutional commitment to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest.	2022	The Rector's Office	Full sign off of the Charter of Diversity	n/a	n/a	n/a
2.1	Governance for Gender Equality	Setting up a robust institutional mechanism to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest	2.1 Establish a flexible operational institutional structure for coordinating and monitoring gender equality at UB.	2022-2024	The Rector's Office	Development of the GEPI Committee capacities	n/a	n/a	n/a
2.2	Governance for Gender Equality	Setting up a robust institutional mechanism to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest	2.2. Gender Equality Office	2022-2023	The Rector's Office and the GEPI Committee	Setting up a gender equality office with qualified personnel.	n/a	n/a	n/a
2.3	Governance for Gender Equality	Setting up a robust institutional mechanism to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest	2.3 Gender Equality Plan (GEP) evaluation report for 2022-2024 and updating the next GEP for a period of 4 years.	2024	The Rector's Office and the GEPI Committee with support from ATHENA project team	The first GEP, which will be valid for 2 years. At the end of the implementation period, the Rector together with the GEPI Committee, supported by the Gender Equality Office, will present a GEP evaluation report.	n/a	n/a	n/a

2.4	Governance for Gender Equality	Setting up a robust institutional mechanism to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest	2.4 Improve the process of collecting, processing and monitoring statistical data at the institutional level to monitor and communicate gender equality indicators.	2022-2024	UB's Statistics Office in partnership with the ATHENA implementation team	Gender sensitive statistical indicators will be presented in a brochure	n/a	n/a	n/a
2.5	Governance for Gender Equality	Setting up a robust institutional mechanism to promote gender equality at the University of Bucharest	2.5 Individual professional performance evaluation of teaching and research staff by introducing specific evaluation criteria on gender equality, discrimination and sexual harassment.	2023-2024	Rector's Office, Dean's Offices and GEPI Committee, CEAC (Quality Committee)	New methodology for evaluating the individual professional performance of teaching and research staff to include questions on gender equality, discrimination and sexual harassment	n/a	n/a	n/a
3.1	Human Resources: recruitment, promotion, retention	Improve gender balance and equal representation of women and men at all levels.	3.1 Training and sensitizing Human Resources staff on the principle of gender equality on the labor market and in the university environment.	2022	ATHENA project team	Number of trainings and number of personnel trained	n/a	n/a	n/a
3.2	Human Resources: recruitment, promotion, retention	Improve gender balance and equal representation of women and men at all levels.	3.2 Increasing the level of knowledge and understanding of the ethical obligations associated with an academic career,	2024	GEPI Committee Ethics Committee / Committees	Pilot online training program on ethics and prevention of discrimination and sexual harassment.	n/a	n/a	n/a

			including the obligations to prevent gender discrimination, and prevent and discourage sexual harassment.						
3.3	Human Resources: recruitment, promotion, retention	Improve gender balance and equal representation of women and men at all levels.	3.3 Revising the framework methodology for awarding professional degrees to teaching and administrative staff.	2022	Human Resources department	Tracking gender disaggregated data on professional awards	n/a	n/a	n/a
3.4	Human Resources: recruitment, promotion, retention	Improve gender balance and equal representation of women and men at all levels.	3.4 Monitoring the professional trajectory of UB graduates with the presentation of gender-disaggregated data	2024	UB's Statistics Office	Gender disaggregated annual reports on professional trajectories of UB graduates	n/a	n/a	n/a
4.1	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.1 Familiarization of UB teachers and researchers with the strategy of gender mainstreaming (GM) in academic research.	2022-2023	Rector's Office and the ATHENA team; Peer learning program of UB (FPSE)	Pilot training program on gender mainstreaming.	n/a	n/a	n/a
4.2	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.2 Establishing an informal network of researchers interested in interdisciplinary research in the field	2022	ATHENA project team	Setting up an informal network of researchers working with gender mainstreaming.	n/a	n/a	n/a

4.3	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.3 Financial allocation at UB level for research projects that propose a gender mainstreaming approach	2024	GEPI/Rectorship	Develop a priority funding area (or granting an evaluation bonus) for research projects that have a gender mainstreaming approach.	n/a	n/a	n/a
4.4	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.4 Starting a research program on the contribution of women to the development of higher education and research in Romania	2023	GEPI and the Faculty of History	Setting up a research program on women's contribution to the development of academic research and higher education	n/a	n/a	n/a
4.5	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.5 Development of a platform on the University of Bucharest Research Institute (ICUB) website dedicated to research in the field of gender equality	2022	ICUB/Informal network with support from the ATHENA team	New action area (gender equality) on the University of Bucharest Research Institute (ICUB) website. Roster of researchers interested in working on gender equality.	n/a	n/a	n/a
4.6	Integrating the gender dimension in interdisciplinary academic research	Enhance the number of research projects with gender components	4.6 Setting up a collection of gender studies the University Publishing House	2023-2024	ICUB and Rector's Office	Editorial plan established in partnership with Bucharest University Publishing House	n/a	n/a	n/a

5.1	Integrating the gender dimension in academic curriculum	Increase the number of courses that integrate a gender perspective in their approaches	5.1 Interdisciplinary summer school on gender studies for undergraduate students	2023-2024	GEPI Committee	An undergraduate summer school on gender studies with a focus on students enrolled in STEAM disciplines	n/a	n/a	n/a
5.2	Integrating the gender dimension in academic curriculum	Increase the number of courses that integrate a gender perspective in their approaches	5.2 Pilot analysis on the gender dimension in the curriculum of a faculty	2024	GEPI Committee/Faculty of Sociology	Research report on the gender dimension in the curriculum of a University of Bucharest Faculty	n/a	n/a	n/a
5.3	Integrating the gender dimension in academic curriculum	Increase the number of courses that integrate a gender perspective in their approaches	5.3 Promoting inter-university partnerships in the domain of teaching gender studies.	2023-2024	Rector's Office Faculties	Partnerships established	n/a	n/a	n/a
6.1	Work life – family life balance and care responsibilities	Improve policies for work life-family life balance and care responsibilities targeting employees and students	6.1 Promoting work life – personal life balance by establishing a scheme to make working time more flexible for UB employees.	2022	Rector's Office	Approved regulation regarding flexible working time.	n/a	n/a	n/a
6.2	Work life – family life balance and care responsibilities	Improve policies for work life-family life balance and care responsibilities targeting employees and students	6.2 Promoting the reconciliation of student's educational and care obligations in order to encourage tertiary education for all young people, regardless of family	2023	Rectors Office	Approved regulations regarding the attendance regime of students with care obligations, especially of young mothers.	n/a	n/a	n/a

			obligations						
6.3	Work life – family life balance and care responsibilities	Improve policies for work life-family life balance and care responsibilities targeting employees and students	6.3 Organizing an education and care structure for pre-school and young school children of UB's staff and students.	2024	GEPI Committee	Opportunity assessment report and identification of financial sources.	n/a	n/a	n/a
6.4	Work life – family life balance and care responsibilities	Improve policies for work life-family life balance and care responsibilities targeting employees and students	6.4 Institutional communication of UB's commitment to work life - personal life balance.	2023	GEPI/ Office for Gender Equality	Communication materials on the website of the University of Bucharest	n/a	n/a	n/a
7.1	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Raise awareness on sexual harassment and gender based discrimination in the university setting and create trustworthy mechanisms for reporting, investigations and actions	7.1 Establishing an effective and transparent mechanism for investigating incidents of sexual harassment and gender discrimination in UB.	2023	Office for Gender Equality, GEPI, Rector's Office	Procedure for recording and investigation incidents of sexual harassment and gender discrimination Independent channel for registering complaints, etc	n/a	n/a	n/a
7.2	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual	Raise awareness on sexual harassment and gender based discrimination in the university setting and create trustworthy mechanisms for reporting, investigations and	7.2 Campaign on combating discrimination and sexual harassment in UB carried out by students through	2023-2024	Office for Gender Equality, Student associations, Rector's Office	Number of campaigns and numbers of audience reached.	n/a	n/a	n/a

	harassment	actions	student associations and through partnerships with relevant NGOs.						
7.3	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Raise awareness on sexual harassment and gender based discrimination in the university setting and create trustworthy mechanisms for reporting, investigations and actions	7.3 Developing training material (possibly online) on combating sexual harassment and gender discrimination. The training will be addressed to both new students and UB employees.	2024	Office for Gender Equality, Rector's Office, Faculty of Foreign Languages	Online training program on combating sexual harassment and gender discrimination.	n/a	n/a	n/a
8.1	Institutional communication for gender equality	Improve institutional communication on gender equality and raise awareness of the UB's GEP and its actions	8.1 Gender Equality website of the University of Bucharest	2022	ATHENA Team, UB's Communications Department	Website	n/a	n/a	n/a
8.2	Institutional communication for gender equality	Improve institutional communication on gender equality and raise awareness of the UB's GEP and its actions	8.2 Efforts to increase the visibility of women's contribution to the development of higher education and research (renaming lecture theatres, classrooms, series of conferences, events, awards, etc.	2022-2023	Rectorship, Deanships, Office for Gender Equality	Concrete initiatives, such as: information on the pages of the faculties, events dedicated to the work of some personalities, renaming some rooms, portraits of female personalities	n/a	n/a	n/a

8.3	Institutional communication for gender equality	Improve institutional communication on gender equality and raise awareness of the UB's GEP and its actions	8.3 Communications plan regarding gender equality in UB.	2022-2024	UB's Communications Office with GEPI and the ATHENA	Communication plan and calendar of activities to promote gender equality: diversity month, women's rights month, campaign to prevent and combat domestic violence, research excellence among women/Women in Science	n/a	n/a	n/a
8.4	Institutional communication for gender equality	Improve institutional communication on gender equality and raise awareness of the UB's GEP and its actions	8.4 International conference on the promotion of gender equality in universities and research units. Promoting collaboration with other Romanian universities and institutes that have developed/are in the process of developing GEPs.	2023	ATHENA Team, Rectorship, Office for Gender Equality	Event and number of participants	n/a	n/a	n/a
8.5	Institutional communication for gender equality	Improve institutional communication on gender equality and raise awareness of the UB's GEP and its actions	8.5 Promote inclusive language in all official communications of the University of	2024	Office for Gender Equality and UB's Communications Office	Guide on inclusive language with terminological clarifications and concrete examples	n/a	n/a	n/a

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6.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

The University of Bucharest adopted its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) on April 20, 2022. This GEP will cover 2 years (2022 to 2024) and its end will correspond to the end of the current Rector's mandate. During the consultation conducted for the crafting of the first GEP, the GEPI Committee members recommended that, as a rule the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest should be a four-year plan, adopted at the beginning of a Rector's mandate and duly evaluated and discussed at the end of the Rector's term. The linkage between the adoption of a new GEP and the Rector's Mandate will give more strength and visibility to gender equality within the University. For the four-year plan, an interim evaluation will be conducted mid-way into the plan (after two years) in order to have a solid view of how measures included in the plan are being implemented and in case of delays mitigating actions could be put in place in order to achieve all indicators described in the plan.

The current GEP is an exception from the above-mentioned rule. The current GEP includes 8 SMART objectives broken down in concrete actions with assigned responsible units and relevant indicators. However, given that this is a first plan and that the current Rector's term ends in two years, the decision of GEPI and Rector's Office was to have a two-year GEP (2022-2024). In 2024, the Rector's Office, with the support of the GEPI Committee and with the technical support of the Gender Equality Office (which will be set up in the incoming two years) will prepare an evaluation report on all the measures included in the plan. The Rector's Report will be presented in the General Administration Council of the University of Bucharest as well as in the Senate of the University of Bucharest. These are the two main decision-making bodies. The current GEP 2022-2024 was also approved in the similar manner both in the GA and in the Senate.

6.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

The University of Bucharest (UB) adopted its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) on April 20, 2022. Objectives and measures included in the GEP were based on a complex assessment and research report but drafted in consultation with GEPI Committee members as well as with other institutional stakeholders such as: The Bureau of Statistics of the University of Bucharest, the Rector's Office, student representatives, various researchers and teaching staff interested in gender equality. Moreover, the ATHENA team consulted with partners from the Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation (UEFISCDI), the main RFO in Romania which had also launched its Gender Equality Plan in February 2022. The larger community of the University of Bucharest was regularly kept up to date with announcements related to the launch of the ATHENA project and with various project activities through the newsletter of the University of Bucharest. This is a regular information tool used by the management of the University and sent out to all community members via email.

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Since March 2022, the University of Bucharest website included a dedicated webpage to its Gender Equality Plan. This is the website <https://gep.unibuc.ro/> where relevant information connected to both ATHENA project activities as well as other information related to the promotion of gender equality in higher education is constantly updated.

The University of Bucharest, ATHENA team also presented its progress and work in the general ATHENA network newsletter.

The dissemination strategy of University of Bucharest's GEP includes the following actions:

- On April 20, 2022, after the formal adoption of UB's Gender Equality Plan 2022-2024, the University of Bucharest Newsletter included a section dedicated to the its adoption and presented the full plan.
- Since the end of April, 2022, the University of Bucharest website displays the full length Gender Equality Plan at the following link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1vmVVvEqqc6hoyChly6tRrtSHIKKWdJrp/view>
- On May 13 Laura Grünberg, ATHENA project leader participated (in Session 9, "The Institutionalization and Professionalization of Gender/Equal Opportunities Expertise in Romania") with a presentation titled "How to make (or not make) gender equality in higher education work."
- In the period February – May 2022, ATHENA project team at the University of Bucharest convened an informal network of researchers interested in gender studies. The informal network included over 20 participants throughout three distinct meetings. Future meetings are planned for the following months
- From June to November 2022, a series of awareness raising trainings will be organized for various groups within the UB community. These trainings will further disseminate the provisions of the gender equality plan.
- The ATHENA team at the University of Bucharest conducted a stakeholder mapping exercise and identified and contacted over 20 relevant national stakeholders. Forms documenting the consent of the stakeholder to be included in a database were sent out. These contacts will be used to further disseminate information from the gender equality plan and from the compendium of best practices elaborated under the Athena project.

6.8 Annex

The UB GEP was approved by the University Senate on April 20, 2022. The Romanian and official version of the GEP is available [here](#).

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Gender Equality Plan

University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
(ULPGC)

7. ULPGC Gender Equality Plan

7.1 Introduction

The University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria has among its commitments to promote equal opportunities between women and men, through the promotion of policies, initiatives and measures that foster it within the university community itself. In this sense, the Gender Equality Plan that is presented is an essential tool to advance equality in all processes and areas of the University.

Spanish Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the effective equality of women and men, defines equality plans as "an ordered set of measures, adopted after carrying out a diagnosis of the situation, aimed at achieving equality in the company equal treatment and opportunities between women and men and to eliminate discrimination based on sex".

The I Gender Equality Plan of the ULPGC, which validity period ended in 2020, laid the foundations to promote equal opportunities between women and men in our institution; Based on what has been achieved to date, it is essential to promote new actions and develop initiatives and measures that allow the gender gaps that still persist to be eliminated.

The II Gender Equality Plan of the ULPGC intends to advance along these lines, which will last four years. To do this, it is based on a diagnosis of the situation that addresses the matters indicated in Spanish Law 3/2007: selection and hiring process; professional classification; training; professional promotion; working conditions, including pay audit; co-responsible exercise of the rights of personal, family and work life; female underrepresentation; remuneration, and prevention of sexual and gender-based harassment. The preparation of this diagnosis has made it possible to identify the priority spheres of action in the targeted areas. Once this phase of study, analysis and diagnosis has been completed, the Plan includes the objectives pursued and the measures to be adopted, the deadline for its application, the resources necessary for its implementation, the responsible bodies, and a monitoring and evaluation system.

The elaboration and approval of this II Plan, promoted by the Equality Unit, is the result of a process of dialogue, participation and negotiation developed within the commission constituted for this purpose, of which workers representatives have been part. the teaching and research staff and the administration and services staff of the ULPGC, and representatives of the government team. In addition to the involvement and contributions of the members of the aforementioned commission, the collaboration and work carried out by the people who made up the technical team should also be

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highlighted. Without the work, availability and involvement of all of them, it would not have been possible to have the II Equality Plan today.

This II Gender Equality Plan, unanimously approved by the negotiating committee, is structured around 6 lines of action: promotion of a culture of equality; access and promotion; teaching, research and transfer; participation and representation; co-responsible conciliation; and prevention of sexual and gender-based harassment. These axes are developed in 14 objectives and 49 measures that respond to the situation reflected in the diagnosis and must contribute to achieving real equality between women and men in the field of our University.

Once the process for drafting and approving the II Gender Equality Plan has concluded, the phase aimed at its application begins, and for this the commitment of those who make up the University is essential, joining forces to promote its effective implementation. Added to the foregoing is the monitoring and evaluation of the measures provided for in the Plan, which will make it possible to verify their implementation.

Finally, it is important to note that the participation of the ULPGC in the European ATHENA Project (HORIZON 2020 Funds) has been essential in the process of renewing the Equality Plan. A project whose main objective is to support participating organizations in the implementation of Equality Plans to promote research with a gender perspective.

7.2 Development process and GEP management

In accordance with the Spanish Law (RD 901/2020, of October 13), the negotiating committee is an essential body for the negotiation and approval of the Equality Plan, in which the representation of the government team participates equally of the University and the representation of teaching and research staff and administration and services. Likewise, this negotiating committee will be in charge of the monitoring, evaluation and periodic review of the II Equality Plan, in compliance with the provisions of article 9 of the aforementioned RD 901/2020.

In the development of the II Gender Equality Plan of the ULPGC, the following have participated as members of the negotiating commission:

On behalf of the ULPGC government team:

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- Francisco Artilés López, Vice Manager of Human Resources.
- María Asunción Beerli Palacio, Vice-Rector for Social Projection and Communication.
- Inmaculada González Cabrera, Secretary General
- Carmen Grau Pineda, Director of Teaching Staff.
- Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of the Equality Unit.
- Asunción Morales Martín, Director of Teaching Staff.
- Marcos Antonio Pérez Delgado, Superior Technician in Occupational Risk Prevention.

On behalf of the workers of the ULPGC:

- Pastora Calvo Hernández, union representative (UGT) in the Teaching and Research Staff Committee.
- Elena Carretón Gómez, union representative (CCOO) in the Teaching and Research Staff Committee.
Replaces : José Manuel Arias Febles, trade union representative (CCOO) in the Teaching and Research Staff Committee.
- Ana Falcón Martínez de Marañón, union representative (CCOO) in the Board of Teaching and Research Staff.
- Oscar Fernández Camba, union representative (CSIF) in the Administration and Services Personnel Committee.
- José Antonio Herrera Valladolid, union representative (CCOO) in the Administration and Services Personnel Committee.
Replaces : José Ángel Bueno García, union representative (FSOC) in the Administration and Services Personnel Committee.
- Vanesa Reyes Mendoza Grimón , union representative (APU) in the Teaching and Research Staff Committee.
Substitutes : María Luz Alonso Aguiar , union representative (APU) in the Teaching and Research Staff Committee.
- Carmen Rosa Pérez Martín, union representative (SEPCA) in the Administration and Services Personnel Committee.

On the other hand, it has been essential to have the participation of a technical team made up of professors from the University and technical personnel hired within the framework of the European ATHENA project:

- Ana Falcón Martínez de Marañón, Professor at the School of Civil Law.

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- Beatriz González López-Valcárcel, Professor of Quantitative Methods in Economics and Management.
- Carmen Grau Pineda, Director of Teaching Staff and Professor of Labor and Social Security Law.
- Carolina Mesa Marrero, Director of the Equality Unit and Professor of Civil Law.
- Yaiza Gómez Yáñez, Graduate in Law and Expert in Equality and Gender.
- Enrique Suárez Carreño, Double graduate in Law and Business and Administration Management.

7.3 Diagnosis

The diagnosis of the situation of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the first phase of the gender equality plan, is the result of the process of taking and collecting data aimed at identifying and estimating the magnitude, through quantitative and qualitative indicators, of the existing inequalities, differences, disadvantages, difficulties and obstacles to achieve effective equality between women and men in the university environment.

The elaboration and analysis of this diagnosis has allowed the identification of existing gender imbalances. Based on this diagnosis, a series of measures are adopted in order to guarantee equality between women and men in any area of the university. Next, we proceed to detail the aspects to improve and to take into account to achieve this objective:

The data collected from the Research Teaching Staff in the academic year 2019/20, have shown the distribution by branches of knowledge and departments, denoting the different gender imbalances found in the University. By branches of knowledge, it can be concluded that the Arts and Humanities, the Social and Legal Sciences and the Health Sciences are the ones that have equal representation between men and women. However, the branches of knowledge of Sciences and Engineering and Architecture do not have parity data and female underrepresentation is found in both.

The study of the evolution of the Administration and Services Personnel in the years 2016 to 2020, shows that the presence of women throughout those years represents 54.65% of the total, compared to 45.35% of men, being within 40-60% that stipulates that the distribution of men and women in this category is equal.

Regarding the Official Teaching and Research Staff in the academic year 2020/21, a notable imbalance has been observed in different categories that suppose an

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underrepresentation of women in this sector of the ULPGC. This situation is very evident in the categories of University Professor with 102 men (76.69%) compared to 31 women (23.31%), the category of Associated University Professor with 10 men (90.91%) compared to 1 woman (9.09%) and the category of University School Professor with 17 men (85%) compared to 3 women (15%). It is important to bear in mind that all categories of the University have more male representation, highlighting the Emeritus Teaching Staff, which has 100% men (10) and no women (0%).

After analyzing the different six-year terms of the Official PDI of the years 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021, it can be concluded that the women of the ULPGC are underrepresented in each of the years, favoring that men are present in more than double. It is important to make visible that PDI women present themselves to fewer calls and are awarded fewer projects compared to the male sector, as we have analyzed in the research axis. In the same way, women have little presence in the selection courts for Teaching and Research Staff without reaching equal representation in the years 2019, 2020 and 2021.

Regarding the composition of the management teams of departments in the second quarter of 2022, an underrepresentation of women has been observed in the people who make up said teams, leaving a composition of women of 29.5% compared to an important 70.5% of men. In relation to the data related to the governing bodies, the underrepresentation of women in the Social Council stands out in particular.

Regarding the students enrolled at the ULPGC in the years 2017/2018 to 2020/2021, different areas of study that continue to be masculinized or feminized are perceived. In this case, the areas with the greatest presence of women have to do with Arts and Humanities, Social and Legal Sciences, and Health Sciences. While men are more present in Social and Legal Sciences and Engineering and Architecture.

Regarding the training of the ULPGC staff, it is concluded that there is no notable difference between men and women when it comes to developing at a professional level in the different courses that the university can offer. However, the amount of training that can be provided on equality matters can be improved, since they are minimal. An example of this are the courses for Administration and Services Personnel, which have had two equality courses in the period from 2017 to 2021.

There is a gender gap in the professional promotion of Research Teaching Staff that has persisted throughout the four years analyzed (2018 to 2021) and that shows an underrepresentation of women in each of the years presented.

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It is recommended to update the regulations on permits, licenses and vacations of the Teaching and Research Staff of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria from 2006, since, as we noted in the Working Conditions axis, it is outdated in different issues such as conciliation. This regulation could be updated following the Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for effective equality between women and men and Royal Decree 6/2019 of March 1 on urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in employment and occupation.

The global results in terms of co-responsibility of the rights of personal, family and work life show that during the years 2018-2019-2020 women availed much more than men to permits and licenses related to co-responsibility. The years 2019 and 2020 stand out due to the great difference that exists, since women received almost five times more than men in 2019 and three times more in 2020. Regarding the breastfeeding permit for indistinct use by the mother or the father has collected that in the period (2018-2021) no man has been welcomed compared to 31 women who have.

The ULPGC has a protocol approved by the Governing Council on July 27, 2017 against the prevention of sexual and sexist harassment with different action procedures. However, it is recommended to expose in a more visible and notorious way the tools that are available on the University website. All this will make it easier for the university community to be aware of this type of resource since, for example, only 32% of the students surveyed said they knew of its existence.

The language and communication of the university is of vital importance to apply the gender approach both in the internal and external communication of the entity. For this reason, it is recommended to review the different grammatical expressions on the institutional website and different documents are provided to guarantee the correct use of inclusive language.

The surveys provided to the ULPGC staff result in the need to continue improving the possible alternatives to reconcile family and work life, training in equality or the actual practice of the actions planned in terms of equality.

The surveys provided to the students of the ULPGC, result in the need to continue improving in matters that have to do with offering greater training in gender equality, promoting acts and actions that guarantee gender equality and giving more visibility to the existence of the Equality Unit and the protocol for sexual and/or gender-based harassment.

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The data produced by the remuneration audit indicate that there is a gender wage gap in the complements associated with the greater historical presence of men in the Institution and in research, which is in line with the results returned by the studies of other national public universities and with the analysis carried out throughout this diagnostic report. The existing percentage differences that are not explained by the high intra-group variability do not reach 25%, which does not mean that actions should not be carried out in pursuit of equal remuneration.

7.4 Objectives

AXIS 1: The first axis of the equality plan is the promotion of a culture of equality to transform the thinking of the university community in search of equity. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 1.1. Promote and transmit the institutional commitment to equality and non-discrimination.
- OBJECTIVE 1.2. Promote activities to raise awareness in the university community about the value of equality
- OBJECTIVE 1.3. Advance in non-sexist communication.

AXIS 2: The second axis of the equality plan aims to achieve equality between women and men in the access and promotion of workers at the University. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 2.1. Promote equal opportunities in the professional career.
- OBJECTIVE 2.2 Know the causes that hinder the professional promotion of women.

AXIS 3: The third axis of the equality plan seeks to unleash the research potential of women in equal conditions, as well as a good transfer of its results. It also seeks a teaching job in equity. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 3.1. Promote the gender approach in teaching.
- OBJECTIVE 3.2. Promote the participation and leadership of women in research and transfer.

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- OBJECTIVE 3.3. Promote the incorporation of the gender perspective in research.

AXIS 4: The fourth axis of the equality plan wants to achieve equality for the presence, participation and representation of women in all the operating bodies of the university (teachers, researchers and management) and especially in management positions. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 4.1. Promote the participation of women in university life.
- OBJECTIVE 4.2. Promote the balanced presence of women and men in governing and representative bodies.

AXIS 5: The fifth axis of the equality plan seeks to promote good conditions for reconciling personal, family and work life for the workers of the University. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to promote a balanced distribution between women and men for the care of the family. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 5.1. Ensure compliance with conciliation measures.
- OBJECTIVE 5.2. Promote co-responsible conciliation

AXIS 6:

The sixth axis of the equality plan wants to curb any act of sexual or gender-based harassment that occurs among the entire University Community. These are the objectives:

- OBJECTIVE 6.1. Raise awareness to prevent sexual and gender-based harassment.
- OBJECTIVE 6.2. Assessment of the Protocol for detection, prevention and action in cases of sexual harassment and for reasons of sex-gender.

7.5 Actions

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The actions that will be carried out in relation to each of the objectives mentioned in the previous section are shown below:

OBJECTIVE 1.1. Promote and transmit the institutional commitment to equality and non-discrimination.

MEASURE 1.1.1. Disseminate the University Equality Plan.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Social Outreach and Communication
Equality Unit
Term: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out

MEASURE 1.1.2. Make the Equality Unit visible among the university community.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Social Projection and Communication
Equality Unit
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Improve access through the web
Number of dissemination actions

MEASURE 1.1.3. Involve the university community in the activities and initiatives promoted by the Equality Unit.

Responsible: Vice-Rector for Social Projection and Communication
Equality Unit
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Number of communication actions

MEASURE 1.1.4. Promote awareness campaigns on equal opportunities between women and men.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Social Outreach and Communication
Equality Unit
Centers
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out
Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups

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MEASURE 1.1.5. Support student councils and associations in actions related to equal opportunities between women and men.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Students , Alumni and Employability
Equality Unit Centers
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Number of requests addressed in this regard

MEASURE 1.1.6. Promote information campaigns among secondary school students to remove gender stereotypes in the choice of university studies.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Students, Alumni and Employability
Equality Unit
Term: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out annually

MEASURE 1.1.7. Promote actions to recognize and make visible academic and scientific women.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Vice-rectorate for Social Projection and Communication
Equality Unit
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out

MEASURE 1.1.8. Promote and support the initiatives presented for the granting of the title of honorary doctorate, and other mentions or recognitions of the ULPGC to academic women for their professional career.

Responsible: Vice-Rectorate for Research and Transfer
Governing Council
Centers
Departments
University Institutes
Equality Unit
Term: Throughout the term of the PI
Indicators: Number of actions proposed and applications approved

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OBJECTIVE 1.2. Promote activities to raise awareness in the university community about the value of equality

MEASURE 1.2.1. Develop training activities on equality and non-discrimination.

Responsible : Equality Unit
Centers
Deadline : Throughout the term of the PI
Minimum 2 actions during the term of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of training activities
Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups

MEASURE 1.2.2. Design awareness-raising actions in the prevention and action against gender violence.

Responsible : Equality Unit
Centers
Term: Throughout the term of the PI
Minimum 2 actions during the term of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out
Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups

MEASURE 1.2.3. Participation and organization in the celebration of commemorative acts of equality.

Responsible: Equality Unit
Term: Throughout the validity of the PI
Indicators: Number of acts carried out annually

MEASURE 1.2.4. Encourage the organization of activities with a gender perspective in the programming of the university extension service, and other training offer of the ULPGC.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Undergraduate, Postgraduate and New Degrees
Vice-rectorate for Students, Alumni and Employability
Equality Unit
Deadline: Throughout the term of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of activities carried out
Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups

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OBJECTIVE 1.3. Advance in non-sexist communication.

MEASURE 1.3.1. Guarantee the use of non-sexist language in the documentation of the ULPGC and the institutional website.

Responsible: All the Vice Presidents
Equality Unit
Management
Centers
Departments
University Research Institutes
Period: Throughout the term of the PI
Indicators: Continuous review of the website
Number of documents reviewed

MEASURE 1.3.2. Ensure the use of non-sexist language in acts and institutional communications.

Responsible: All the Vice Presidents
Equality Unit
Management
Centers
Departments
University Research Institutes
Term: Throughout the term of the PI
Indicators: Follow-up and verification of compliance.

MEASURE 1.3.3. Guarantee that data collection in any area of the ULPGC is carried out disaggregated by sex.

Person in charge: All the Vice-Rectorates
Management
Information Technology Service
Term: Throughout the validity of the PI
Indicators: Verify annually, through consultation with the bodies involved, compliance with the measure

OBJECTIVE 2.1. Promote equal opportunities in the professional career.

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MEASURE 2.1.1. Guarantee that in the promotion of PDI positive discrimination is made against the underrepresented sex.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation

Deadline: During the second year of validity

Indicators: Verify the incorporation of the positive action measure
Number of changes in the distribution of the workforce by sex/group and job position

MEASURE 2.1.2. Include an additional score in the scale of doctoral positions in the areas of science, engineering and architecture and mathematics, in order to give preference to women.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation

Deadline: During the second year of validity

Indicators: Verify the inclusion of the additional score in the scale

MEASURE 2.1.3. Guarantee a balanced presence between women and men in the access commissions for the selection of PDI and PAS personnel.

Person in charge: Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation

Deadline: The entire duration of the PI

Indicators: Verify compliance annually

OBJECTIVE 2.2. Know the causes that hinder the professional promotion of women.

MEASURE 2.2.1. Prepare a study to analyze the possible difficulties that PDI and PAS women may have in order to be promoted.

Responsible: Equality Unit

Term: During the first and second year of validity of the PI

Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 2.2.2. Depending on the result of the previous study, the appropriate measures will be adopted to solve the difficulties detected. And regarding the PDI, in

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particular, the necessary actions will be established, on the one hand to establish a system that favors the research activity of women (who have difficulties due to family responsibilities justified according to the legislation) and on the other hand to guarantee the participation of the women in mobility programs.

Responsible party: Equality Unit
Vice-rectorate for Research
Vice-rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation
Vice-rectorate for Internationalization, Mobility and International Projection
Management

Term: After completion of the study provided for in the previous measure

Indicators: Analysis of the results of the study and, in if applicable, verification of the measures adopted
Number of women in mobility programs

OBJECTIVE 3.1. Promote the gender approach in teaching.

MEASURE 3.1.1. Offer training courses on the incorporation of the gender perspective in teaching.

Responsible party: Equality Unit
Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation

Deadline: From the first year of validity of the PI
Minimum 2 trainings during the entire validity of the PI

Indicators: Number of courses offered
Number of attendees disaggregated by gender

MEASURE 3.1.2. Promote the implementation of, at least, one own degree in terms of equality.

Responsible party: Equality Unit
Vice-Rector for Undergraduate, Postgraduate and New Degrees

Deadline: From the second year of validity of the PI

Indicators: Completed YES/NO
Number of degrees

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MEASURE 3.1.3. Ensuring the announcement of awards to recognize the best final degree projects that address issues related to equality and/or the incorporation of gender as an analytical perspective.

Responsible: Equality Unit
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

OBJECTIVE 3.2. Promote the participation and leadership of women in research and transfer.

MEASURE 3.2.1. Promote the leadership of women as main researchers in the research projects of the ULPGC, establishing a specific additional score, in the corresponding scale.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Verify the inclusion of the additional score in the scale
Number of own research projects led
by women

MEASURE 3.2.2. Disseminate specific research calls on equality.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Number of dissemination actions

MEASURE 3.2.3. Preparation of a database of women researchers for communication purposes and for their visibility.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Deadline: Between the second and third year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 3.2.4. Promote collaboration agreements with public and private institutions to encourage the transfer of research results.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer Term

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: Between the second and third year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Number of collaboration agreements

OBJECTIVE 3.3. Promote the incorporation of the gender perspective in research.

MEASURE 3.3.1. Promote the dissemination of studies and research on gender.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Vice-rectorate for Social Projection and Communication
Equality Unit
Term: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Number of dissemination actions

MEASURE 3.3.2. Promote the incorporation of the gender perspective in research activities within the Doctoral Programs.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Deadline: From the first year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions of proposal and implementation of the action

MEASURE 3.3.3. Promote training activities aimed at including the gender perspective in the field of research.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Research and Transfer
Equality Unit
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Minimum 2 activities during the term of the PI
Indicators: Number of scheduled activities
Number of attendees disaggregated by sex

OBJECTIVE 4.1. Promote the participation of women in university life.

MEASURE 4.1.1. Guarantee the balanced participation of women and men in institutional events.

Responsible: All the Vice
Presidents General Secretariat
Equality Unit

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Centers
Deadline: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 4.1.2. Promote the participation of women in all electoral processes.

Responsible : Central Electoral Board
Management
Term: Electoral processes after the approval of the PI
Indicators: Number of women who participate in the
electoral processes

MEASURE 4.1.3. Ensure balance in the composition of the commissions and courts,
and justify, if this is not possible, the reasons that prevent it.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and
Educational Innovation
General Secretariat
Deadline : During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Percentage of commissions and tribunals with balanced composition
Assessment of the reasons that motivate the impossibility

MEASURE 4.1.4. Promote the appointment of women in the presidency of commissions
and courts.

Responsible: Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and
Educational Innovation
General Secretariat
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Check annually the number of women in the
presidency of commissions and courts

**OBJECTIVE 4.2. Promote the balanced presence of women and men in governing
and representative bodies.**

MEASURE 4.2.1. Guarantee the balanced presence of women and men in the
management team (rector and vice-rectors).

Responsible: Area of the Rector and Vice-

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Term: Rectorships General Secretary
During the term of the PI
Indicators: Verify the composition by sex of the candidacies for
rector and/or government team.

MEASURE 4.2.2. Ensure parity in the management teams of the Faculties, Schools, Departments, Research Institutes of the ULPGC, as well as in the representative bodies of the teaching and research staff and administration and services staff.

Responsible : Central Electoral Board
Centers
Departments
University institutes
Deadline: Electoral processes after approval of the PI
Indicators: Verify the number of women in the teams

MEASURE 4.2.3. Develop actions and initiatives that promote female leadership.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Social Projection and Communication
Equality Unit
Deadline: During the validity of the PI
Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out and data on people
attending disaggregated by sex and group

OBJECTIVE 5.1. Ensure compliance with conciliation measures.

MEASURE 5.1.1. Review and update the internal regulations regarding permits, licenses and vacations for PDI and PAS personnel.

Responsibility : General Secretariat
Management
Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and
Educational Innovation
Deadline: During the first and second year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 5.1.2. Review and adapt the application for permits and licenses of the PDI so that it is consistent with the law and with the internal regulations of the ULPGC.

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Responsible: Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation, Management
Term: Within the first year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 5.1.3. Assimilate the conciliation rights of the PDI to the PAS.

Responsible: Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation
Deadline: During the first and second year of validity of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 5.1.4. Ensure that meetings are held preferably before 5:00 p.m.

Responsible: General Secretariat
All Vice Presidents
Management
Centers and Departments
Term: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Monitor possible queries and/or complaints of non-compliance.

MEASURE 5.1.5. Guarantee the preparation of a database, disaggregated by sex, for the monitoring of all permits, licenses and leave of absence requested by the PDI and PAS for the purpose of conciliation. As well as data on family conditions, number of children, dependents, and their ages.

Responsible: Vice-rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation
Management
Term: During the term of the PI
Indicators: Completed YES/NO

OBJECTIVE 6.1. Raise awareness to prevent sexual and gender-based harassment.

MEASURE 6.1.1. Promote dissemination measures among the university community of the Protocol on sexual and sex-gender harassment. Person in

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charge: Vice-rectorate for Social Outreach and Communication
Occupational Risk Prevention Service
Equality Unit

Deadline: During the term of the PI
Minimum two dissemination actions during the term of the PI

Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out

MEASURE 6.1.2. Promote awareness and training actions.

Responsible : Equality Unit
Centers

Term: During the term of the PI

Indicators: Number and type of actions carried out
Data of the attendees disaggregated by sex
Subsequent survey of degree of knowledge

OBJECTIVE 6.2. Assessment of the Protocol for detection, prevention and action in cases of sexual harassment and for reasons of sex-gender.

MEASURE 6.2.1. Analyze the application of the Protocol regarding sexual and gender-based harassment.

Responsible : Inspection
Service Occupational Risk Prevention Service
Equality Unit

Deadline: During the first and second year of validity of the PI

Indicators: Completed YES/NO

MEASURE 6.2.2. Assess the adequacy of the Protocol to all types of harassment and, where appropriate, propose its modification.

Responsible party: General Secretariat
Inspection
Service Occupational Risk Prevention Service
Equality Unit

Deadline: During the second and third year of validity of the PI

Indicators: Evaluation report and fulfillment of its result

Table 12. Actions implemented in the ULPGC GEP

Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	TIME FRAME	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Promotion of a culture of equality	1. Promote and transmit the institutional commitment to equality and non-discrimination.	Disseminate the University Equality Plan.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit	Number and type of actions carried out
		Make the Equality Unit visible among the university community.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit	Improve access through the web
			During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit	Number of dissemination actions
		Involve the university community in the activities and initiatives promoted by the Equality Unit.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit	Number of communication actions
		Promote awareness campaigns on equal opportunities between women and men.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit. centers	Number and type of actions carried out
			During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit. centers	Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups
		Support student councils and associations in actions related to equal opportunities between women and men.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Students, Alumni and Employability. Equality Unit. centers	Number of requests addressed in this regard

		Promote information campaigns among secondary school students to remove gender stereotypes in the choice of university studies.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Students, Alumni and Employability. Equality Unit	Number and type of actions carried out annually
		Promote actions to recognize and make visible academic and scientific women.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Research and Transfer. Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unit	Number and type of actions carried out
		Promote and support the initiatives presented for the granting of the title of honorary doctorate, and other mentions or recognitions of the ULPGC to academic women for their professional career.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Research and Transfer. Government council. Centers. Departments. University Institutes. Equality Unit	Number of actions proposed and applications approved
	2. Promote activities to raise awareness in the university community about the value of equality	Develop training activities on equality and non-discrimination	During the entire validity of the GEP. Minimum 2 actions during the term of the GEP	Equality Unit. centers	Number and type of training activities
			During the entire validity of the GEP. Minimum 2 actions during the term of the PI	Equality Unit. centers	Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups
		Design awareness-raising actions in the prevention and action against gender violence.	During the entire validity of the PI. Minimum 2 actions during the term of the GEP	Equality Unit. centers	Number and type of actions carried out
			During the entire validity of the GEP. Minimum 2 actions during the	Equality Unit. centers	Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups

			term of the GEP		
		Participation and organization in the celebration of commemorative acts of equality	During the term of the GEP	Equality Unit.	Number of acts performed annually
		Encourage the organization of activities with a gender perspective in the programming of the university extension service, and other training offer of the ULPGC.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Degrees, Postgraduate Studies and New Degrees. Office of the Vice President for Students, Alumni and Employability. Equality Unit	Number and type of activities carried out
			During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Degrees, Postgraduate Studies and New Degrees. Office of the Vice President for Students, Alumni and Employability. Equality Unit	Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and groups
	3. Advance non-sexist communication	Guarantee the use of non-sexist language in the ULPGC documentation and institutional website	During the term of the GEP	All Vice Presidents. Equality Unit. Management. Centers. Departments. University Research Institutes	Continuous review of the website
			During the term of the GEP	All Vice Presidents. Equality Unit. Management. Centers. Departments. University Research Institutes	Number of documents reviewed
		Ensure the use of non-sexist language in institutional acts and communications	During the term of the GEP	All Vice Presidents. Equality Unit. Management. Centers. Departments. University Research Institutes	Monitoring and verification of compliance.

		Guarantee that data collection in any area of the ULPGC is carried out disaggregated by sex.	During the term of the GEP	All Vice Presidents. Management. Computer Service	Verify annually, through consultation with the bodies involved, compliance with the measure
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Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	TIME FRAME	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1. Promote equal opportunities in professional careers.	Guarantee that, in the promotion of PDI, positive discrimination is made against the underrepresented sex.	During the second year of validity	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation	YES/NO
			During the second year of validity	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation	-Number of changes in the distribution of the workforce by sex/group and job
		Include in the scale an additional score in order to give preference to women in contracted doctoral positions in the STEM areas (science, engineering and architecture and mathematics)	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation	-Verify the incorporation of the additional score in the scale
		Guarantee a balanced presence between women and men in the access commissions for the selection of PDI and PAS personnel.	During the first and second year of validity of the GEP	Management and Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation	-Check compliance annually
	2. Know the causes that hinder the professional promotion of women	Carry out a study to analyze the possible difficulties that PDI and PAS women may have in promoting	Before the third year of validity of the GEP	Equality Unit	YES/NO

		Depending on the result of the previous study, the appropriate measures will be adopted to solve the difficulties detected. And regarding the PDI, in particular, the necessary actions will be established, on the one hand to establish a system that favors the research activity of women (who have difficulties due to justified family responsibilities according to the legislation) and on the other hand to guarantee the participation of the women in mobility programs.	After completion of the study provided for in the previous measure	Equality Unit. Vice President for Research. Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation. Vice-Rectorate for Internationalization, Mobility and International Projection. Management	Analysis of the results of the study and, where appropriate, verification of the measures adopted.
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Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	TIME FRAME	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1. Promote the gender approach in teaching	Offer training courses on the incorporation of the gender perspective in teaching	From the first year of validity of the PI Minimum 2 trainings during the entire validity of the GEP	Equality Unit - Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation	Number of courses offered -Number of attendees disaggregated by sex
		Proposal to modify the measure Promote the implementation of at least one title on equality	From the second year of validity of the GEP	Equality Unit Vice President for Undergraduate, Postgraduate and New Degrees	YES/NO and number of titles
		Ensure the announcement of awards to recognize the best final degree projects that address issues related to equality and/or the incorporation of gender as an analytical perspective	During the term of the GEP	equality unit	YES/NO

	2. Promote the participation and leadership of women in research and transfer	Promote the leadership of women as main researchers in the research projects of the ULPGC, establishing a specific additional score, in the corresponding scale.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Research and Transfer	Verify the inclusion of the additional score in the scale, Number of own research projects led by women
		Disseminate specific research calls on equality	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Research and Transfer	Number of dissemination actions
		Development of a database of women researchers for communication purposes and for their visibility	Between the second and third year of validity of the GEP	Vice President for Research and Transfer	YES/NO
		Promote collaboration agreements with public and private institutions to encourage the transfer of research results	Between the second and third year of validity of the GEP	Vice President for Research and Transfer	Number of collaboration agreements
	3. Promote the incorporation of the gender perspective in research	Promote the dissemination of studies and research on gender	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Research and Transfer - Office of the Vice President for Social Outreach and Communication - Equality Unit	Number of dissemination actions
		Promote the incorporation of the gender perspective in research activities within the Doctoral Programs	From the first year of validity of the GEP	Vice President for Research and Transfer	Number and type of actions of proposal and implementation of the action
		Promote training activities aimed at including the gender perspective in the field of research	During the term of the GEP Minimum 2 activities during the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Research and Transfer - Equality Unit	Number of scheduled activities, Number of attendees disaggregated by sex

Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	TIME FRAME	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	1. Promote the participation of women in university life.	Guarantee the balanced participation of women and men in institutional events.	During the term of the GEP	All Vice Presidents -General Secretariat -Equality Unit - Centers	Done YES/NO
		Promote the participation of women in all electoral processes	Electoral processes after the approval of the GEP	Central Electoral Board - Management	Number of women participating in electoral processes
		Ensure balance in the composition of the commissions and courts, and justify, if this is not possible, the reasons that prevent it.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation - General Secretariat	Percentage of commissions and courts with balanced composition - Assessment of the reasons that motivate the impossibility
		Promote the appointment of women in the presidency of commissions and courts.	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation - General Secretariat	Check annually the number of women in the presidency of commissions and courts
	2. Promote the balanced presence of women and men in governing and representative bodies.	Guarantee the balanced presence of women and men in the management team (rector and vice-rectors)	During the term of the GEP	Area of the Rector and Vice-Rectorates - General Secretariat	Verify the composition by sex of the candidates for rector and/or government team.
		Ensure parity in the management teams of the Faculties, Schools, Departments, Research Institutes of the ULPGC, as well as in the representative bodies of the teaching and research staff and administration and services staff.	During the term of the GEP	Central Electoral Board. Centers. Departments. University institutes	Check the number of women in the teams

		Develop actions and initiatives that promote female leadership.	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Equality Unity.	Number and type of actions carried out and data on attendees disaggregated by sex and group
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Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	Start/End	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Work-life balance and organizational culture	1. Ensure compliance with conciliation measures	Review and update the internal regulations regarding permits, licenses and vacations for PDI and PAS personnel	During the first and second year of validity of the GEP	General Secretary. Management. Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation	YES/NO
		Review and adapt the application for permits and licenses of the PDI so that it is consistent with the law and with the internal regulations of the ULPGC	In the first year of validity of the GEP	Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation. Management	YES/NO
		Assimilate the conciliation rights of the PDI to the PAS	During the first and second year of validity of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation	YES/NO
		Ensure that meetings are held preferably before 5:00 p.m.	During the term of the GEP	General Secretariat -All Vice Presidents - Management -Centers and Departments	Monitor possible queries and/or complaints of non-compliance
		Guarantee the preparation of a database, disaggregated by sex, for the monitoring of all permits, licenses and leave of absence requested by the PDI and PAS for the purpose of conciliation. As well as data on family conditions, number of children,	During the term of the GEP	Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation - Management	YES/NO

		dependents, and their ages.			
2. Promote co-responsible conciliation		Promote the dissemination, through the ULPGC website, of the rights in terms of conciliation of personal, family and work life between the PDI and the PAS of the ULPGC.	During the term of the PI Minimum 2 dissemination activities throughout the GEP	Office of the Vice-Rector for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation, Office of the Vice-Rector for Social Outreach and Communication, Management	Number and type of dissemination actions
		Develop training activities in order to promote co-responsibility	During the term of the GEP	Office of the Vice President for Teaching Staff, Academic Organization and Educational Innovation - Management -Equality Unit	Number and type of scheduled actions - Number of attendees disaggregated by sex and group
		Strengthen the offer of "summer campus" programs for the sons and daughters of PDI and PAS	During the term of the GEP	Vice President for Culture, Sports and Social Activation of the Campuses	Number of programs offered -Number of participants disaggregated by sex and group

Content Area	Specific Objective	Action within the GEP in Athena	TIME FRAME	Responsibility	Impact Assessment
Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	1. Raise awareness to prevent behaviors of sexual harassment and for reasons of sex-gender.	Promote dissemination measures among the university community of the Protocol on sexual and sex-gender harassment.	During the term of the GEP. Minimum two dissemination actions during the term of the GEP	Vice President for Social Projection and Communication. Occupational Risk Prevention Service. Equality Unit	Number and type of actions carried out

			During the term of the GEP	Equality Unit. Centers	Number and type of actions carried out
		Promote awareness and training actions.	During the term of the GEP	Equality Unit. Centers	Data of the attendees disaggregated by sex
			During the term of the GEP	Equality Unit. Centers	Subsequent survey of degree of knowledge
	2. Assessment of the Protocol for detection, prevention and action in cases of sexual harassment and for reasons of sex-gender.	Analyze the application of the Protocol regarding sexual and gender-based harassment.	During the first and second year of validity of the PI	Inspection Service. Occupational Risk Prevention Service. Equality Unit	YES/NO
		Assess the adequacy of the Protocol to all types of harassment and, where appropriate, propose its modification.	During the second and third year of validity of the PI	General Secretary. Inspection Service. Occupational Risk Prevention Service. Equality Unit	Evaluation report and fulfillment of its result

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7.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

Without prejudice to the fact that the Gender Equality Plan must be reviewed when the circumstances provided for in Spanish Law (RD 901/2020, of October 14), occur, the measures of the Plan may be reviewed at any time, in order to evaluate that they are effective and efficient with the in order to add, reorient, improve, correct, intensify, attenuate or even stop applying any measure that it contains depending on the effects that are appreciated in relation to the achievement of its objectives. The body in charge of carrying out the monitoring, evaluation and review will be the monitoring committee, which is made up of the same people who are members of the negotiating committee of this II Gender Equality Plan. To carry out these functions, the commission will meet at least once a year during the term of the Plan.

The II Gender Equality Plan of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria will be valid for four years from the date of its approval. This plan will apply to all workers at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria in any of its centres, faculties and schools.

For the implementation of the measures included in the II Gender Equality Plan, the responsible units of the University will allocate the means and resources, material and human, necessary to ensure compliance.

7.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

The II Equality Plan has been published on the website of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria in the section dedicated to the Equality Unit. This Unit also has a section of the ATHENA project. The link is as follows:

<https://www.ulpgc.es/igualdad/ii-plan-igualdad>

Likewise, the request has been submitted to register it on the official website, required by Spanish law, REGCON: Deposit and Registration of Collective Agreements, Equality Plans and other Collective Agreements. In this way, any natural or legal person can consult all the information related to the equality plan and the official documents for its preparation, development and approval.

As of September 2022, coinciding with the start of the new academic year, various dissemination and dissemination actions will be carried out. These actions are intended to publicize the II Equality Plan to the entire university community.

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Gender Equality Plan

Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS)

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8. SAS Gender Equality Plan

8.1 Introduction

You are reading the first ever Gender Equality Plan of the Slovak Academy of Sciences (GEP SAS). It was created in response to the need to promote equality and diversity at various levels of the SAS and also as a response to the natural evolution of the strategic direction of the European Research Area, of which we are a part. The European Research Area is continuously suffering a significant loss of female talents. The European Commission has been pointing to this challenge for years and encouraging Member States to take measures that¹⁰:

- remove barriers to the recruitment and career development of women researchers,
- address gender imbalances at the level of governance and decision-making,
- strengthen the gender perspective in research programmes.

The Horizon 2020-funded *Gendered Innovations* Expert Group ¹¹ in its report, outlines the key reasons for integrating the category of gender and/or sex in research and innovation. This integration:

- adds value to research in terms of excellence;
- increases creative and commercial opportunities in research;
- weakens existing stereotypes or gender norms and facilitates the introduction of new patterns;
- increases the societal relevance of research by addressing the diverse needs of the EU population;
- better responds to demand in new markets and provides overall support for goods and services that better respond to market needs.

There are several reasons for moving towards gender equality. In the context of the research¹²:

¹⁰ [European Commission's Communication for a Reinforced European Research Area \(2012\)](#)

¹¹ [Directorate-General for Research and Innovation \(European Commission\) \(2020\). Gendered innovations 2: How inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation : policy review.](#) Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, p. 8

¹² [Directorate-General for Research and Innovation \(European Commission\). \(2021\). Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\).](#) p. 8

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- Gender equality improves the quality of scientific outputs because it takes into account diverse perspectives and approaches.
- Gender equality creates better working conditions that help produce quality results and the potential of the whole team.
- Gender equality is a prevention of a talent loss.

The ability to reflect critically on gender in science and research and to promote the principles of gender equality (including intersectionality - multiple disadvantages due to gender and other characteristics, e.g. age, ethnicity, health status, etc.) thus become a key condition for the future of the European Research Area. Institutional and cultural change is a prerequisite for removing barriers to gender equality. We know that equality and the promotion of diversity in research workplaces helps to achieve better and more innovative outputs and develop research potential. Thanks to the Gender Equality Plan, the Slovak Academy of Sciences will also become one of the modern European research institutions. The Plan will help us to better reflect the dynamically changing world and to fulfil the vision and values of the Slovak Academy of Sciences.¹³

8.2 Development process and GEP management

GEP is built on the first-year work focused of gender audit and mutual cooperation with mostly internal stakeholders.

The data collection methodology was developed in the form of a gender audit within the project ATHENA - Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe by a team from the UVSK SAV in cooperation with Universitatea din Bucuresti (Romania), Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach (Poland) and Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation SL (Spain, main coordinator of the project).

The data collection took place during the months of March - December 2021. In the first step, the project team from the UVSK SAV evaluated the published annual reports from all SAS organisations (47 workplaces in total). The aim of the first step was to obtain publicly available data for quantitative GEA indicators. In the second step, we identified missing data for the indicators and created a query letter that was sent to all SAV organizations to obtain additional input necessary for the evaluation of the indicators. The request letter was sent repeatedly, leaving a final number of 30 to obtain data. Of the 30 organizations, several did not provide a more in-depth analysis regarding salary inputs, typically reporting lack of time or privacy concerns. Despite

¹³ [Stratégia SAV 2030 \(SAS Strategy 2030\)](#)

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repeated requests for data, including extensions to the delivery deadline, 17 SAV organizations did not provide additional inputs for data collection.¹⁴

Gender equality indicators were clustered into 6 dimensions:

- The pool of graduate talents
- Gender balance in research
- Gender balanced career advancement
- Gender balance in decision making
- Gender balanced working conditions
- Gender balance in research outputs

The basis for the indicators was the European data collection system on women in science, *She Figures*.¹⁵ The data collection included tracking qualitative aspects of gender equality measures in the institution. Most of the indicators were inspired by mapping already from the project submission phase and the EIGE GEAR tools.¹⁶ In total, we evaluated 59 instruments and policies relevant to gender equality in research.

SAS Presidency approved the GEP in December 2021 based on preliminary data from gender audit. Nevertheless, in October and November 2021, the gender audit continued with its qualitative inquiry, using semi-structured interviews and focus groups to learn about personal experiences with gender equality issues and views on gender equality in the SAS. At the same time, a survey was realized in order to gain a deeper understanding of existing gender biases. The results from this phase of the gender audit will be considered and incorporated in the next version of the SAS Gender Equality Plan.

Details of the methodology can be found online at the project website [ATHENA Equality - Gender Equality to Unlock Research Potential](#). The preparation and implementation of the Gender Equality Plan is done in cooperation with the GEPI (Gender Equality Plan Implementation) Project Committee of the H2020 ATHENA project.

¹⁴ Here, we would like to express our gratitude and acknowledgement to all the staff members who, beyond the scope of their work duties, devoted time and energy to the questionnaire, participated in the data collection and thus contributed to a better understanding of the state of gender equality in the SAS

¹⁵ EC (2019). *She Figure 2018*; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019; Dostupné na: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>; EC (2019). *She Figures Handbook 2018*; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019; Available at <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/09d777dc-447c-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹⁶ EIGE (2016). *Gender Equality In Academia And Research, Gear Tool*; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016; Available at: https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/mh0716096enn_1.pdf

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The SAS Presidency adopts the Gender Equality Plan as a strategic document of SAS. It becomes binding for all SAS organisations upon their accession to the document. They thus subscribe to the value of gender equality in research and will participate in the implementation of the objectives of this strategic document, including ongoing monitoring.

8.2.1 Coordination of gender equality activities (human resources)

The coordination of activities, including long-term monitoring, is the responsibility of the SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities. As the document is published as an output of the H2020 ATHENA project - Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe, the Institute for Research in Social Communication SAS (UVSK SAV) together with the GEPI Commission of the H2020 ATHENA project are involved in its implementation for the duration of the project.

8.2.2 Financial allocation for gender equality

SAS Presidency hereby undertakes to fund, to the extent necessary, all activities for which it is named as a source of funding for SAS (namely in the form of covering staff costs, services and indirect costs).

8.2.3 Linkage of the Gender Equality Plan with other strategic documents

The Gender Equality Plan is to be implemented in synergy with the following strategic documents of the SAS:

- [SAV 2030](#);
- [SAV Chairmanship Action Plan - SAV 2021 \(and the forthcoming SAV Chairmanship Action Plan SAV 2025\)](#);
- [European charter and code for researchers](#);
- [HRS4R - SAV Action Plan](#);
- [Code of Ethics of the SAS](#).

8.3 Diagnosis

Since March 2021, a gender audit has been realized at the SAS organizations to gain a deeper understanding of the current state of GE. We are currently presenting preliminary results on quantitative indicators and selected qualitative indicators in the area of measures to promote gender equality. At the same time, data collection through interviews and focus groups, including a questionnaire survey on gender bias,

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continues until the end of 2021¹⁷. These results will be considered in subsequent versions of the Gender Equality Plan.

8.3.1 Vertical segregation

Vertical segregation refers to the concentration of men or women in senior or management. Such roles are often associated with 'desirable' functions, including higher pay, prestige and security. In the context of research and innovation, an example of such segregation is the high representation of men among senior managers in scientific institutions and universities.

The representation of women and the proportion of women in individual positions in the SAS is an important, but not the only, indicator of the state of GE. In 2020, women accounted for 54% of all SAS employees. However, this ratio is not reflected equally at all levels. As in other EU countries¹⁸, the phenomenon of the 'leaky pipeline' is also emerging at the SAS. While women dominate in non-scientific positions (other staff, professional staff with a full secondary education and professional staff with a university degree) (up to 71 %), this predominance drops to 57 % in the case of professional staff (research and development staff) and 44 % in the case of scientific staff (scientific staff).

¹⁷ We are presenting the approved version of GEP at SAS from December 2021. In the next version, data from the whole audit will be considered, together with the first insights from the monitoring.

¹⁸ Dubois-Shaik, F. & Fusulier, B. (Eds.). (2015). *Academic Careers and Gender Inequality: Leaky Pipeline and Interrelated Phenomena in Seven European Countries*. University of Trento, Via Calepina. Available at: https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/garcia_working_paper_5_academic_careers_gender_inequality.pdf

Figure 6: The so-called leaky pipeline: representation of women and men in different positions at the SAS

Data source: 2020 Annual Reports of SAS organisations

Figure 7: Comparison of the representation of PhD graduates and currently employed researchers at the SAS

Data source: 2020 Annual Reports of SAS organisations

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8.3.1.1 Glass ceiling index in personal scientific growth

The glass ceiling metaphor represents the invisible barriers that women face in their career advancement. The glass ceiling index is an indicator that draws our attention to the proportion of women in academia and research (in positions A, B, C: in the Slovak context, qualification level I, IIa and IIb) in proportion to the representation of women in top academic positions (qualification level I). A score of 1 indicates that there is no difference between men and women in the chances of career advancement. A score of less than 1 reflects that women are more likely to be represented in the institution at the top academic position. Conversely, a score greater than 1 indicates the presence of a glass ceiling, a situation where women are less often represented in the highest academic positions. The higher the number, the thicker this imaginary glass ceiling.¹⁹

While the EU has a glass ceiling index of 1.64 for 2016 and Slovakia has a total of 1.74 for 2016²⁰, SAV achieves an index of **1.83** in 2020.

SAS score 1.83 in 2020 in the glass ceiling index. This indicates that women are disadvantaged in their career progression.

8.3.1.2 Women in leadership and management

The gender disbalance in the SAS representation is most pronounced in the area of management. The Slovak Academy of Sciences has never been headed by a woman. Only 20% of the current Presidency members of the Slovak Academy of Sciences are women. In the Scientific Council of the SAS, there are 18.2% of female members (including external members and members). There are 19 women in the position of Director of the Institute/Centre out of 47 positions (40.4%), and 20 women (34.5%) in the position of Deputy Director/ out of 58 positions.

Figure 8: Representation of women and men in the Presidium of the SAS

Women
Men

¹⁹ [She figures handbook 2018 - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁰ The year 2016 is given because it is the latest available figure. [She figures 2018 - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

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Figure 9: Representation of women and men in the Scientific Council of the SAS

Figure 10: Representation of women and men in the position of director of the SAS organisations

Data source: the SAS website (2020)

8.3.2 Horizontal segregation

Horizontal segregation refers to the concentration of women or men in different sectors (sectoral segregation) and occupations (occupational segregation). It can occur within fields of study or scientific disciplines. Unlike vertical segregation, these fields of study or scientific disciplines are not ranked according to a particular criterion. However, the problem of horizontal segregation can lead to greater vertical segregation.

Within the SAS, horizontal segregation is most evident in the field of technical and natural sciences (when looking at the total number of male and female researchers). Men are slightly predominant even in the humanities and social sciences. Women dominate in the medical sciences and slightly in the agricultural sciences.

However, despite the heterogeneous proportion of women across scientific disciplines in the organisations of the SAS, we also see a noticeable vertical segregation - men dominate in the category of professorships and in qualification level I (with the exception of the medical sciences). Conversely, as qualification and position decreases, the ratio skews in favour of female representation for almost all scientific fields.

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We have broken down horizontal segregation into R&D disciplines according to the so-called Frascati Manual²¹ as follows.

Table 13: SAS organizations

Scientific fields	SAS organizations	
Natural sciences	Astronomical Institute SAS Institute of Geography Institute of Hydrology Institute of Physics Mathematical Institute Institute of Experimental Physics Earth Science Institute of the SAS	Centre of Biosciences SAS Institute of Chemistry SAS Institute of Inorganic Chemistry Institute of Molecular Biology Polymer Institute Institute of Zoology SAS
Technology	Centre for Advanced Materials Application SAS Institute of Electrical Engineering SAS Institute of Geotechnics SAS Institute of Informatics	Institute of Materials and Machine Mechanics Institute of Material Research Institute of Measurement Science Institute of Construction and Architecture
Medical sciences	Biomedical Research Center SAS Centre of Experimental Medicine SAS	Institute of Neuroimmunology
Agriculture	Plant Science and Biodiversity Center SAS Institute of Parasitology	Institute of Forest Ecology Institute of Landscape Ecology
Social sciences	Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences SAS Institute of Economic Research	Institute for Sociology Institute of Political Sciences SAS Institute of State and Law Institute for Research in Social Communication SAS
Humanities	Art Research Centre of SAS Ludovit Stur Institute of Linguistics Jan Stanislav Institute of Slavistics SAS Institute of Musicology Institute of Oriental Studies Institute of Slovak Literature	Institute of World Literature Institute of Archaeology Institute of History Institute of Philosophy SAS

²¹ [Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development \(oecd-ilibrary.org\)](https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/frascati-manual-2015)

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Figure 11: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Natural sciences at SAS

Figure 12: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Technology at SAS

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Figure 13: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Medical sciences at SAS

Figure 14: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Agriculture at SAS

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Figure 15: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Social sciences at SAS

Figure 16: Vertical segregation within the horizontal segregation – Humanities at SAS

Data source: 2020 Annual Reports of SAS organisations

8.3.3 Working conditions

Within the area of working conditions and GE, our audit focused on pay gap, the use of maternity and parental leave and so-called precarious working conditions as part of the quantitative data collection.²² According to the gender pay gap indicator, the findings are incomplete and have significant limitations. The total gender pay gap at the level of the SAS in unadjusted form²³ could not be ascertained due to data unavailability. Only 23 organisations provided overall average data covering all their male/female employees. In addition, 15 organisations provided a more detailed breakdown of the data: separately for all male and female scientists and also for a subset of them – category of independent male and female scientists. Analysis of this incomplete data indicates a gender pay gap for all overall staff of 9.2% against women; for female scientists, the gap was smaller at almost 3% against women. Paradoxically, it was found that in the sub-category of independent scientists, the difference was reversed - of 8.25% against men. This is apparently a specific situation in the environment of the 2nd Department of Sciences (from where the vast majority of the data were provided). The career acceleration of women is evident in this environment (this finding can be contrasted with the identical trend in the representation of women in qualification I (senior female scientists), which is highest in the medical, agricultural and natural sciences. The ambition of the future pay gap survey is to identify the overall gender pay gap for all organizations of the SAS, but also differences in personal allowances, remuneration and the breakdown of the individual departments of the SAS.

Table 14: 'Unadjusted' gender income gap in SAV (% , 2020)

Job classification	Gender income gap (%)
All employees (23 SAV institutes)	9,20
Independent researchers (15 institutes of the SAS)	- 8,25
Researchers (15 SAS institutes)	2,93

Note: The gender income gap is the difference between the average monthly functional salaries (i.e. excluding miscellaneous bonuses) of men and women, expressed as a percentage of men's average earnings. Positive values indicate the percentage by which women's salaries are lower than men's; negative values indicate the lower average salaries of men compared to women.

²² Precarious working conditions refer to a variety of conditions that put an employee at a disadvantage compared to others. These can be short-term contracts, contracts outside the employment relationship, which deprive the person concerned of some of the protections and benefits that come with the employment relationship. For more information, see e.g. [European Institute for Gender Equality, \(2017\). Gender, skills and precarious work in the EU Research note](#)

²³ The gender pay gap is defined as "unadjusted" because it provides an overall picture of gender inequalities in terms of pay and measures a concept that is broader than the concept of equal pay for equal work. All employees working without age or hours worked are included (Eurostat, [Gender pay gap in unadjusted form - Products Datasets - Eurostat \(europa.eu\)](#)).

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Source: based on data requested from SAV organisations.

Examples of precarious working conditions may include fixed-term contracts, contracts for less than 12 months or work under performance agreements. The SAS survey found that slightly more women work on fixed-term contracts (434 compared to 339 men), slightly more men work on contracts of less than 12 months (115 men compared to 94 women), and similarly for outside employment contracts (140 men and 129 women). All of these forms of cooperation are in a sense less protected by the Labour Code. Institutes and centres often have to resort to these forms of cooperation because of their participation in projects that bring in time-limited wage resources.

At the same time, fixed-term contracts may raise problems in the context of maternity and parental leave. The trend towards a change in the ratio of maternity and parental leave is gradually reaching SAS organisations: in 2020, 8 men and 66 women were taking maternity or parental leave. In terms of days on maternity/parental leave, women clearly outnumbered men (10 089 days) compared to men (178 days),²⁴ while it is useful to track the differences in how many days women stay at home with young children, which has implications for career progression.

8.3.4 Gender equality in research outputs

Poorer working conditions in terms of career breaks due to parental responsibilities, lower and less valued jobs, as well as lower participation in decision-making, can be barriers to the full use of women's scientific potential and talent. We investigated whether the worsened conditions are reflected in publishing and project activity.

8.3.4.1 Publication activity

He realized an analysis of first authorship in top scientific publications, carried out in cooperation with the Central Library of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. We used the balance of the ratio:

F/M as first authors

²⁴ Note: the number of days may not represent actual days of absence from work - for example, there are known cases of maternity/parental leave and concurrent work, part-time but sometimes full-time (especially for men who receive maternity leave, remain in employment and the child is still cared for by the child's mother).

F/M all authors

Table 15: Ratio of first authorship to authorship of men and women in the SAS

Section I			Section II			Section III		
Foreign outputs	Slovak output	All	Foreign outputs	Slovak output	All	Foreign outputs	Slovak output	All
AAA	AAB ADD		AAA	AAB ADD		AAA	AAB ADD ADN	
ADC	ADN		ADC	ADN		ADC		
ADM			ADM			ADM		
1,738	1,417	1,714	1,260	1,447	1,291	1,050	1,076	1,074

Note: The index expresses the ratio of Ž/M of first authorship to Ž/M of all authorship s
Source of data: the Central Library of the Slovak Academy of Sciences

This index is relative, based on the actual status of female/male authorship, and does not show how many female and male authors, or first authors, there are in absolute numbers. It only reflects the ratio of women to men in the categories of first authorship. The baseline parameter was the ratio of women to men in the authorship category. The figures in the table show that the **ratio of women to men is 1.05 to 1.738 times higher** in the first authorship category **than it is in the overall authorship category**. Relatively, the highest proportion of female first authorship is in Section 1 of the sciences (1.714). The lowest, but still above 1.0, it is in the Section 3 (1.074). Thus, women figure as first authors (relative to men) in the Section 3 about as much as they figure in the authorship category relative to men.

The current analysis has limitations due to the different practice of reporting the order of authors across disciplines. In Section 1, it is reportedly a predominantly alphabetical order (although order by contribution to publication also occurs). In Section 2, the order of authors is governed by the rate of contribution to the publication (but combined with the rate of contribution attributed to the corresponding author). In the Section 3, we encounter both approaches, with both alphabetical ranking and ranking by contribution. Therefore, the table is mostly valuable for the Section 2. In any case, this is one of the few positive findings of the gender audit in the SAS.

8.3.4.2 Project activity

In the gender audit, we surveyed the proportion of women among principal investigators in different types of national and international projects. In 2020, women accounted for a total of 40% of principal investigators in national projects and 43 % of principal investigators of international projects of type A (where the SAS organisation is a coordinator) and 31 % of international projects of type B (the SAS organisation is

a co-investigator). These proportions are close to the actual representation of women scientists (44 % women) in the whole SAS, but not to the proportion of women researchers with the highest scientific qualifications.

We also monitored the proportions of projects submitted and currently implemented. For national type A projects, male coordinators are more successful than women (4.7 times more successful); the opposite trend is present in the field of international projects, where women are more successful (10.8 times more successful) when comparing projects submitted and projects currently implemented. For international B projects, the success rate again skews in favour of men (2.3 times more successful) in the ratio of projects submitted to projects successful. These figures represent a cross-section for 2020, so they do not consider possible distortions due to grant call announcements, etc.²⁵ Together with the indicators of the high proportion of women as first authors of top scientific publications, these findings are promising signs the possibility of a positive development.

8.3.5 Selected qualitative indicators of gender equality in SAV

The gender audit also mapped qualitative indicators of gender equality in the areas of talent management, gender balance in research, career advancement, management and decision-making, working conditions, working atmosphere and scientific outputs. In total, there were 59 indicators in different dimensions. As a result of the assessment, we found that a number of existing tools for promoting gender equality, which we set as indicators, have never been implemented or information on implementation is missing. This was particularly the case in the area of mentoring programmes, scholarships to support women or policies for transparent selection and career advancement. Similarly, there is still a lack of activities at SAV aimed at increasing awareness or support for reconciling family and work life, e.g. in the form of a children's centre, which has been piloted in the past.

Table 16: Selected examples of qualitative indicators in talent management

No	Indicator	Status at SAS
1.	Gender dimension in the research	0 - no information
2.	Scholarships and grants to support career development for female scientists	1 - has never been implemented
3.	Support for dual-career couples	1 - has never been implemented
4.	Career mentoring for female scientists	1 - has never been implemented
5.	Fellowship offered to women students/researchers only	1 - has never been implemented
6.	Specific trainings/seminars on academic publishing for women students/scientists	1 - has never been implemented

²⁵ The data were drawn from the annual reports of the SAS organisations and additional data were requested directly from the SAS organisations.

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7.	Gender balance is taken into account for the recruitment of administrative and academic/research staff	0 - no information
8.	Use of gender-sensitive language in the wording of job descriptions	0 - no information
9.	All male and female applicants are invited as part of the recruitment process, but under-represented gender is highlighted	1 - has never been implemented
10.	Information on internal promotion opportunities is presented to all equally	0 - no information
11.	There is a non-discriminatory gender/gender policy in recruitment	1 - has never been implemented

8.3.5.1 Synergy between the Gender Equality Plan and HRS4R

The issue of gender equality does not exist in isolation; it is deeply embedded in the existing system, for example in human resources management. The Gender Equality Plan should be implemented in synergy with the European Charter for Women Researchers, the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and be in line with the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) as implemented. This is because gender issues go beyond sex/gender, but are also linked to, for example, cultural background. It was the GAP analysis (gap analysis)²⁶ in the preparation of the HRS4R that identified the absence of documents in English as one of the key barriers in the field of human resources management.

There is also a lack of clearer and more transparent recruitment standards, lack of wheelchair accessibility in the organisations' buildings, lack of support for parents (e.g. in the form of a nursery school). The GAP analysis confirmed and highlighted the issue of gender imbalance in management and decision-making. Clearer career support strategies are also absent. There is therefore a need for the Gender Equality Plan to be implemented in synergy with the HRS4R Action Plan for SAS.²⁷

8.4 Objectives

The SAS Gender Equality Plan covers the following 5 areas after considering the available gender audit data. The activities of this plan, as well as those of future plans, should consider not only the intervention activities on eliminating inequalities, but to prevent gender inequalities and their consequences.

²⁶ [Gap Analysis \(sav.sk\)](#)

²⁷ [HRS4R akčný plán \(sav.sk\)](#)

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Figure 17. Content areas within the UVSK SAV GEP

These goals were identified under suggested areas:

- Goal 1: The Slovak Academy of Sciences actively supports the work-life balance among employees.
- Goal 2: The Slovak Academy of Sciences promotes equal representation of women and men in management and decision-making in organisations of the SAS.
- Goal 3: The Slovak Academy of Sciences actively promotes gender equality in the recruitment process and in career development.
- Goal 4: Research conducted at the SAS integrates a gender perspective.
- Goal 5: The Slovak Academy of Sciences promotes a work environment free of gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

8.5 Actions

GEP Action plan is provided in the next table:

Table 17. Actions implemented for SAS' GEP

Content area	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
Work-life balance and organisational culture	Objective 1.1. Support for employees in the context of maternity/parenthood (on, during and after maternity/parental leave)	Action 1.1.1. Development of a maternity/parenting plan together with recommendations and examples of good practice	01.01. 2022-30. 6. 2022	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, Office of the SAS	Elaborated document	Lack of interest, lack of awareness on the published document, limited implemented actions which will be recommended in the documents	Working groups will be prepared
	Objective 1.2.: Familiarizing employees with the issue of alignment of work and private life.	Action 1.2.1. Gender equality training for male and female employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	1. 1. 2022 - 31.12. 2023	ATHENA project team	25 trained employees	Time constrains, lack of interest from employees	Intense promotion of the trainings
	Objective 1.3. Supporting fathers' involvement in childcare through maternity and parental leave	Action 1.3.1. Presentation of "role models" in the Academy magazine	Annually	Press Department of the Slovak Academy of Sciences	Published interviews	Not identified	
	Objective 1.4.: Kindergarten for the needs of SAS employees	Action 1.4.1.: Explore the possibilities of establishing a kindergarten in the SAS campus in Patrónka	2022	SAS Presidium	Feasibility strategy	Limited options to adopt innovative policies, lack of resources	Possible problem: lack of resources can be tackled through EU funds
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Objective 2.1. Familiarizing employees with the issue of gender equality in the field of management	Action 2.1.1. Trainings in the field gender equality within the ATHENA project.	1. 1. 2022 - 31.12. 2023	ATHENA project team	25 trained employees	Time constrains, lack of interest	Intense promotion of the trainings

	Objective 2.2. Increase the proportion of women in the Presidium of SAS, in the Board of the SAS Assembly and the management of organizations of the Scientific section 1 and 3 (in synergy with HRS4R)	Action 2.2.1 Survey of barriers to considering candidacy of women. Communication with organisations on the preparation candidates to the corresponding positions.	2022, 2023, 2024	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS Presidium (SAS P)	Analysis of barriers, increase ratio of women in decision making	Limited possibilities to implement certain actions based on the data	Several members of the GEPI committee are also members of the SAS Presidency - they can tackle the challenge.
	Objective 2.3. Support for career development with emphasis on young female scientific workers	Action 2.3.1 Explore the possibility of creating a mentoring programmes with emphasis on young female researchers, pilot training of mentors	2023	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS P, Young Scientists at SAS, UVSK SAV	Knowledge capital, existing trainings modified for mentoring purposes, networkings	Time constrains, lack of interest	Deeper involvement of the organization of Young Scientists
	Objective 2.4. Management training for higher management employees on the issue gender equality	Action 2.4.1 Module integration gender equality in existing platforms training	2022	SAS Presidium	Implementation training	Time constrains, lack of interest	Involvement of GEPI members
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Objective 3.1. Supporting gender equality in the recruitment process	Action 3.1.1. Supporting gender equality in the recruitment process (in synergy with HRS4R activity), including recommendations to prevent conflicts of interest in gender equality selection procedures	1.1.2022 - 30.6. 2022	SAS Ethics Committee, SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS P, Office of the SAS	Published document	Formalization of the procedure without direct actions	Can be aimed at the trainings provided.

		Ensure the use of gender-sensitive language in advertisements and welcome packs in accordance with HRS4R activities	1. 1. 2022 - 30. 6. 2022	SAS Office, Press department, Presidium of SAS	Directive	Formalization of the procedure without direct actions	Involvement of GEPI members, involvement the Press department in trainings
	Objective 3.2. Sensitising male and female employees to the gender equality issues in the recruitment and career development	Action 3.2.1. Gender equality training for male and female employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	1. 1. 2022 - 31.12. 2023	Athena project team	25 trained employees	Time constrains, lack of interest	Intense promotion of the trainings
	Objective 3.3. Strengthening gender equality in senior research degrees and among postdoctoral fellows	Action 3.3.1. Survey of barriers, communication of P SAV with SAS organisations on the preparation of the conditions for candidates	Ongoing	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS Presidium	Analysis of barriers, numbers/ proportions	Limited possibilities to implement certain actions based on the data	Several members of the GEPI committee are also members of the SAS Presidency - they can tackle the challenge.
	Objective 3.4. Measuring income inequalities by gender	Action 3.4.1. Preparation of calculation and data methodology	2022	SAS Presidium, Athena project team	Academic statistics	Time constrains, lack of interest	
Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Objective 4.1. Promotion of the issue gender perspective in research and teaching	Action 4.1.1. Gender training equality for employees of the Slovak Academy of Sciences within the ATHENA project	1. 1. 2022 - 31.12. 2023	Athena project team	25 trained employees	Time constrains, lack of interest	Intense promotion of the trainings

	Objective 4.2. Implementation of analytical focus on gender equality to research applications projects (VEGA and international projects)	Action 4.2.1. Professional event	2022 - 2023	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS Presidium	Proposal, Implementation, Evaluation applications based on reporting	Time constrains	Several members of the GEPI committee are also members of the SAS Presidency - they can tackle the challenge.
	Objective 4.3. Regular monitoring gender perspective in research SAS	Action 4.3.1. Implementing to the structure of the annual reports an item relating to gender mainstreaming, mostly in research and teaching	31.10.2022 Annually	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, SAS Presidium	Renovated structure for annual reports	Action was already implemented	
	Objective 4.4. Creation of an expert platform researchers, who integrate a gender perspective equality into your research	Action 4.4.1 Examining the staff possibilities to develop the expert platform which may be in charge of selected GEP actions	2022	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities, ATHENA project team	Create a basis for platform, VEGA Project proposal	Time constrains	Several members of the GEPI committee are also members of the SAS P - they can tackle the challenge.
Measures against gender-based violence,	Objective 5.1. Familiarizing staff to gender equality issues in the area of gender-based violence, including	Action 5.1.1. Gender equality training for SAV staff within the ATHENA project (including training of trainers)	1. 1. 2022 - 31.12. 2023	ATHENA team project	25 trained employees	Limited interest from the management of the institutions/centres	Intense promotion of the trainings

including sexual harassment	sexual harassment	Action 5.1.2. Training on gender-based violence for directors and vice-directors of SAV organisations and trade union representatives (possibly for other target groups)	2022, beginning 2023	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities	Training for directors and other stakeholders	Limited interest from the management of the institutions/centres	Intense promotion of the trainings
	Objective 5.2. Establishment of a guideline on preventing and addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment	Action 5.2.1. Adopt an internal regulation against gender-based violence and sexual harassment (in synergy with HRS4R)	31. 12. 2022	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities	Adoption of the regulation, informing organisations	Time-constraints, lack of awareness of the policy	Intense promotion of the trainings, visibility of the document

8.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

The Gender Equality Plan will be subject to regular monitoring. Monitoring will be carried out through the annual reports of the SAS organisations and by collecting additional data in cooperation with the SAS organisations. The UVSK SAV, within the *H2020 project ATHENA Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe*, will develop a monitoring system and will subsequently be involved in three monitoring cycles (end of 2022, 2023 and 2024), these activities will be a part of the project tasks.

SAS Presidency together with SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities have the main responsibility for monitoring of the GEP with the Institute for Research in Social Communication providing monitoring tools, including recommendations on the sustainability of activities.

Table 18. SAS GEP Monitoring

Partial objectives	Activities and tools	Deadline	Responsibility	Indicators	Budget
Support for regular monitoring of activities	Monitoring	Once a year	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities ATHENA project team (until 2024)	Submitted and approved monitoring report	SAS, ATHENA project budget allocation
	Alignment of monitoring indicators with the structure of the annual report of the SAS organizations	Once a year	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities Presidium of SAS	VS provides source materials for the selection of monitored indicators	SAS
Support for participatory revision creation of the Gender Equality Plan	Informing about the possibility of participating in the revision of the PRR SAS	Once a year	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities	Announcement on the SAS website in the news section, communication with the SAS organizations	SAS
Support for the sustainability of the activities of the SAS Gender Equality Plan	Creating an annual report on the fulfilling of the PRR	Once a year	SAS Commission for Equal Opportunities	Report on the fulfilment of the action plan	SAS
	Creation of the position of "persons responsible for coordination, monitoring and implementation of selected activities in the area of gender equality"	January 2022	Presidium of SAS	Created and occupied position with adequate time and financial allocation	SAS

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8.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

The Gender Equality Plan is a publicly available document. It is the responsibility of the SAS Office and the directors of the adhering organisations to act in accordance with the GEP and to inform their employees of its wording and the tasks it entails.

8.8 Annex: Lists of international and national policies

List of relevant international policies

- [Universal Declaration of Human Rights in December 1948](#);
- [International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights \(ICESCR\)](#);
- [Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women \(CEDAW\)](#);
- [The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action \(BDPA\)](#);
- [Millennium Development Goals \(MDGs\)](#);
- [Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\)](#);
- [UNESCO's Convention against Discrimination in Education \(CADE\)](#);
- [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#);
- [European Pillar of Social Rights](#);
- [Gender Action Plan III for 2021-2025 \(GAP III\)](#);
- [Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2024](#).

List of national policies

- Act No. 460/1992 Coll. Constitution of the Slovak Republic (Zákon č. 460/1992 Z.z. Ústava Slovenskej republiky);
- Act No. 365/2004 Coll. on Equal Treatment in Certain Areas and on Protection against Discrimination and on Amendment of Certain Acts (Anti-discrimination Act), (Zákon č. 365/2004 Z.z. o rovnakom zaobchádzaní v niektorých oblastiach a o ochrane pred diskrimináciou a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov (antidiskriminačný zákon));
- Act No. 311/2001 Coll. on the Labour Code (Zákon č. 311/2001 Z.z. Zákonník práce);
- Act No. 552/2003 Coll. on Works Performed in the Public Interest (Zákon č. 552/2003 Z.z. o výkone práce vo verejnom záujme);
- Act No. 461/2003 Coll. on Social Insurance (Zákon č. 461/2003 Z.z. o sociálnom poistení)
- Act No. 124/2006 Coll. on Work Safety and Health (Zákon č. 124/2006 Z.z. o bezpečnosti a ochrane zdravia pri práci);
- Act No. 125/2006 Coll. on Labour Inspection (Zákon č. 125/2006 Z.z. o inšpekcii práce);

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- [National Strategy for Equality between Women and Men and Equal Opportunities in the Slovak Republic for 2021-2027 and Action Plan for Equality between Women and Men and Equal Opportunities for 2021-2027](#)
- The Law on Public Research Institutions, No 243/2017, available at <http://www.zakonypreludi.sk/zz/2017-243>
- Act No. 131/2002 Coll. on Higher Education (Zákon č. 131/2002 Z.z. o vysokých školách);
- Act No. 245/2008 on Education (Schools Act) (Zákon č. 245/2009 Z.z. o výchove a
- vzdelávaní (školský zákon)
- National Programme for Education Development (“Learning Slovakia”). https://www.minedu.sk/data/files/6987_uciace_sa_slovensko.pdf
- The task for Audit of the research and innovation system, https://www.vedatechnika.sk/SK/VedaATechnikaVSR/Rada%20vldy/9.%20Rokovanie%2016_3_2017/6%20Audit%20syst%C3%A9mu%20v%C3%BDskumu%20a%20inov%C3%A1ci%C3%AD%20v%20SR/Material_AuditSystemuValvSR.pdf
- [Roadmap of research infrastructures - SK VI Roadmap 2020 - 2030](#)
- [Slovak Recovery and Resilience Plan](#)

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Gender Equality Plan

University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
(URAK)

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9. URAK Gender Equality Plan

9.1 Introduction

The Gender Equality Plan at University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev" was developed as a result of the ATHENA Project (101006416-ATHENA-H2020-SwafS-2018-2020/H2020 - SwafS - 2020 - 1).

The plan complies with the normative acts of national law - the Constitution of the Republic of Bulgaria, the Law on Protection against Discrimination, the Law on Equality between Women and Men (Official Gazette No. 33 of 26.04.2016), as well as with the acts of European Union law (gender equality is a core value of the EU, a fundamental right and a fundamental principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights)²⁸ and with international treaties to which the Republic of Bulgaria is a party.²⁹

The plan was developed in accordance with the National Strategy for the Promotion of Equality between Women and Men 2021-2030, adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers No. 969 of 30 December 2020 and the National Action Plan for the Promotion of Equality between Women and Men for the period 2021-2022, taking into account the specifics of the activity of RU "Angel Kanchev" as a higher school within the meaning of the Law on Higher Education. The guidelines of the European Institute for Gender Equality for the development and implementation of plans for equality between women and men are also taken into account.³⁰

9.2 Development process and GEP management

Priority areas:

- equality of women and men in access to educational services, in obtaining scientific degrees, in holding academic positions and in concluding labor and civil contracts at Ruse University "Angel Kanchev" (URAK).
- non-admission of gender differences in the payment of remuneration, additional material incentives and scholarships.

²⁸ See Art. 2 and Art. 3, paragraph 3 of the TEU, Art. 8, 10, 19 and 157 of the TFEU and Art. 21 and 23 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU; The EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (COM/2020/152 final); European Pillar of Social Rights.

²⁹ The 1995 Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (<https://beijing20.unwomen.org/en/about>), the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, the Sustainable Development Goals and the Sustainable Development Agenda 2030, the European Pillar of Social Rights, etc.

³⁰ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/step-step-guide>.

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- promoting the equality of women and men in the decision-making processes in the management bodies of Ruse University "Angel Kanchev" (General Assembly, Academic Council, Rector, Student Council), as well as in the management bodies of the main units (faculties, branches, departments) and service units (administrative directorates and departments) combating violence and protecting and supporting victims;
- overcoming gender stereotypes in various spheres of public life and sexism (measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment).

9.3 Diagnosis

In order to achieve the goals of the plan in the priority areas, measures have been developed to achieve specific results, with deadlines and University bodies responsible for the implementation of the measures, as well as indicators of results and impact.

After the in-principle acceptance of the main document by the AC of the University of Ruse, it will be supplemented with an impact matrix and a calendar of events harmonizing with Areas 1-5 until the end of the Project ATHENA program period.

9.4 Objectives

The main objectives of the plan are:

- through amendments and additions to the internal acts of the University and implementation of various activities to create a permanent normative and institutional environment that will contribute to the de facto equality of women and men (students, doctoral students, administrative staff and academic staff) in the University.
- to ensure the implementation of a uniform policy of equality between women and men in all activities carried out by the University.
- to ensure permanent prevention against direct and indirect discrimination on the basis of gender, as well as on the basis of other discriminatory characteristics such as race, nationality, ethnicity, human genome, citizenship, origin, religion or belief, education, beliefs, political affiliation, personal or social status, disability, age, marital status, property status or any other characteristics established by law or in an international treaty to which the Republic of Bulgaria is a party.

9.5 Actions

This is the main section of the GEP, which is devoted to designing an action plan to promote GE. This section should address the following:

- Description of actions to be undertaken under each specific objective.
- Actions should be structured around the five thematic areas recommended by the EC.

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- Include a table of specific objectives and actions in line with the ATHENA table template below.

Table 19. Actions for URAK GEP

Action No.	Content area	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment	Success stories	Problems encountered during implementation	Strategies to solve the problem
1	Work-life balance and organizational culture	1. Annual information on existing state of the ratio between men and women in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration.	Get current information about the ratio between men and women in teaching, research and administrative activities.	Term: permanent.	Academic Staff Development.	Reflecting on the state in the Rector's annual report on the activities of the University to the General Assembly.	Publicity of information.	Acceptance of the proposed changes by different boards at URAK.	General Strategy for Area No. 1. Ensuring conditions for equality of women and men through access to educational services, when obtaining scientific degrees, when occupying academic positions and when concluding labor and civil contracts in the University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev" and an equal degree of economic independence.
		2. Preparation of a project for an addition to the Regulations for the activities of the University, including provisions for the non-admission of discrimination against based on gender and other discriminatory characteristics established in a law or in an international treaty by which the Republic of Bulgaria is a party in carrying out the activities of the University. Accepting of the suggestions of General Assembly.	Creating lasting internal regulatory framework guaranteeing equality between women and men.	Deadline: first upcoming General Assembly of the University.	Head of Education Sector.	Amended Regulations for activity of the university, determination of rights and obligations in connection with the guarantee of the equality between women and men and prevention other forms of discrimination.	Publicity, introduction and application of The regulations for activity of the university.	Lack of interest, lack of awareness on the published document, limited implemented actions which will be recommended in the documents.	

	<p>3. Preparation of project proposals for amendments and additions to other internal acts of the University, adopted by the Academic Council with regulations regarding equality between women and men and their approval by the Academic Council.</p>	<p>Creating lasting internal regulatory base guaranteeing equality between women and men.</p>	<p>Term: 1. 08. 22 - 30.10. 2022.</p>	<p>Dean of the Faculty of Law. Chairman of the Board of Directors.</p>	<p>Updated internal acts of the University including regulations to prevent discrimination Altered Ethical code of teachers and the employees of URAK.</p>	<p>Publicity. Accessibility of the acts of the inside page of the university.</p>	<p>Acceptance of the proposed changes by different boards at URAK.</p>	
	<p>4. Preparation of suggestions for amendment and complement of the Code of Ethics of the teachers and the employees of the University of regulations regarding ensuring equality between women and men in university activities and delegation of powers to Ethics committees in the university in this area. Accepting of the proposals.</p>	<p>Reflecting on the general university policies for equality between women and men. Reflecting the basic ethical requirements in the behavior of students, PhD students, academic staff, administrative and service staff, to ensure equality between women and men.</p>	<p>Term: 1.08.22 - 30.10.22</p>	<p>Secretary General</p>	<p>Conducted training.</p>	<p>Publicity. Accessibility of The Code of Ethics of the inside page of the university.</p>	<p>Lack of skills to develop such system.</p>	
	<p>5. Training of the members of the Ethics Committees on topics related to guaranteeing the equality between women and men.</p>	<p>Providing expert capacity on the questions about ensuring equality between men and women.</p>	<p>Deadline: 1.10.2022</p>	<p>Chairman of the Commission on academic ethics at the Academic Council.</p>	<p>Number of participants.</p>	<p>Application of the results of the training in activity of the committees. Disclosure of the rules and their practical application.</p>	<p>Time constrains, lack of interest from employees.</p>	

		6. Upgrading the system for the adaptation of young specialists when occupying an academic position and starting a job at the University, through the "Young Teacher" School reflected in the Internal Rules.	Supporting the overall development and improvement of the professional skills of young specialists according to the specifics of teaching, research and administrative activities.	Deadline: 31.12. 2022.	Chairman of the Commission on academic ethics at the Academic Council.	Adoption of internal rules for the adaptation of young specialists when occupying an academic position and starting a job at the University based on the current acts of the URAK.	Written information on the University website.	Not identified.
		7. Ensuring a better reconciliation of the professional and personal life of parents with young children and large families.	The activity is aimed at ensuring a better reconciliation of the professional and personal life of parents with small children and large families.	Term: annually during the period 1.01.- 31.03.	Vice Rector Career Development and Continuing Education.	Provision of information to parents with small children and large families regarding the possibilities for their stimulation according to national legislation.	Number of supported parents with small children and large families.	Not identified.
		8. Ensuring equal access when hiring women and men with permanent disabilities usual working and specialized work environment under the National Program for Employment of People with Disabilities, according to Art. 46 and Art. 49 of the Soviet Union and of equal access to their education.	Creating conditions for hiring, employment, education, and/or promotion of employability to people with permanent disabilities.	Term: permanent.	Head of the Academic Staff Development. Assistant Rector.	Building a work environment - access to workplace and administrative service, adaptation of the work environment for people with permanent physical disabilities.	Number of annually trained and employed women and men with permanent disabilities.	Not identified.

		9. Provision of opportunities for different forms of employment - hourly, in person, remote environment.	Achievement of balance between professional and personal life at the exercise of the rights and obligations of students, the doctoral students, the academic staff and the administrative staff.	Term: permanent.	Assistant Rector.	Advance and timely notification of applicable forms of employment.	Annual investment for working environment.	Not identified.
		10. Provision for academic and administrative staff of a conducive environment, about finding a balance between personal life and professional growth.	Achievement of balance between professional and personal life.	Term: permanent.	Rector's Guide. Branch Managers and faculties.	Realization of specializations, participation in research forums and other scientific events, financed if funds are available at URAK under national and international programs.	Publicity of the information of the inside page of the university.	Not identified.
		11. Provision of a system for informing the university management about the state of equality between men and women in the University.	Maintaining awareness of the University's leadership on the implementation of the equality plan in order to adopt impact measures.	Term: permanent.	Chairman of the University Ethics Committee. Rector's Guide. Academic Council.	Provision of annual information to the Rector's management on the implementation of the plan for equality between women and men.	Annual reference to the report of the main units and the report of the Rector's management on the activities of the university. Implementation of the equality plan.	Weak collaboration between different units collecting data.

2	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	1. Review and Amendment Proposals and complement of the Internal acts of University related to labor remuneration, the additional material incentive and the scholarships. Non-admission of differences based on gender upon receipt of remuneration from the University and the provision of scholarships.	Non-admission of differences based on gender upon receipt of remuneration from the University and the provision of scholarships.	Deadline: upon subsequent resigning of the Collective Labor Agreement.	Rector. Chairman of Trade Union organizations.	Updated internal acts of the University.	Publicity of the information on the internal page of the University and in the archive with the decisions of the Academic Council.	Not identified.	General Strategy for Area No. 2. Non-admission of gender differences in the payment of remuneration, additional material incentives and scholarships.
		2. Approval of the Collective Labor Agreement as an instrument for equal pay for women and men. Ensuring equality between women and men in receiving remuneration and other payments.	Ensuring equality between women and men in receiving remuneration and other payments.	Deadline: annually until 31.03.	Assistant Rector, Chief Accountant.	The inclusion of an express clause in the Collective Labor Agreement, not allowing inequality between women and men in the payment of remuneration.	Publicity of the information on the internal page of the university and in the archive with the decisions of the Academic Council.	Not identified.	
		3. Awareness of the academic staff and administrative staff regarding the level of pay for women and men for the University's activities. Publicity of the regulatory framework.	Publicity of the regulatory framework.	Term: permanent.	Rector's Guide. Branch Managers and Faculties.	Written information available.	Information on the number of women and men involved in decision-making to the annual documents for reporting the activities of the University.	Not identified.	

3	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	1. Guaranteeing equal opportunities for the participation of women and men in decision-making processes in the structures of the University.	Application of the principles of equality between women and men in decision-making.	Term: permanent.	Rector's Guide. Branch Managers and faculties.	Number of women and men involved in decision-making.	Information on the number of women and men involved in decision-making to the annual reports for reporting the activities of the University.	Not identified.	General Strategy for Area No. 3. Observing and promoting the equality of women and men in decision-making processes in the management bodies of RUAK (General Assembly, Academic Council, Rector, Student Council), as well as in the management bodies of the main units (Faculties, Branches, Departments) and service units (Administrative Directorates and Departments).
		2. Publicly announced and transparent criteria for election to governing bodies have been established, in compliance with the principle of equality between women and men.	Publicity of the regulatory framework.	Term: permanent.	Secretary General Chairman of the Central Commission for Election Preparation.	Provisions in the Regulations and other internal acts of the University guaranteeing equality between women and men.	Publicity of the information on the internal page of the University and in the archive with the decisions of the Academic Council.	Not identified.	

4	Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	1. Prevention against violence, as violation of human rights and form of discrimination gender based.	Provision of public information about the regulations regarding prohibitions on discrimination in fulfillment of Art. 22 and Art. 30 Protection from Discrimination Act.	Term: permanent.	President of the Student Council. Chairmen of trade union organizations.	A separate section on the University's website containing the main normative acts prohibiting discrimination.	Publicity of the information on the internal page of the university and in the archive with the decisions of the Academic Council.	Time constrains, lack of Interest.	General Strategy for Area No. 4. Combating violence and protecting and supporting victims.
		2. Meetings and public lectures with representatives of the Commission on Discrimination or the Judiciary on the issues of the prohibition of discrimination and the non-admission of violence.	Awareness of cold, academic staff and administrative staff.	Term: annually	Assistant Rector. Chairmen of the Student Council and trade union organizations.	Number of meetings held and participants.	Number of participants. Publicity of Disclosure of Meetings.	Time constrains, lack of interest.	
		3. Organization of a scientific conference at the University (Faculty of Law) on the issues of prohibition of discrimination and measures to combat violence.	Awareness of cold, academic staff and administrative staff.	Term: 1.01.23 - 31.12.23	Deputy rector for scientific research. Dean of the Faculty of Law.	Number of participants.	Publication of scientific results in a collective monograph	Not identified.	
		4. Taking effective measures to prevent all forms of discrimination in the workplace and at school by persons from the teaching or non-teaching staff or by students.	Guarantee of protection of the rights of persons in fulfillment of Art.17, Art. 29, para. 2 and Art. 31 of the Anti-Discrimination Act.	Deadline: 30.10.22.	Chairman of the Ethics Committee General Secretary. Dean of the Faculty of Law. Chairmen of the Student Council and trade union organizations.	Procedures developed in internal acts and normative documents of the University.	Publicity of the procedures.	Limited possibilities to implement certain actions based on the data.	

5	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	1. Promotion of measures for effective implementation of the policy on equality between women and men.	Implementation of a procedure for obtaining a Distinctive Badge for significant achievements in the effective implementation of the policy on equality between women and men.	Deadline: 1.01. 24 - 31.12.24.	Vice Rector Research. Assistant Rector. Presidents of the Student Council and Trade Union organizations.	Preparation of documentation for participation in the procedure.	Publicity of the procedure and its results.	Limited possibilities to implement certain actions based on the data.	General Strategy for Area No. 5. Overcoming gender stereotypes in various spheres of public life and sexism. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.
		2. Implementation of an information policy in the University system to raise the awareness of students, academic staff and administrative staff regarding the principle of equality between women and men.	Application of the principle of equality between men and women. Awareness of equal opportunities for men and women.	Term: permanent.	Rector. Assistant Rector. Presidents of the Student Council and Trade Union organizations. Public Relations and Advertising Department.	Application of the principle of equality of women and men when publishing informational materials on the University's website and when conducting public events.	Positizing trends in behavioral, social and visual models in the University regarding the equality of women and men.	Limited interest from the management of the institutions/ centers.	
		3. Providing a link to the rubric "Equal opportunities" maintained by the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy.	Promotion of the national policy on equality between women and men in national and international events.	Term: permanent.	Public Relations and Advertising Department.	Application of the principle of equality.	Link on the University website.	Limited interest from the management of the institutions/centres.	
		4. Organization of meetings - talks between students, academic staff and the representatives of the central and local authorities (coordinators for equality between women and men).	Combating discriminatory practices, familiarization with various practical hypotheses.	Term: annually.	Rector. Vice rectors. Assistant Rector. Chairmen of the Student Council and Trade Union organizations.	Raising the awareness of the University staff, by making them aware of the rights of individuals and which institutions to turn to for assistance.	Number of meetings held.	Time-constrains, lack of awareness of the policy.	

		<p>5. Organizing the presentation of information on the benefits to society and the economy of equality between women and men by representatives of the central or local government.</p>	<p>Awareness of the need to guarantee equal opportunities between women and men and its benefits for society.</p>	<p>Term: once every two years.</p>	<p>Public Relations and Advertising Department.</p>	<p>Raising the awareness of University staff about the social importance of equality between women and men.</p>	<p>Number of events held on the social and economic benefits of equality between women and men, and measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.</p>	<p>Not identified.</p>	
		<p>6. Holding talks with representatives of the central and local authorities to raise awareness of the new challenges that have an impact on the equality of women and men - new technologies, digital industries, artificial intelligence, transition to a green and digital economy, the need for new skills and new jobs, climate change, migration, threats to public health such as pandemics, possible conflicts disrupting peace and security, etc.</p>	<p>Raising the awareness of the academic, administrative and student staff about the importance of equality between women and men in the face of new societal challenges.</p>	<p>Deadline: 2023.</p>	<p>Public Relations and Advertising Department. Rector's Guide. Administrative guidance. Student Council. Trade Union organizations.</p>	<p>Raising the awareness of the academic, administrative and student staff of the University about the social significance of equality between women and men.</p>	<p>Number of events held and participants.</p>	<p>Time-constraints, lack of awareness of the policy.</p>	

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9.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

- Some of the described actions in the GEP of URAK include periodical monitoring and reporting of the implementation of the GEP. On annual base such reports will be produced as part of the sector under the umbrella of the Vice-rector in research.
- The monitoring methodology carried out for GEP evaluation and impact is based on the indicators in column “Impact assessment” in the previous section 5. Some of the indicators are periodical, while others a permanent. The responsible person for the implementation of this methodology and periodical monitoring, reporting and assessment is the Vice-rector in research.
- The GEP of URAK will be active four years. The periodical reports will facilitate the Academic Council of URAK to collect enough data during the first four years and prepare some improvements for the second four years.

9.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

- The GEP of URAK is published on the institution’s website. It has been approved by the Academic Council and disseminated by internal and external stakeholders.
- Every year URAK will organize workshops to keep the awareness for the GEP by trainings which to address the topics of unconscious bias and/or other specific topics.
- Thanks to these workshops the GEP will reach the whole institutional community.
- Thanks to the collaboration with the Bulgarian Ministry of Education the GEP of URAK will be disseminated to other Bulgarian universities and research organizations.

9.8 Annex

- Picture from 10 June 2022 when the GEP of URAK has been presented to the Bulgarian minister of education and regional stakeholders.

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Gender Equality Plan

Canary Islands Agency for Research,
Innovation and Information Society of the
regional government
(ACIISI - GOBCAN)

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10. ACIISI - GOBCAN Gender Equality Plan

10.1 Introduction

10.1.1 Presentation of the Gender Equality Plan and expression of the institution's commitment to gender equality.

The Canarian Agency for Research, Innovation and the Information Society (ACIISI), as established by Decree 9/2020 of 20 February (BOC n.º 44, 04.03.2020), approving the Organic Regulations of the Ministry of Economy, Knowledge and Employment, is the highest body, with the rank of Directorate-General, responsible for carrying out the competences related to public policies and programmes in the field of research, technological development, business innovation and the deployment of the information society of the information of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, as well as of the entities dependent on it and ensure administrative coordination in the matters assigned to it, in accordance with the guidelines agreed by the Coordination Commission of Science, Technology and Innovation, of the bodies and entities of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, and of these with the organs and entities of the other public administrations, national and international, for which purpose it will act as an interlocutor with said bodies and entities.

ACIISI has developed this business plan for equal treatment and opportunities between women and men, which will be valid for the period 2022-2026. This work has been carried out on a voluntary basis since the obligation established by the Ministry of Equality of the Government of Spain refers to companies with more than 50 workers and in the case of the ACIISI, although it is a management center belonging to the Government of the Canary Islands this challenge has been taken as a spearhead to promote the culture of equality within the framework of research funding organizations even though the number of workers in the management center is less than this figure. The elaboration of the same is framed in the participation of the ACIISI in the ATHENA project, financed in the call H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1 of the European Horizon 2020 programme to be developed between 2021 and 2025, whose objective is: to support the consortium partners, among which are 6 Research Organisations (PROs) and 2 Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), in the development and implementation of the Gender Equality Plans (PIG), as a way to generate systemic institutional changes.

The Equality Plan of The ACIISI has been designed taking as a reference the fulfillment of Royal Decree 901/2020 of October 13, which regulates equality plans and their registration and modifies Royal Decree 713/2010, of May 28, on registration and deposit of collective labor agreements and agreements and Royal Decree-Law 6/2019, of 1 March which established important clarifications regarding the content of the diagnosis and the equality plan listing the matters that should necessarily be dealt

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with in the diagnosis and the elements that the plan should contain, as well as a register in which all equality plans must be registered. This new framework arises to comply with the regulatory development mandate established in the new article 46.6 of Organic Law 3/2007 of March 22.

In addition, it takes as a reference royal decree 902/2020, of October 13, on equal pay between women and men.

This Equality Plan, in accordance with the provisions of Organic Law 3/2007 of March 22, for the effective equality of women and men, has as its main objective to guarantee real equality and effective opportunities between women and men within the Institution and avoid any type of employment discrimination between women and men. In order to give effect to the principle of equality, the specific objectives of equality to be achieved have been set.

10.1.2 Legal context and relevant national/regional regulatory framework.

The Spanish Constitution (1978) allows the adoption of mechanisms to correct inequality, even before the UN approved CEDAW (1979), a fundamental instrument to articulate an international legal framework for equality, since it requires States Parties not only not to discriminate, but also to modify the traditional role of men and women in society and in the family. In addition, it allows them to adopt positive action measures, of a temporary nature, aimed at accelerating equality between men and women (art. 4 CEDAW). Spain signed it in 1981.

With regard to secondary legislation, two Community rules have led Spain to adapt its legal framework: Directive 2002/73/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions; and Directive 2004/113/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment between men and women in access to goods and services.

Its obligatory nature in our national legal system led to the approval of Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the Effective Equality of Women and Men (LOIEMH). One of the main characteristics of this law is precisely the application of the principle of transversality and its projection in all policies at all levels and orders.

The need to give formal coverage to gender equality policies in Spain has been approached from a double perspective. The first refers to the legislation and legal regulations that develop them. The second concerns an entire administrative structure whose central axis is the promotion and encouragement of equality of both sexes, as well as the facilitation of the conditions for the effective participation of women in political, cultural, economic and social life.

Within the scope of the General State Administration, as well as in the Ministry of Health, Social Affairs and Equality, the State Secretariat for Social Services and

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Equality, the Government Delegation for Gender Violence and the Institute for Women and Equal Opportunities (IMIO) are included.

The purpose of the Commission, as an autonomous body, is to promote and foster conditions that make possible the social equality of both sexes, as well as the participation of women in political, cultural, economic and social life. Its functions include the prevention and elimination of all forms of discrimination against persons on the basis of birth, sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion, ideology, orientation, sexual identity, age, disability or any other personal or social condition or circumstance. Its activity is mainly developed through the signing of collaboration agreements with other organizations and public and private institutions in the cultural, educational, sports, economic and social fields. In addition, the Women's Institute for Equal Opportunities, through public calls for grants and subsidies, it finances activities and projects aimed at promoting equal opportunities between women and men, especially research on gender and knowledge and dissemination of the situation of women.

In Spain, since the end of the 1990s, plans/programs have been developed to promote gender equality at the central, regional and -to a certain extent- local level. The main objectives of these plans have been to address gender equality in the workplace, the empowerment of women and gender-based violence. Equality plans are the most widely used instruments to implement gender equality provisions and have been developed at the state, regional and local levels. The Equality Plans are, however, non-binding political instruments in which the government's roadmap to achieve gender equality is applied. Each department decides on the specific policy or action to be taken to increase gender equality in its respective field of competence. In March 2022, the III Strategic Plan for the Effective Equality of Women and Men 2022-2025 has just been approved. The Plan is structured around four lines of intervention. In the first place, Good Government, to move towards a more inclusive and democratic model of government; secondly, the Economy for life and the fair distribution of wealth, against the feminization of poverty and precariousness; thirdly, Lives free of sexist violence for women, with the aim of eradicating all forms of violence; and finally, a fourth axis that aims to ensure all women the effective exercise of their rights in all areas of life. The objective of the first axis is to ensure that all public policies have a gender perspective and, for example, guarantee that all public personnel are trained in this regard. The second axis concentrates 91% of the economic resources of the plan on measures for decent employment and the reduction of wage and pension gaps, as well as co-responsibility for care: "That there be schools for children from 0 to 3 years old and public conciliation policies such as the Corresponsables Plan, which allow women, who are the ones who mostly assume these care tasks, to free up their time to be able to exercise each and every one of their rights and not only be able to reconcile working life with family life, but also personal life. In the third block, to achieve lives free of sexist violence, the aim is to strengthen coordination and institutional response systems for early detection and comprehensive care for victims, both of violence by their partner or ex-partner and sexual violence, sexual exploitation and trafficking. The fourth axis includes various measures to respond to the realities and needs of women who, in addition to

inequality based on sex, are affected by inequalities caused by their sexual orientation, race, disability or origin.

Royal Decree-Law 6/2019 ("on urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in employment and occupation") included new measures to promote equality between men and women in the workplace (also included various provisions to progressively increase mandatory paternity leave to 16 weeks in 2021). In this sense, Royal Decrees 901/2020 (Gender Equality Plan) and 902/2020 (Gender Salary Information) entered into force on January 14, 2021, and April 14, 2021, respectively. Mainly, the new regulations extend the existing obligation to implement a gender equality plan in Spain to companies with 50 or more employees (previously 250 or more employees). Among other obligations, the aforementioned companies must prepare salary records that show the average salary levels broken down by gender; and said records must be made available to the workers' legal representatives for review. Employers should know that any difference between the average salary by gender of 25% or more must be justified. An equality plan aims to achieve equal treatment and opportunities between women and men at work, and to eliminate discrimination based on sex. To this end, the law establishes that in each plan the company must ensure that this equality is achieved in several areas: Selection and hiring process; Classification of jobs; Training; professional promotion; Working conditions, including an equal pay audit; Co-responsible exercise of the rights to personal, family and work life; and Compensation and Prevention of sexual and gender-based harassment.

The principles of equality legislation apply in the field of education and research. Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the Effective Equality of Women and Men (LOIEMH) establishes that public administrations must promote teaching and research on the meaning and scope of equality between women and men (art. 25) in the field of higher education. The State Research Agency (AEI), attached to the Ministry of Science and Technology (MCIN), is responsible for financing Spain's public funds for R&D&i, as well as the promotion of Science and technology in all study areas. In November 2018, this institution created the Strategic Group for Gender Equality to implement the gender perspective and promote gender equality. These are defined in the Guidelines for the development of the European Research Area (ERA) in Spain 2016-2020. In this context, the AEI develops its first diagnosis of gender equality at the beginning of 2019, and subsequently the I Gender Equality Action Plan 2021-2023 of the National Research Agency for activities financed with R&D+ is designed. I110 by the Strategic Group for Gender Equality. Along with the work and diagnoses carried out by the AEI on gender equality, this tool prioritizes work in three areas with seven objectives and includes thirteen parts. For more information about them, read the Action Plan.

Area 1. Structures and mechanisms for gender equality.

Goals:

- Improve the analysis, monitoring and dissemination of data separated by sex.

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- Strengthen and consolidate the structures of the AEI that implement gender equality measures in a sustainable manner, considering time.

Area 2. Awareness, training and organizational culture.

Goals:

- Improve the training of specialists in gender equality in the administration of the scientific-technological application process in the AEI.
- Promote greater integration of the gender perspective in the R&D projects presented in the application processes at the AEI.

Area 3. Evaluation and scientific monitoring.

Goals:

- Coordinate the proper application of gender equality criteria, established in the legal texts.
- Integrate the gender perspective systematically in scientific-technical evaluations and in the monitoring of aid.
- Identify all the possible factors that contribute to creating a gap between women and men in their success as Principal Investigators in a research project.

The implementation of the measures included in the I Action Plan for Gender Equality must be carried out by the Strategic Group for Gender Equality of the AEI, the Equality Unit and the Women and Science Unit of the MCIN, as well as the SUPERA111 project.

In Spain, since 2018, the Higher Council for Scientific Research (CSIC) awards the Gender Equality Accreditation Distinction to CSIC research institutions. The award aims to promote the gender perspective in all areas of the CSIC, as well as measures to eliminate gender barriers. The last call for the prize was awarded in 2022 to the Institute of Neurosciences, a mixed center of the Miguel Hernández University (UMH) of Elche and the Higher Council for Scientific Research, for eliminating the barriers that prevent equal employment between women and men.

On the other hand, the Ministry of Science and Innovation ensures the application of gender equality policies, following the regulations established in Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the effective equality of women and men, the Law of Science, Technology and Innovation and the National Strategy for Science and Technology and Innovation 2013-2020, focused on research and innovation. To carry out its work, several organizations have been created:

- Equality Unit, regulated by article 77 of Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, and article 3.2 of Royal Decree 259/2019, of April 12.

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- Unit of Women and Science, whose objective is to develop the Order PRE/525/2005, of March 7, and guarantee the access and presence of women in research centers.
- Women, Science and Innovation Observatory, is an interdisciplinary body responsible for measuring and advancing gender equality in research institutions, as well as promoting gender equality policies in the Spanish Science, Technology and Innovation System.

Together with these organizations, each research institution dependent on the Ministry of Science and Innovation has its own Equality Unit that oversees the application of gender policies. In Spain, the legal responsibility for promoting gender equality in research and in higher education institutions falls on the Observatory for Women, Science and Innovation, which is responsible for promoting gender equality in collaboration with institutions of relevant research and innovation, as well as with ten other ministries: Ministry of Defense; Vocational Education and Training; Presidency, Relations with the Courts and Democratic Memory; Labor and Social Economy; Inclusion, Social Security and Migrations; Territorial Policy and Public Function; Economy and Digital Transformation; Health; Gender Equality and Universities.

[Law 14/2011, of June 1, on Science, Technology and Innovation.](#)

DA 13- **Implementation of the gender perspective**

2. The Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and the State Plan for Scientific and Technical Research will promote the incorporation of the gender perspective as a transversal category in research and technology, so that its relevance is considered in all aspects of the process. , including the definition of scientific-technical research priorities, research problems, theoretical and explanatory frameworks, methods, data collection and interpretation, conclusions, applications and technological developments, and proposals for studies futures. They will also promote gender and women's studies, as well as specific measures to stimulate and give recognition to the presence of women in research teams.
4. Procedures for selecting and evaluating research staff at the service of public universities and Public Research Bodies of the General State Administration, and procedures for granting aid and subsidies by research funding agents, will establish mechanisms to eliminate gender bias that will include, whenever possible, the introduction of confidential evaluation processes.

[Spanish Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation 2021-2027.](#)

[Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan.](#) The Spanish plan is structured around four transversal axes that will structure the transformation of the economy as a whole and that are fully aligned with the strategic agendas of the EU, the 2030 Agenda and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals: the ecological transition, digital transformation, gender equality and social and territorial cohesion.

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These axes will guide the entire recovery process, inspiring the structural reforms and investments that are launched, with the ultimate goal of recovering growth, promoting the creation of companies and accelerating job creation.

Canary Islands CCAA Legislation

Since 2010, the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands has had the Canary Islands Institute for Equality (ICI), created by Law 1/1994, of January 13, whose predecessor was the Canary Islands Institute for Women. The involvement of the Government of the Canary Islands in the defense and promotion of real equality between women and men has provided the ICI with a wide range of functions and powers that go far beyond the mere coordination of actions, carrying out activities, advising o The promotion and promotion of 38 measures aimed at achieving equality policies. In this sense, the actions, functions and powers of the ICI include the monitoring of current legislation and its application, as well as the preparation of proposals for legislative reform aimed at eliminating the obstacles that hinder or prevent real and effective equality between the sexes. As a consultative and advisory body, it must be taken into account and has the capacity to make proposals in the procedures for drawing up general provisions promoted by the Government of the Canary Islands. Finally, its competence to develop protocols for the prevention and protection of victims of sexual harassment and harassment based on sex cannot be ignored.

In addition, in the Canary Islands there are two important laws whose main objectives are the promotion of equality between women and men and protection against gender violence: Law 1/2010, of February 26, Canary Islands on equality between women and men, and Law 16/2003, of April 8, on the Comprehensive Prevention and Protection of Women against Gender Violence, modified by Law 1/2017, of March 17, which incorporates the provisions contained in the Istanbul Convention and the resolutions of international organizations. In this way, it is intended to extend the scope of application to all forms of violence against women. In addition, the agreement of the Government of the Canary Islands of June 26, 2017, which establishes the guidelines on how to prepare and the basic contents to be included in gender impact reports in bills, regulatory provisions and plans approved by the Government of the Canary Islands.

In the area of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, the recent modification of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands, approved by Organic Law 1/2018, of November 5, introduces for the first time the rights of equality between women and men, collected as a principle governing in article 17. The principle of equality between women and men and non-discrimination is guaranteed, favoring the participation of all people in public life under conditions of equality, which was not part of the consolidated text of the Statute of Autonomy of 1982 New articles related to equality between women and men are incorporated, such as article 11. Right to equality and cooperation, and article 17. Right to gender equality.

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Therefore, the following are of particular relevance:

[Decree 15/2016, of March 11, of the President, which establishes the internal rules for the preparation and processing of the Government's regulatory initiatives and approves the guidelines on their form and structure \(BOC. No. 55, 03/21/2016\).](#)

Thirtieth. - *Non-sexist language.*

1. In the drafting of the draft and draft regulatory provisions, language will be used that avoids the use of discriminatory or androcentric forms, so that the terminology used is in harmony with the principle of equality of the sexes.
2. The use of the generic masculine will be avoided, for which purpose the following alternatives will be taken into account:
 - a) Use of generic or collective nouns to encompass both sexes.
 - b) Use of periphrasis.
 - c) Use of grammatical constructions in which the direct reference to the sex of the subject is omitted, as long as this is clear and does not create any type of ambiguity. Thus: - With the use of verbal structures with impersonal formulation.
- By using infinitives and gerunds.
 - d) In the case of nouns with a single determination for both sexes, in which the article assumes the function of determining the gender, different alternatives can be used: - Omit the article in certain contexts. - Use a pronoun. - Substitute a determiner without a gender mark.
 - e) Use of metonymic constructions, alluding to the position, profession, trade or degree in preference to the designation of the person who holds or holds them.
 - f) When the generic masculine is used, the use of explanatory appositions may also be resorted to, which clarify that in said case its use responds to its generic function.
 - g) When for legal reasons, legislative technique or style, it is not possible to use any of the previous lexical-semantic and morphosyntactic resources, the generic masculine will be used.
3. The duplication strategy will be avoided as far as possible, as well as double agreements regarding gender in articles, nouns and adjectives. However, when the use of splits is essential, the order of their use will be indistinct.
4. In no case should resort to the use of the bar in the drafting of normative texts.
5. In references to the positions of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community, the following criteria will be followed:

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- a) In the references to the proposals of the regulations and in the signatures of the same, the position will be cited in its corresponding feminine or masculine gender depending on the person who is performing it at that moment.
- b) In the text of the regulation, the designation will be made to the administrative body: Presidency, Vice-Presidency, Ministry, Vice-Ministry, General Technical Secretariat, General Secretariat, General Directorate, General Deputy Directorate, Territorial Directorate.
- c) In the designation of the highest body of the departments, duplication will be used, referring to the President, Vice President or Vice President and Counselor or Counselor.
- d) In the appointment of members of collegiate bodies, the use of metonymic constructions will be sought, avoiding at the same time that the article accompany the position or representation, for the purpose of not designating sex.

Processing of normative initiatives with the force of law and regulations: The initiative must contain a Report on the impact by reason of gender.

In terms of budget, each year an Order is approved by which rules are issued on the preparation and structure of the General Budgets of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands. (Latest Order: **Order of July 12, 2021, which establishes rules on the preparation and structure of the General Budgets of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands for the year 2022. (BOC, No. 146, DE 16/07/2021).**)

- ✓ Article 2- Processing: The autonomous public sector entities will prepare their budget proposals in accordance with the criteria and guidelines approved by the Government, taking into account the criterion of transversality of the principle of equal treatment between women and men, incorporating the gender approach of budgets (...)
- ✓ Article 9- Procedure and deadline for submitting other information. Section and program memories. It will be sent to the General Directorate of Planning and Budget:
The gender impact report by budget program of the department, in accordance with the guidelines and the model included in Annex 8. This report must be consistent with the objectives and actions set out in the reports of the programs, as well as reflect the necessary improvements, and be conveniently evaluated by means of indicators.
- ✓ As an example, the gender impact assessment report for the 2022 budget of program 463B is attached in Annex 1.

Legislation Canary Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society

- **Canarian Pact for Science**

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- **New Smart Specialization Strategy S4 (In preparation process)**
- **Entrepreneurial Digital Territory Canarias Strategy** - Guidelines to promote development through digital growth in the Canary Islands.

It is a transformative agenda in collaboration and consensus with broad sectors of Canarian society, and thereby reduce the gaps (social, territorial, generational and gender)

Values: Only by guaranteeing the full participation of women in society and in the digital economy, it will be possible to reduce the gaps and achieve gender equality.

Measures and objectives to be achieved in 2025 related to TRAINING:
Objective: that 80% of Canarians have basic digital skills and that half of them are women.

- **Canary Islands Digital Agenda 2025 (In preparation process):**

It seeks to reduce the existing digital gap in digital skills of the population and a Canarian society with greater basic digital skills - Digital inclusion of the least favored people and support for women.

Objectives of the Canarian entrepreneurial digital territory to which it responds:

- That 80% of citizens have basic digital skills and that half of them are women.
- Raise the percentage of the population with digital skills 7 points above the basic ones.
- Reduce the gap in digital skills of the young population, until reaching the same state average in 2025.

Performance Indicators:

- Digital gender gap (internet).
- Digital gender gap (regular use of the internet).
- Digital gender gap (online purchases).
- Digital skills of the population (no skills).

Some of the actions identified: Promote the participation of women through the management of courses, workshops, seminars and conferences.

Finally, recently communicated and not yet published: the Canarian Strategy for Equality Transition of the Government of the Canary Islands, promoted by the Vice-Ministry of Equality and Diversity, which was approved in the Government Agreement of 4/28/2022 published in the BOC - 2022/ 91, is a work plan for the promotion of equality in the islands through concrete data that allows the generation of accurate public equality policies. The objective is to provide the Canarian community with its own toolbox against inequality, based on our cultural, geographical and social particularities as an archipelago that allow us to advance in equality in an undoubted and concrete way. We are talking about profound changes that require sowing seeds of equality that have time to grow. The Canarian Strategy for Egalitarian Transition is

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projected for 16 years with the intention of generating the necessary structures, strengthening the path and establishing dynamics that will ultimately lead us to the Canary population developing habits of equality. During the first legislature, the structure of the strategy will be based on four basic pillars: Plan, train, implement and communicate (Canarian Strategy for Egalitarian Transition (gobiernodecanarias.org)).

10.2 Development process and GEP management

ACIISI has participated in the Athena project as a legal partner since its inception in February 2021. The development and implementation of an institutional equality plan is one of the commitments for the year 2022. As a preliminary step, in 2021 a process of diagnosis to identify the main current legislation, measures already existing in the entity and possible proposals for the improvement of the institutionalization of gender equality in the ACIISI. The study was carried out through an online questionnaire addressed to all ACIISI staff, as well as the organization of a focus group with the equality commission created for this purpose. With the results of the information collected, a report was prepared in December 2021 that was added to the reports made by other partner entities in the Athena report to deliver as a product of the program. At the beginning of 2022, the ACIISI equality commission was updated and the information regarding the indicators established in the Athena project and the detail of the equality actions that are currently being carried out by the entity through face-to-face meetings. With these data, the present proposal for an institutional equality plan was drawn up.

10.2.1 Description of the members of the institutions involved in the development of the GEP.

The people involved in the development of this Equality Plan have been, on the one hand, all the ACIISI staff who have provided diagnostic information, and mainly, on the other hand, the people who are members of the Equality Commission, who will also be in charge of monitoring and evaluating the Plan application:

- ✓ Antonio López, Head of ACIISI Area.
- ✓ Guzmán Palacios Arazuri, Head of the R&D Support Service.
- ✓ Patricia Oramas Gallar, Head of Section of the ACIISI Coordination Area.
- ✓ Javier Roo, Head of R&D&I Projects.
- ✓ Patricia Jiménez López, Senior Technician ACIISI.
- ✓ Guendolina Martín Díaz. Responsible for communication.
- ✓ Carmen Sánchez López. Head of Business.
- ✓ Carmen Alonso. Computer technique.
- ✓ Asunción Jiménez. General Director of Labor (GC).
- ✓ Teresa Barroso. General Sec. Technical TF.

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10.2.2 Description of the participatory techniques used (staff surveys, interviews, focus groups, debates, etc.).

The participatory methodology used has included online surveys, focus groups and discussion meetings.

In this context, monthly meetings of the working group dedicated to this work are being held since January 2022, to follow up on the equality plan that will be extended to all the Center's staff, as well as surveys of 26 the 44 people employed in the ACIISI, as a sample to be able to carry out the diagnosis phase and establish the objectives that are intended to be achieved aligned with the cases identified from them.

10.2.3 Persons or body responsible for the implementation of the GEP and resources that will be dedicated to its implementation (human, financial, etc.).

The people responsible for the implementation of the gender equality plan of the ACIISI are the members of the institutional equality commission and the person in charge of the allocation and monitoring of human and financial resources is the Head of the ACIISI Area.

- ✓ Antonio López, Head of ACIISI. Head of PIG
- ✓ Guzmán Palacios Arazuri, Head of the R&D Support Service.
- ✓ Patricia Oramas Gallar, Head of Section of the ACIISI Coordination Area.
- ✓ Javier Roo, Head of R&D&I Projects.
- ✓ Patricia Jiménez López, Senior Technician ACIISI.
- ✓ Guendolina Martín Díaz. Responsible for communication.
- ✓ Carmen Sanchez Lopez. Head of Business.
- ✓ Carmen Alonso. Computer technique.
- ✓ Asuncion Jimenez. General Director of Labor (GC).
- ✓ Teresa Barroso. General Sec. Technical TF.

10.2.4 Date of entry into force and term of application.

The effective date of the equality plan will be July 2022 until December 2026.

10.2.5 Summary of the contents and structure of the Plan.

The Equality Plan of the ACIISI as a financing entity for Research and Innovation Actions at the regional level, as well as a participant in R&D&I projects of the Horizon Europe program of the European Union, must comply with a series of principles of eligibility among which are the commitment to Gender Equality and the implementation of an institutional Equality Plan. In accordance with the foregoing, the ACIISI PIG is based on four mandatory aspects that have been established by the new Horizon Europe program and that emanate from the new strategy for Gender Equality 2020-2025 implemented by the COM Commission (2020) 152 end; and that

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were already specifically included in the communication of the Commission for the European Research Area COM (2012) 392 final:

- Be a public document: The GEP must be a formal document signed by senior management and disseminated within the institution. You must demonstrate a commitment to gender equality, set clear goals and detailed actions and steps to achieve them.
- Have dedicated resources: Resources for the design, implementation and monitoring of GEPs may include funding for specific positions, such as Equality Officers or Gender Equality Teams, as well as allocated working hours for academic staff, administrative and management.
- Include arrangements for data collection and monitoring: GEPs should be evidence-based and based on sex- or gender-disaggregated baseline data collected across all categories of staff. This data should inform the GEP goals and targets, indicators, and ongoing assessment of progress.
- Be supported by training and capacity building: Actions may include developing gender competencies and addressing unconscious gender bias among staff, leaders and decision-makers, setting up working groups dedicated to specific issues and raising awareness through workshops and communication activities.

In addition to these mandatory process-related requirements, the following 7 topic areas are recommended for content.

1. Reconciliation of work life, personal life and organizational culture.
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making.
3. Gender equality in hiring and career progression.
4. Integrate the gender dimension in research and teaching content.
5. Measures against gender violence, including sexual harassment.
6. Budgets with a gender perspective and budget gender impact.
7. Inclusive and non-sexist institutional communication.

10.3 Diagnosis

All actions planned by the ACIISI in terms of R&D&i contribute to the incorporation of more women to structure the Canarian R&D&i ecosystem. The measures already contemplated by the management center in the different thematic areas indicated already currently include, among others, the following:

10.3.1 Organizational culture, reconciliation of work and personal life

Diagnostic Information:

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There is a tradition of flexible organizational culture in the ACIISI both within the framework of the general conciliation policies of the Government of the Canary Islands and those of the management center itself.

Results of the questionnaire sent to ACIISI staff:

Gender biases are detected in unemployment in the scientific field related to being a woman and motherhood:

- 35% answered that obtaining a higher qualification in the scientific field is easier for a man than for a woman and 12% stated that they do not know.
- The aspect that the staff participating in the survey considers could have the most negative impact on their career is taking maternity/paternity/adoption leave.
- 40% answered that men make much more progress in research while women have young children, one participant commented that being a mother can influence the difficulty of achieving certain objectives in the scientific field and almost a third answered that they consider that time constraints related to family responsibilities is one of the obstacles to obtaining the highest qualifications in the scientific and academic fields.

On the other hand, regarding time availability, it seems that it exceeds the agreed working day according to the answers obtained:

- Almost 80% state that they work weekends and a third very often
- 65% who work more than 10 hours a day and more than 25% often
- More than 50% work during the holidays and a third very often
- 40% get home from work too tired to do the tasks they need several times a week and 13.33% several times a month.

Actions in progress:

The law of the basic statute of public servants is applied, some examples of measures are the following:

- Permits for the birth of a child or the death or serious illness of a relative up to the second degree of consanguinity or affinity.
- Permission for adoption, guardianship for the purpose of adoption, or fostering, both temporary and permanent.
- Permission for the birth of premature children or children who for any other reason must remain hospitalized after delivery.
- Nursing leave for a child under twelve months. They will be entitled to one hour of absence from work that they can divide into two fractions. This right may be replaced by a reduction in the normal working day by half an hour at the beginning

and at the end of the working day, or by one hour at the beginning or at the end of the working day.

- Permission for the direct care of someone under twelve years of age, an elderly person who requires special dedication, or a person with a disability who does not perform paid activity, will be entitled to a reduction in their weekly working hours.
- Leave due to gender violence against female officials. The lack of attendance of civil servants who are victims of gender-based violence will be considered justified.
- Flexibility of the fixed part of the schedule for reconciling work and family life and due to gender violence. In the cases of public employees who are in charge of elderly people, children under 12 years of age or people with disabilities, as well as those who are in direct charge of a family member with a serious illness up to the second degree of consanguinity or affinity, they may request make the fixed part of the schedule more flexible by one hour a day, and in any case must comply with their weekly shift. - Public employees who are victims of gender-based violence will have the right to a reduction in the working day, with a proportional reduction in remuneration, or the reorganization of working time, through the adaptation of the schedule.

10.3.2 Gender balance in leadership and decision making.

Diagnostic Information:

The Management Center and the ACIISI show a balanced scorecard (table a) in terms of the ratio of women and men with a tendency to favor the female gender.

Table 20. Updated dashboard of the Management Center

Management/Headquarters Positions	Women	Men	Total
Holder of the CECE	1	0	1
Person in charge of the General Technical Secretariat	1	0	1
Head of the ACIISI Directorate	0	1	0
Head of Area	0	1	1
Head of Service	3	3	6
Head of Section	5	4	9
Business Headquarters	9	2	11

In order to extract diagnostic information, surveys were issued to ACIISI staff with the aim of collecting subjective data related to the gender perspective. To carry out the pertinent assessments, the number of people who completed them is taken into consideration, this being 26, which represents 59% of the staff of this Managing Body.

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From this percentage and from their responses, it is identified that no relevant differentiation or gender gap is perceived, since 28% state that there is a preference for assigning administrative tasks to women and 17% that service roles are assigned to them, which finds its foundation in the fact that the % of the workforce are administrative/auxiliary/Head of Bureau and these are tasks of the RPT they occupy.

Regarding the questions related to the assignment of important tasks and roles, the attention received from the Senior Management and its feedback, as well as the representation of the Agency in public and private events, between 11% and 23% have the perception that there is a preference for men.

In the survey carried out on staff within the framework of the Athena project regarding the distribution of tasks and resources, some gender biases are detected:

Actions in progress:

- A Working Group for Equality of the General Technical Secretariat of the Ministry of Economy, Knowledge and Employment, to which the Management Center depends, has been set up.
- Advice and accompaniment process in the evaluation and preparation of gender impact reports of budget programs.
- Regarding its external work, the ACIISI carries out several initiatives that promote the leadership and visibility of women in research:
- Women for Africa Foundation Grant, for the training of women researchers in research centers in the Canary Islands, in accordance with the program called Science for Women, in line with its mission of contributing to the development of Africa through its women, with the objective to promote to Africa women's leadership in scientific research and technology transfer and to build the capacity of research centers in their home countries. The main objective is to enable African women researchers and scientists to meet the great challenges facing Africa through research in health, agriculture and food security, water, energy and climate change, as well as in mathematics and economic sciences. To achieve this ambitious objective, the Women for Africa Foundation collaborates with the Spanish Centers of Excellence, whose prestige is unanimously recognized throughout Spain and internationally, thus ensuring excellence in scientific research in various fields.
- The project is part of the “Ellas Investigan” program, which was born with the ambition of empowering African female researchers in the STEM areas (Science, Technology, Engineer and Mathematics), so that they can be protagonists of Africa's transition towards a society based on knowledge and guided by innovation. “Ellas Investigan” is an initiative of the Women for Africa Foundation to support advanced research by African scientists through 6-month postdoctoral stays at the Spanish Severo Ochoa centers of the CSIC and other associated centers of excellence throughout Spain.

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- **Pioneers in the development of the Science and Innovation Mini-Fairs in the Canary Islands and the “Women and Girls in Science” program.** With this event, the Canarian executive promotes the participation of the different agents of the R+D+i system in the archipelago, becoming a great space of knowledge to show science, as well as its advances and research. The 2022 Minifairs host different activities aimed at Women and Girls in Science, making different protagonists of Canarian science visible today. With them, the youth of the islands will be able to learn how their work influences in fields related to engineering, telecommunications, biology, marine technology or the health of the oceans, to try to reduce "the gender gap in the sectors of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) that has persisted for years throughout the world.

10.3.3 Gender equality in hiring and career progression

Diagnostic Information:

According to the 2022 gender analysis sheet and assessment of budget programs. 463B Research and innovative human capital prepared by the ACIISI, in the Canary Islands the total number of employed women does not reach 40% in 2019-2020.

Access to the public function and professional progression in the management centers of the Government of the Canary Islands, as is the case of the ACIISI, is based on selective processes regulated by the constitutional principles of equality, merit and capacity, which are articulated through public competition. and competitive. In this sense, the organizational structure of the ACIISI (Table b) is unbalanced in terms of the ratio of women and men, represented by 66% of women in the workforce and a greater female representation in all age ranges (Table c)

Table 21. Organizational structure of the Management Centre (ACIISI-GOBCAN)

Services/Departments	Women	Men	Total	%Women	%Men
Total, ACIISI	29	15	44	66%	34%
Coordination Area	7	4	11	64%	36%
Support to the Director	1	0	1	100%	0%
Research support service	4	4	8	50%	50%
Innovation service	6	0	6	100%	0%
Information society service	2	2	4	50%	50%
Media inspection	2	4	6	33%	67%
Administrative service and modernization	3	1	4	75%	25%
ATHENA Project	4	0	4	100%	0%

Table 22. Age structure of the management center staff (ACIISI-GOBCAN)

AGE	Women	Men	Total
25-34	1	0	1
35-44	4	2	6
45-54	8	7	15
55-64	13	8	21
65+	1	0	1

According to the questionnaire prepared within the framework of the Athena project and distributed at the end of 2021 among ACIISI staff (26 people responded):

- 5% of the people surveyed consider that there is a slight preference towards women when hiring and 21% respond that they do not know.
- When promoting, 5% consider that they actually prefer men and 26% respond that they do not know.
- Regarding salaries and bonuses, 10% affirm that they prefer men and 31% that they do not know.
- In the allocation of scholarships at the national level, 5% consider that women are preferred and 42% that they do not know, and at the international level, 5% that women are preferred and 52% that they do not know.
- There has always been a man in management when most of the staff are women.

A lack of information has been detected in the following aspects:

- Personnel dedicated to innovation, areas in which they carry out their activity and professional categories they occupy.
- Presence of women and men in scientific and outreach events by fields or themes.
- Personal speaker or facilitator of scientific and dissemination events by areas or themes.

In addition, the equality commission states that the numbers of men and women hired by other institutions or companies or in the subsidies that receive funds from the ACIISI are not known to know if there are discriminatory gaps or not. They could be obtained, including budgets with a gender perspective, disaggregated and with impact analysis and if there are gaps, see the possibilities of applying positive action measures regarding contracting, participation and beneficiaries.

Actions in progress:

In the following, criteria that favor the hiring of women are included in the regulatory bases of subsidies:

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• ***ORDER of July 14, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for the incorporation of innovative personnel into the productive fabric. (BOC No. 142 of 07/27/2016)***

Base 9.- Application evaluation criteria.

1. Applications will be evaluated by the competitive bidding procedure in accordance with the principles of publicity, transparency, objectivity, equal opportunities and non-discrimination.

Base 15.- Obligations of the beneficiary entities.

9. As it is an activity co-financed by the European Social Fund (ESF), the justification must comply with the provisions of the Order of November 10, 2009, which establishes rules for the management, monitoring and control of the operations co-financed with Structural Funds and in Community Regulations No. 1303/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, 2013 and No. 1304/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, 2013, regarding the European Social Fund, and in accordance with the instructions given by the Management Authority of the Canary Islands ESF Operational Program 2014-2020 regarding co-financed operations and compliance with the provisions, policies and actions must be guaranteed throughout the time the expenditure is made. community, including those corresponding to the rules of competition, public procurement, protection and improvement of the environment, elimination of inequalities and promotion of equality between men and women, as well as information and advertising. You must provide the data required for the performance indicators of the POC 2014-2020, for subsequent certification to the FSE.

• ***ORDER of July 7, 2020, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for the Catalina Ruiz postdoctoral research staff training program. (BOC No. 147 of 07/22/2020)***

Base 9.- Concession procedure.

1. The grant award procedure will be competitive, through public calls, in accordance with the principles of publicity, transparency, equal opportunities and non-discrimination based on sex or disability.

Base 19.- Requirements for researchers.

f) Not have been sanctioned criminally or administratively with the loss of the possibility of obtaining subsidies or public aid, or incurring in legal prohibition that disqualifies him for it, including those that have occurred due to discrimination based on sex in accordance with the provisions of the Sixth final provision of Law 4/2005, of February 18, for the Equality of Women and Men.

Base 23.- Justification of the subsidy.

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1. The justification of the subsidy will be carried out by means of a supporting account with an auditor's report, as established in article 27 of Decree 36/2009, of March 31, which establishes the general system of subsidies of the Autonomous Community of Canary Islands, and must be formalized through the contribution of:

a) Audit Report.

x. Compliance with applicable European, national and regional regulations, specifying each specific regulation (in terms of public procurement, subsidies, state aid, the environment, equal opportunities between men and women, information and communication and the eligibility of expenditure).

10.3.4 Integrate the gender dimension in research and teaching content.

Diagnostic information:

An analysis is not being carried out from the gender perspective of the contents of the research or materials that are being financed.

Actions in progress:

The ACIISI, as the management center in charge of carrying out the powers related to public policies and programs in matters of research, technological development, business innovation and deployment of the information society of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, develops different programs and financing actions that already integrate the gender dimension in their development, for example:

8.3.4.1 Hiring measures for external agents:

8.3.4.1.1. Assessment criteria in the award of contracts: A positive assessment criterion for gender equality is incorporated into the Administrative Clauses Documents (PCA).

As an example, the latest selection criteria used in the PCAs for contracting services related to the Digital Agenda and the new Smart Specialization Strategy (S4).

SCORE CRITERIA	SCORE CRITERIA
1. Proposed methodology for carrying out the works object of the contract	20
2. Proposed improvements	5
3. Participation of the different Economic and Social Agents and interest groups	10

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SCORE CRITERIA	SCORE CRITERIA
4. Delivery time reduction	20
5. Gender equality*	5

***The criterion 'Gender equality' is valued with up to 5 points the commitment to promote equality between men and women in the execution of this contract, and specifically in tasks that are not merely administrative.**

8.3.4.1.2. In the execution of the contract:

In the PCA it is established for the execution of the contract, in accordance with art. 202 of Law 9/2017, of November 8, on Public Sector Contracts- Special conditions for the execution of the contract of a social, ethical, environmental or other nature: "The contractor must meet the following conditions":

- *Eliminate inequalities between men and women in said market, favoring the application of measures that promote equality between women and men at work.*
- *Promote the greater participation of women in the labor market and the conciliation of work and family life.*

8.3.4.1.3. In the justification or evaluation of compliance with the contract: To date, no measures had been established.

8.3.4.2. Measures implemented in the Grants granted by the ACISII:

By way of example, different actions are set out that include the gender dimension in their regulatory bases and/or assessment criteria.

8.3.4.2.1. Actions that integrate the dimension of gender equality in their regulatory bases:

- **ORDER of November 9, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases that must govern the granting of subsidies, under the de minimis regime, for participation in the CIDE Network. (BOC No. 226 of 11/22/2016)**

Base 19.- Obligations of the beneficiaries.

12. As it is an activity co-financed by the European Development Fund, Community Regulations No. 1303/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, 2013 and No. 1301/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, December 2013, regarding the European Regional Development Fund, the rules on eligible expenses of the operational programs of the European Regional Development Fund and the Cohesion Fund, the rules for the

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management, monitoring and control of operations co-financed with Funds Structural and in accordance with the instructions given by the Management Authority of the ERDF Canary Islands 2014-2020 Operational Program regarding co-financed operations, it must guarantee compliance, throughout the time the expenditure is made, with the provisions, policies and community actions, including the corresponding to the rules of competition, public procurement, protection and improvement of the environment, elimination of inequalities and promotion of equality between men and women, as well as information and advertising.

16. Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of the subsidized project.

• **ORDER of December 2, 2016, which approves the bases that will govern the calls for grants of the Predoctoral Research Staff Training Program, co-financed with the European Social Fund. (BOC No. 240 of 12/14/2016)**

Base 26.- Applicant requirements.

d) It undertakes to comply with the Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the effective equality of women and men, and Law 1/2010, of February 26, Canaria of Equality between Women and Men, and is not serving an administrative or criminal sanction for incurring discrimination based on sex, or for encouraging or tolerating labor practices considered discriminatory by current legislation.

Base 28.- Obligations of the affiliated centers in their capacity as collaborating entities and of the companies in which doctoral theses are developed.

28.1. The following are obligations of the affiliated center, without prejudice to those derived from the employment relationship established with the beneficiary:

h) Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of projects.

28.2. The following are obligations of the companies in which doctoral theses are developed:

d) Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of projects.

Base 31.- Rights and duties of the beneficiary research staff.

31.2. Duties of the beneficiary research staff:

j) Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of projects.

Base 41.- Obligations of the affiliated centers in their capacity as collaborating entities.

The following are obligations of the affiliation center:

c) Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of projects.

8.3.4.2.2. Actions that integrate the gender dimension in their bases and assessment criteria.

• **ORDER of November 9, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases that must govern the granting of subsidies, under the de minimis regime, for participation in the CIDE Network. (BOC No. 226 of 11/22/2016)**

Base 13.- Assessment criteria and scales.

d) Number of newly hired people, particularly women or people with disabilities or in a situation of social exclusion (up to 15 points).

Criterion	1	2	More t 3
d	5	10	15

Base 19.- Obligations of the beneficiaries.

12. As it is an activity co-financed by the European Development Fund, Community Regulations No. 1303/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, 2013 and No. 1301/2013, of the European Parliament and of the Council, of December 17, December 2013, regarding the European Regional Development Fund, the rules on eligible expenses of the operational programs of the European Regional Development Fund and the Cohesion Fund, the rules for the management, monitoring and control of operations co-financed with Funds Structural and in accordance with the instructions given by the Management Authority of the ERDF Canary Islands 2014-2020 Operational Program regarding co-financed operations, it must guarantee compliance, throughout the time the expenditure is made, with the provisions, policies and community actions, including the corresponding to the rules of competition, public procurement, protection and improvement of the environment, elimination of disabilities and promotion of equality between men and women, as well as information and advertising.

16. Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of the subsidized project.

• **ORDER of August 12, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for carrying out R&D Projects by research organizations and companies in the priority areas of the Smart Specialization Strategy of the Canary Islands.**

Base 14. Concession procedure and electronic processing.

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1. The procedure for granting subsidies will be that of competitive competition, provided for in articles 14 to 20 of Decree 36/2009, of March 31, which establishes the general system of subsidies of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, in accordance with the principles of publicity, transparency, objectivity, equality and non-discrimination.

Base 16. Minimum content of the application and mandatory documentation.

4. Next, the legal representative of the requesting entity, prior to the electronic signature and registration of the request, must:

b) Declare responsibly that the requesting entity he represents:

It undertakes to comply with the Organic Law 3/2007, of March 22, for the effective equality of women and men, and Law 1/2010, of February 26, Canaria of Equality between Women and Men, and is not complying sanction administrative or criminal for incurring discrimination based on sex, or for encouraging or tolerating labor practices considered discriminatory by current legislation.

Base 18. Application evaluation criteria.

3. In the second phase of evaluation and for the cases in which it proceeds in accordance with the procedure established in rule 19, the following assessment criteria and additional points will be met:

Criteria Score	Score
Projects in which neither gender is represented by less than 40% of the total number of members of the research team	0,2
Projects in which the principal investigator is a woman	0,2
Projects in which the research group includes at least one member with a percentage of disability equal to or greater than 33%.	0,2

Base 19. Evaluation and selection procedure.

3. The Selection Commission will be chaired by the director of the Canarian Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society or a person delegated by him and will be made up of four members and a secretary, appointed by the director from civil servant, labor or statutory staff. at the service of the public sector, unless their affiliated entity has submitted an application in the respective call. In its composition, equal representation of men and women will be sought.

Base 25. Obligations of the beneficiaries.

Grant recipients are subject to the following obligations

13. Measures must be adopted to promote equality between men and women, as well as to avoid any discrimination based on sex, race or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation. Ensure a non-sexist use of language and ensure that an egalitarian, plural and non-stereotyped image of women and men is transmitted in the execution of the subsidized project

Likewise, the principle of sustainable development and promotion of the conservation, protection and improvement of the quality of the environment will be respected in accordance with articles 7 and 8 of Regulation (EU) No. 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council, of 17 December 2013

3.4.2.3. In monitoring the execution of subsidies:

Indicators disaggregated by sex have been implemented in different grants/aid granted, for this:

- A field for the applicant disaggregated by sex is included in the grant application form.
- A dashboard is created, with all the data collected disaggregated by sex in the application for all grants.

The results extracted for monitoring are summarized in the following table of indicators:

PERFORMANCE NAME AWARDED		Women	Men	% WOMEN	% MEN
INCORPORATION OF INNOVATIVE PERSONNEL (IPI 2020-2022)	40	18	22	45.0	55.00
INCORPORATION OF INNOVATIVE PERSONNEL (IPI 2021-2023)	26	15	11	57.6	42.3
CATALINA RUIZ INNOVATIVE STAFF TRAINING 2021	10	6	4	60.0	40.0
TRAINING OF INNOVATIVE PERSONNEL CATALINA RUIZ 2022	14	5	9	35.7	64.29
CIDE NETWORK 2020-2022	23	15	8	65.2	34.78
CIDE DIGITAL NETWORK 2021	16	9	7	56.2	43.75
PREDCTORAL PROGRAM FOR THE TRAINING OF INNOVATIVE PERSONNEL (THESIS 2021)	62	39	23	62.9	37.10
PREDCTORAL PROGRAM FOR INNOVATIVE PERSONNEL TRAINING (THESIS 2022)	60	38	22	63.33	36.67
INNOVATION MANAGERS 2020-2021 UNIVERSITY OF LAS PALMAS FOUNDATION 518 291 227 56.18 43.82	518	291	227	56.18	43.82
INNOVATION MANAGERS 2020-2021 LA LAGUNA UNIVERSITY FOUNDATION	499	293	206	58.72	41.28

NAME OF THE ACTION AWARDED	PROJECTS RESEARCH	PERSONNEL	Women	Men	%WOMEN	% MEN
R&D&I PROJECTS BY RESEARCH ORGANIZATIONS AND COMPANIES IN THE PRIORITY AREAS OF THE CANARY ISLANDS INTELLIGENT SPECIALIZATION STRATEGY RIS-3 (SUPPORT FOR RESEARCH MARIA DEL CARMEN BETENCOURT Y MOLINA). CO-FINANCING BY THE OPERATIONAL PROGRAM FEDER CANARIAS 2014-2020:	58	254	88	166	34.65	65.35
R&D&I PROJECTS BY RESEARCH	46	186	67	119	36.02	63.98

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ORGANIZATIONS AND COMPANIES IN THE PRIORITY AREAS OF THE CANARY ISLANDS INTELLIGENT SPECIALIZATION STRATEGY RIS-3 (SUPPORT FOR RESEARCH MARIA DEL CARMEN BETENCOURT Y MOLINA). CO-FINANCING BY THE OPERATIONAL PROGRAM FEDER CANARIAS 2014-2020:						
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In summary, it can be seen that of the 12 financing actions whose gender dimension has been analyzed, 7 exceed parity in favor of women, which identifies more than 58% of the financing actions as positive from a gender perspective. requiring the same attention in the programming of the remaining 42%.

10.3.5 Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

Diagnostic information:

The Government of the Canary Islands has a protocol for action in situations of harassment and violence in the work environment of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands that includes all its manifestations. The Protocol was approved by Resolution of May 8, 2019 (BOC No. 102 of May 29, 2019). This protocol includes a Section with particularities related to moral, labor or psychological harassment; sexual, for reasons of sex, sexual orientation or identity and for any other discriminatory circumstance, as a formal manifestation of the political commitment to zero tolerance with respect to situations or manifestations of harassment and a guarantee that said zero tolerance policy is recognized by all Departments and Public Organizations of the Autonomous Administration, serving as a general instrument of action against all types of harassment that could occur in any of its work centers, its objective being to establish preventive measures that avoid it, formal and informal procedures that help resolve it in the event that it occurs and guidelines for the recovery of the personal and professional life project of the people who suffer from it.

In this way, the aforementioned regulatory framework recognizes and declares the need to prevent harassment behavior at work, to make it impossible for it to appear and to eradicate any behavior that may be considered constitutive of it in the field of public administration, stating as basic principle of action the right of public employees to receive respectful and dignified treatment in the performance of their duties.

In this context, training has begun at ACIISI since June 2022.

In This Management Center, the actions regarding harassment that the participants in the Athena survey at the end of 2021 (15 answers to these questions, having been surveyed 26 of the 44 people employed in the ACIISI) stated that they have occurred on some occasion , are the following:

- Inappropriate comments regarding appearance or clothing (3)
- Inappropriate comments about skills and competencies (5)
- Inappropriate and unfair criticism (8)

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- Humiliation and degradation (6)
- Calls, emails, text messages, photos or videos with sexual subtitles (1)
- Verbal, non-verbal, psychological threats or physical abuse (1)

Given the existence of these perceptions by an approximate average of 9% of the Center's staff, an action plan is established to address them.

Actions in progress:

Measures are in place to support victims of gender violence through social clauses in hiring.

There is a protocol against workplace harassment that includes sexual or gender-based harassment in the Government of the Canary Islands in force.

10.3.6 Budgets with a gender approach:

Diagnostic information:

The analysis of gender impact in the budgets is mandatory and is not being carried out in the ACIISI.

According to the 2022 gender analysis sheet and assessment of budget programs. 463B Research and innovative human capital prepared by the ACIISI:

- There is difficulty in assessing inequalities since reliable data is not available on some aspects such as the presence of men and women in decision-making positions, both in research policy and in companies or entities linked to the activities R&D.

Actions in progress:

Participation in the Working Group on Gender Equality in R&D&I Funds, held by the R&D&I Policy Network of the Ministry of Science and Innovation, the Ministry of Finance and the Autonomous Communities.

Gender reports in annual budgets (See Annex 1)

10.3.7 Institutional communication.

Diagnostic information:

Not all staff know the existing instruments in the entity: manual and advisory service. Inclusive and non-sexist communication reviews are being carried out on most documents. The calls and bases of subsidies, everything that is published in the

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Official Gazette of the Canary Islands is reviewed by the legal service to guarantee that they have inclusive language.

With a view to promoting it in the financed institutions, it is included in some of the instruments described above that integrate the gender dimension in their bases and assessment criteria.

- ORDER of November 9, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases that must govern the granting of subsidies, under the de minimis regime, for participation in the CIDE Network. (BOC No. 226 of 11/22/2016)
- ORDER of December 2, 2016, which approves the bases that will govern the calls for grants of the Predoctoral Research Staff Training Program, co-financed with the European Social Fund. (BOC No. 240 of 12/14/2016)
- ORDER of November 9, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases that must govern the granting of subsidies, under the de minimis regime, for participation in the CIDE Network. (BOC No. 226 of 11/22/2016)
- ORDER of August 12, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for carrying out R&D Projects by research organizations and companies in the priority areas of the Smart Specialization Strategy of the Canary Islands.

Actions in progress:

Institutional communication: Inclusive language and images in ACIISI communication, existence of a GOBCAN manual, contact telephone number.
<https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/el-personal-del-gobierno-cuenta-con-un-nuevo-espacio-de-consulta-y-recursos-audiovisuales-para-comunicar-en-igualdad/>.

Some examples of the legality reports of the General Technical Secretariat of our Ministry, correcting the language in the drafting of the Order proposals:

- The expression "self-employed and entrepreneurs" should be replaced by "self-employed and entrepreneurs", in response to the thirtieth guideline on the non-sexist use of language, approved by the aforementioned Decree 15/2016, of the President, of March 11.
- The expressions "beneficiaries" and "beneficiary" must be replaced by "beneficiary entities" and "beneficiary entity", respectively, in accordance with the aforementioned guideline on the non-sexist use of language.
- The expression "auditor" and "auditors" should be replaced by "auditor person" and "auditor persons", respectively, in accordance with the aforementioned guideline on the non-sexist use of language.

Incorporation of the Name of Relevant Scientific Women in the actions financed by the ACIISI:

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Support for R&D&i activity. María del Carmen Betencourt y Molina Program: Calls for R&D grants under a competitive concurrence system, by carrying out R&D projects that generate scientific and technical knowledge of excellence in the priority areas for the Canary Islands, which involve qualitative advances and significant in the scientific field and that achieve in the medium and long term to improve the national and international impact of Canarian institutions, centers, research groups and researchers, channel resources towards essential sectors for the Canary Islands and ultimately strengthen the capacity of the Canarian system of science, technology and innovation. These are activities aimed at R&D projects in the areas identified as priorities in the RIS3 of the Canary Islands for research groups and public research centers that lead to the incorporation of new researchers, the programming and joint execution of activities, the use of electronic communication networks and the joint management of knowledge and intellectual property.

10.4 Objectives

This section defines the main objectives, as well as the main results of the quantitative and qualitative analysis regarding gender equality in the institution carried out: the main gender biases identified and the main interventions and priority areas identified in the diagnosis.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE:

Guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in the areas of intervention of the ACIISI through specific measures aimed at preventing, identifying and eliminating gender gaps, if any.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES LINKED TO DIAGNOSTIC INFORMATION AND ACTIONS:

This bill that is being drafted is linked to the fulfillment of all the objectives listed below.

New Canarian Science Law (In process, it will repeal the Canarian Law 5/2001, of July 9, on the promotion and development of scientific research and innovation). As a novelty, this law pays maximum attention to the transversality of equality between men and women and the gender perspective within the framework of the Canarian System of Science, Technology and Innovation. The new specific articles to achieve effective equality are:

- It will establish the obligation to collect and monitor data disaggregated by sex, including specific indicators for measuring the gender impact of strategies, plans, programs, calls and projects that are financed by public funds.

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- Accountability for the specific measures adopted by all SCIDI agents to advance equality between men and women in the field of R&D&i within the SCIDI governance bodies.
- Inclusion of transformative measures that favor gender equality, such as the obligation to have equality plans by public agents of the SCIDI.
- Obligation to establish elements that positively discriminate the participation of women, as well as the inclusion of vulnerable groups, in calls for funding with public funds for R&D&i.

Table 23. Diagnostic and actions for each specific objective - ACIISI-GOBCAN GEP

Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
<p>1. Organizational culture and reconciliation of personal and work life.</p> <p>Maintain an organizational culture that allows the effective reconciliation of personal and work life for the entire ACIISI staff through support for self-care and care responsibilities towards minors and other dependents.</p>	<p>Here is a tradition of flexible organizational culture in the ACIISI both within the framework of the general conciliation policies of the Government of the Canary Islands and those of the management center itself and the following laws are complied with:</p> <p>Law 2/1987 of March 30, on the Canary Islands Public Service (BOC No. 40 of April 3, 1987).</p> <p>Royal Legislative Decree 5/2015, of October 30, approving the Consolidated Text of the Law on the Basic Statute of Public Employees (BOE No. 261 of October 31, 2015), modified by Royal Legislative Decree 7 /2019, of March 1, on urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in employment and occupation.</p> <p>Gender biases are detected in unemployment in the scientific field related to being a woman and motherhood:</p> <p>Regarding time availability, it seems that it exceeds the agreed day according to the answers obtained.</p>	<p>1.1. Continue support for care responsibilities (care for children and other dependents) and parental leave policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permits for the birth of a child or the death or serious illness of a relative up to the second degree of consanguinity or affinity. - Permit for adoption, for guardianship for the purpose of adoption, or fostering, both temporary and permanent. - Permission for the birth of premature children or those who for any other reason must remain hospitalized after delivery. - Nursing leave for a child under twelve months. They will be entitled to one hour of absence from work that they can divide into two fractions. This right may be replaced by a reduction in the normal working day by half an hour at the beginning and at the end of the working day, or by one hour at the beginning or at the end of the working day. - Permission for the direct care of someone under twelve years of age, an elderly person who requires special dedication, or a person with a disability who does not perform paid activity, will have the right to reduce their weekly working hours. - Leave due to gender-based violence against female officials. The lack of attendance of civil servants who are victims of gender-based violence will be considered justified.

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
		<p>1.2. Maintain flexibility in working hours in accordance with the provisions of the Canarian Civil Service Act:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Variable schedule: the variable part of the schedule will cover the time of the day not fulfilled in the fixed part, and may be fulfilled between 7:00 and 9:00 a.m. and between 2:00 p.m. and 5:00 p.m. During the summer period and other dispensations, the fixed part will be twenty hours per week, at a rate of four hours per day, between 9:00 a.m. and 1:00 p.m. and the flexible part between 7:00 a.m. and 9:00 a.m. and between 1:00 p.m. and 4:00 p.m.- Flexibility of the fixed part of the schedule for reconciling work and family life and for reasons of gender violence. In the cases of public employees who are in charge of elderly people, children under 12 years of age or people with disabilities, as well as those who are in direct charge of a family member with a serious illness up to the second degree of consanguinity or affinity, they may request make the fixed part of the schedule more flexible by one hour a day, and in any case must comply with their weekly shift.- Public employees who are victims of gender-based violence will have the right to a reduction in the working day, with a proportional reduction in remuneration, or the reorganization of working time, through the adaptation of the schedule.

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
		<p>1.3. Reintegration of workers after career interruptions.</p> <p>Labor personnel (Royal Legislative Decree 2/2015, of October 23, approving the Consolidated Text of the Workers' Statute):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Forced leave of absence: The worker has the right to reserve the job.2. Voluntary leave of absence: There is a preferential right to reinstatement in vacancies of the same or similar category for the worker who was on voluntary leave of absence.3. Leave of absence to care for children or family members: During the first year, the worker will have the right to reserve the job. <p>Civil servant personnel (EBEP and LFPC): Re-entry into active duty for civil servants who are in a situation of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Forced leave of absence.2. Voluntary leave:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Public officials when they are in a situation of active service in another body or scale of any of the Public Administrations, or begin to provide services in organizations or entities of the public sector.b. Officials who cease in the situation of special services.c. Officials who are on leave to attend to the care of a child,

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
		<p>counting from the date of the child's birth.</p> <p>1.4. Support and advice on Reconciliation of Work Life and Organizational Culture. Development of training activities promoted by the work center aimed at all staff based on information on existing rights, positive aspects and areas for improvement, as well as possible unconscious biases that may influence the institutional culture regarding this axis.</p>
<p>2. Gender balance in leadership and decision making.</p> <p>Establish the appropriate measures so that there is equality between women and men in leadership and decision-making (participation, representation, training and recognition) in conditions of</p>	<p>The Management Centre and the ACIISI show a balanced staffing table (table a) in terms of the ratio of women and men with a tendency to favour the female gender.</p> <p>A working group for equality has been set up in the General Technical Secretariat of the Regional Ministry of Economy, Knowledge and Employment to which the Management Centre is attached.</p> <p>In terms of its external work, the ACIISI carries out several initiatives that promote the leadership and visibility of women in research:</p> <p>Women for Africa Foundation Grant. The project is part of the "Ellas Investigan" programme.</p> <p>Pioneers in the development of the Miniferias de la Ciencia y la Innovación in the Canary Islands and the "Women and Girls in Science" programme.</p>	<p>2.1. Try to attend to the principle of balanced presence of women and men in the appointments and designations of the positions of the management team of the management center. Incorporate training and experience in gender equality among the selection criteria.</p> <p>2.2. Joint contracting tables: representatives of the ACIISI will have a joint participation in the contracting tables and other selection and evaluation commissions of the lines developed by the programs.</p> <p>2.3. Analysis of the possible conscious or unconscious barriers that exist in the selection, promotion or hiring to ensure the representation of women in leadership and decision-making positions: structural, institutional and individual through the development of training activities aimed at responsible personnel.</p> <p>2.4. Stimulate and give recognition to the presence of women in research and innovation teams and promote the development of content in research and technology created by women, incorporating evaluation phases that grant an</p>

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
<p>equity, preventing, identifying and eliminating, if any, existing gender gaps.</p>	<p>Translated with www.DeepL.com/Translator (free version)</p>	<p>additional score of 0.2 points to those projects led by women, as well as those others, in which the representation of each of the sexes in the work team is not less than 40% of the total number of members.</p> <p>2.5. Continue granting grants for the training of women researchers in research centers in the Canary Islands, such as the Women for Africa Foundation.</p>
<p>3. Gender equality in hiring and career progression.</p> <p>Implement the necessary measures to prevent and act, if any, against discrimination based on sex in hiring and professional promotion, guaranteeing gender equality.</p>	<p>In the Canary Islands, the total number of employed women does not reach 40% in 2019-2020.</p> <p>The organizational structure of the ACIISI (Table b) is unbalanced in terms of the ratio of women and men, represented by 66% of women in the workforce and a greater representation of women in all age ranges (Table c). On the other hand, there has always been a man in management when most of the staff are women.</p> <p>In the following orders, criteria that favor the hiring of women are included in the regulatory bases of subsidies:</p> <p>ORDER of July 14, 2016, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for the incorporation of innovative personnel into the productive fabric. (BOC No. 142 of 07/27/2016). Base 9.- Application evaluation criteria and Base 15.- Obligations of the beneficiary entities.</p> <p>ORDER of July 7, 2020, which approves the regulatory bases for the granting of subsidies for the Catalina Ruiz postdoctoral research staff training program. (BOC No. 147</p>	<p>3.1. Include in the call application forms a specific field to collect whether the company or institution has an equality plan and a declaration of responsibility in the case of companies with more than 50 workers required by law.</p> <p>3.2. Include in the external audits aimed at the institutions that receive funds that they have to comply with the current legislation on equality and accredit it: depending on whether more than 50 workers is a voluntary or mandatory equality plan and remuneration record disaggregated by sex.</p> <p>3.3. Continue collecting and analyzing disaggregated data on men and women hired by financed institutions and companies to identify possible gender gaps e.g. Recruitment of doctors.</p> <p>3.4. Continue to include in the regulatory bases of subsidies and all calls for funding with public funds for R&D&i, criteria that favor the hiring of women through positive discrimination measures: eg. CIDE DIGITAL (number of newly hired people, particularly women (up to 15 points).</p>

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
	<p>of 07/22/2020). Base 9.- Concession procedure, Base 19.- Researcher requirements, Base 23.- Subsidy justification.</p> <p>The staff surveyed stated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 5% consider that there is a slight preference towards women when hiring and 21% who do not know.- When promoting, 5% consider that men are actually preferred and 26% do not know.- Regarding salaries and bonuses, 10% affirm that they prefer men and 31% that they do not know.- In the allocation of scholarships at the national level, 5% consider that women are preferred and 42% that they do not know, and at the international level, 5% that women are preferred and 52% that they do not know. <p>The number of men and women hired by other institutions or companies within the framework of the contracts or grants of funds granted by the ACIISI are not known to know if there are discriminatory gaps or not.</p> <p>In addition, a lack of information has been detected in the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Personnel dedicated to innovation, areas in which they carry out their activity and professional categories they occupy.- Presence of women and men in scientific and outreach	

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
	<p>events by fields or themes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personal speaker or facilitator of scientific and dissemination events by areas or themes. 	
<p>4. Integrate the gender dimension in research and teaching content.</p> <p>Include the gender perspective in research actions, educational and communicative content, identifying and eliminating all sexist biases and stereotypes, if any</p>	<p>An analysis is not being carried out from the gender perspective of the contents of the research or materials that are being financed.</p> <p>The ACIISI develops different financing programs and actions that already integrate the gender dimension in their development, for example:</p> <p>Hiring measures for external agents:</p> <p>Assessment criteria in the award of contracts: A positive assessment criterion for gender equality is incorporated in the Administrative Clauses (PCA), for example, the last selection criteria used in the PCA for contracting related services with the Digital Agenda and the new Smart Specialization Strategy (S4).</p> <p>In the execution of the contract: The PCA establishes special conditions for the execution of the contract of a social, ethical, environmental nature and includes gender equality.</p> <p>In the justification or evaluation of compliance with the contract: To date, no measures had been established.</p>	<p>4.1. Guarantee the dimension of gender equality in the contents of all R&D projects that are supported.</p> <p>Include in the funding application forms a section where the gender perspective of the content of the research and the differentiated expected impact are collected. The promotion and dissemination of research includes the gender dimension and define the monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.</p> <p>4.2. Guarantee gender equality in the award of public contracts.</p> <p>Continue with the incorporation in the Administrative Clauses of an assessment criterion for gender equality in the award of contracts: assessment of the gender equality criterion with up to 5 points the commitment to promote equality between men and women in the execution of the this contract, and specifically in tasks that are not of a merely administrative nature. In addition, it is established in accordance with art. 202 of Law 9/2017, of November 8, on Public Sector Contracts- Special conditions for execution of the contract of a social, ethical, environmental or other nature: "The contractor must meet the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eliminate the inequalities between men and women in said market, favoring the application of measures that promote

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
	<p>Measures implemented in the Grants granted by the ACISII.</p> <p>-In the selection: different actions that include the gender dimension in their regulatory bases and/or assessment criteria.</p>	<p>equality between women and men at work. - Promote the greater participation of women in the labor market and the conciliation of work and family life.</p> <p>4.3. Verify through the reports that the projects supported with funding have been implemented from a gender perspective, identifying possible gender gaps and establishing the appropriate mechanisms to eliminate them, if any.</p>
<p>5. . Measures against gender violence, including sexual harassment.</p> <p>Ensure the necessary measures to prevent, identify and act against sexist violence, if any, including sexual and gender-based harassment in the institutional sphere of the</p>	<p>The Government of the Canary Islands has a protocol against workplace harassment that includes sexual or gender-based harassment in force, no training has been carried out in this regard in the ACIISI recently.</p> <p>The actions regarding harassment that the participants in the survey stated that have occurred are the following:</p> <p>Inappropriate comments regarding appearance or clothing</p> <p>Inappropriate comments about skills and competencies</p> <p>Inappropriate and unfair criticism</p> <p>humiliation and degradation</p> <p>Calls, emails, text messages, photos or videos with sexual subtitles</p> <p>Verbal, non-verbal, psychological threats or physical abuse</p>	<p>5.1. Keep ACIISI staff informed about the protocol for action in situations of harassment in the workplace of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands in force through a mailing on where they can access the document and training aimed at all the staff.</p> <p>5.2. Continue including in the bases of subsidies and in the specifications the necessary compliance with European regulations related to support for the hiring of women victims of sexist violence.</p> <p>5.3. Continue to include in external audits aimed at institutions that receive funds the obligation to comply with current legislation on equality and specifically to approve and apply a protocol for prevention and action against sexual and gender-based harassment.</p>

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
ACIISI.	<p>Measures are in place to support victims of gender violence through social clauses in hiring.</p> <p>There is no data regarding whether or not the institutions that receive funds have a protocol against sexual and gender-based harassment (mandatory for entities with more than 50 workers and to be assessed in the case of those with smaller staff in which case is voluntary).</p>	
<p>6. Budgets with a gender approach:</p> <p>Carry out the programming, collection and monitoring of data disaggregated by sex, including specific indicators for measuring budget allocation and gender impact (how much it benefits men or</p>	<p>The analysis of gender impact in the budgets is mandatory and is not being carried out in the ACIISI.</p> <p>According to the 2022 gender analysis sheet and assessment of budget programs. 463B Research and innovative human capital prepared by the ACIISI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is difficulty in assessing inequalities since reliable data is not available on some aspects such as the presence of men and women in decision-making positions, both in research policy and in companies or entities linked to the activities R&D <p>Participation is taking place in the Working Group on Gender Equality in R&D&I Funds, held by the R&D&I Policy Network of the Ministry of Science and Innovation, the Ministry of Finance and the Autonomous Communities.</p> <p>Gender reports have been prepared for the annual budgets</p>	<p>6.1. Maintain in applications for grants and aid a field of the applicant disaggregated by sex and prepare reports on the budgets granted to men and women. For example, predoctoral and postdoctoral contracts as pilot initiatives.</p> <p>6.2. Review specific data disaggregated by sex from the last calls granted to see if there are gender gaps (2020-2025)</p> <p>6.3. Create a dashboard with indicators disaggregated by sex with all the data collected in the application for all subsidies, carry out analyzes and proposals for possible corrective measures, if applicable.</p> <p>6.4. Continue participating in the gender equality working groups on behalf of the ACIISI R&D&I funds and policies.</p> <p>6.5. Include specific objectives in programs related to the promotion of gender equality: Example: promote the inclusion of the gender perspective as a transversal category in science, technology and innovation, as well as a balanced presence of women and men in all the areas of</p>

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
<p>women and the reduction of existing gaps) of strategies, plans, programs , calls and projects that are financed by public funds.</p>	<p>(See Annex 1)</p>	<p>the science technology and innovation system.</p>
<p>7. Inclusive and non-sexist institutional communication.</p> <p>Guarantee that all external and internal communication is carried out with inclusive language and free of content and/or images that include sexist stereotypes.</p>	<p>Not all staff know the existing instruments in the entity: manual and advisory service. Inclusive and non-sexist communication reviews are being carried out on the documents, although not on all of them.</p> <p>Institutional communication: Inclusive language and images in ACIISI communication, existence of a GOBCAN manual, contact telephone number. https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/el-personal-del-gobierno-cuenta-con-un-nuevo-espacio-de-consulta-y-recursos-audiovisuales-para-comunicar-en-igualdad/.</p> <p>Legality reports are carried out by the General Technical Secretariat of the Ministry, correcting the language in the wording of the Order proposals:</p> <p>Incorporation of the Name of Relevant Scientific Women in the actions financed by the ACIISI.</p>	<p>7.1. Gender-sensitive guidelines for communication are disseminated and implemented: manual of the Government of the Canary Islands and existing advice service through contact telephone.</p> <p>7.2. Carrying out a language review from a gender perspective: web, social networks, internal and external communications to identify areas for improvement in order to use inclusive visual and textual communication.</p> <p>7.3. Continue naming performances in honor of women scientists</p> <p>7.4. Continue activities on women and girls in science through mini-fairs.</p> <p>7.5. Continue including the gender dimension in relation to inclusive and non-sexist communication and advertising in the bases and criteria for assessment.</p>

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Specific Objectives	Diagnostic Information	Actions
	With a view to promoting it in the financed institutions, it is included in some of the instruments described above that integrate the gender dimension in their bases and assessment criteria ³¹ .	

10.5 Actions

Table 24. Actions for ACIISI - GOBCAN GEP

Action No.	Content area	Issue to be addressed/evidence (specific objective)[1]	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment
1	Work-life balance and organisational culture	Maintain an organizational culture that allows the effective reconciliation of personal and work life for	1.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it/ All the people who have requested it and meet the legal requirements are granted it.

³¹ . See 8.3.4.

		the entire ACIISI staff through support for self-care and care Responsibilities towards minors and other dependents.	1.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it/ All the people who have requested it and meet the legal requirements are granted it			
			1.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it/ All the people who have requested it and meet the legal requirements are granted it.			
			1.4.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of training days and number of attendees, perhaps they should be included for the entire CECE/At least 3 days are held with 75% of the staff attending.			
2	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Establish the appropriate measures so that there is equality between women and men in leadership and decision-making (participation, representation, training and recognition) in conditions of equity, preventing, identifying and eliminating, if any, existing gender gaps.	2.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of men and women representing the ACIISI at the public contracting tables.			
						Number of ACIISI representatives at public procurement tables with training and/or experience in gender equality			
						R. There is parity in the representation of the ACIISI in the public contracting tables.			
						2.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	R. All the ACIISI representatives in the public contracting tables have training and/or experience in gender equality.
					Equal number of men and women on the scorecard.				
					Number of people appointed with training and experience in gender.				
					R. Parity is maintained on the scorecard.				
		2.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	R. They increase the number of designated people with training and experience in gender.				
						Number of training days and number of attendees, perhaps they should be included for the entire CECE/At least 3 days are held with 75% of the staff attending.			

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						Number of projects approved for the third sector to promote women researchers
			2.4.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of R&D&I projects granted to women and company projects led by women with respect to the total.
						R. The number of R&D&i projects granted to women and company projects led by women is maintained or increased with respect to the total.
			2.5.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of women beneficiaries of financing
						R. The financing granted to the third sector for the promotion of women researchers and the number of women beneficiaries of the financing is maintained.
			3	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Implement the necessary measures to prevent and act, if any, against discrimination based on sex in hiring and professional promotion, guaranteeing gender equality.	3.1.
						Number of companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total.
			3.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of audits that include information on the obligation to comply with equality legislation: remuneration record + equality plan
						Number of companies that accredit it + 50 workers -50 workers on a voluntary basis.
				2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	R. There is a registry

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			3.3	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of men and women hired by the companies or institutions financed
						Number of women and men beneficiaries of the financing
						R. There is a registry to be able to assess and address possible gender gaps and prepare more inclusive budgets.
			3.4.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of R&D&I projects granted to women and company projects led by women with respect to the total.
						R. The number of R&D&i projects granted to women and company projects led by women is maintained or increased with respect to the total.
4	Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Include the gender perspective in research actions, educational and communicative content, identifying and eliminating all sexist biases and stereotypes, if any.	4.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of R&D&i projects granted whose content contemplates the gender dimension.
						A. The number of R&D&l projects whose content includes the gender dimension is maintained or increased.
			4.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of awarded companies that have a voluntary/mandatory equality plan compared to the total number of those that have been presented.
						Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total.
			4.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of funded projects implemented from a gender perspective.
						R. The number of projects implemented from a gender perspective is maintained or increased

5	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Ensure the necessary measures to prevent, identify and act against sexist violence, if any, including sexual and gender-based harassment in the institutional sphere of the ACIISI.	5.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of training sessions given to ACIISI staff during the period of validity of this Equality Plan
						R. Achieve the widest possible dissemination of these measures
			5.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of financial actions that contain references to compliance with regulations related to support for victims of gender violence
						R. The number of financial actions that comply with it is maintained or increased.
			5.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of entities/individuals benefiting from the funding actions that apply a protocol against sexual and gender-based harassment.
						R. The number of beneficiary entities/persons that have this protocol is increased.
6.	Budgets with a gender approach	Carry out the programming, collection and monitoring of data disaggregated by sex, including specific indicators for measuring budget allocation and gender impact (how much benefits men or women and the reduction of existing gaps) of strategies, plans,	6.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Annual budget granted to men and women.
						R. Keep track of budget items disaggregated by sex.
			6.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of men and women beneficiaries of each action during the period 2020 – 2025
						R. Identify gender gaps.
			6.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Implementation of the scorecard
						R. Have a control panel that allows the visualization and analysis of the information from the historical data.

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		programs, calls and projects that are financed by public funds.	6.4	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of working groups in which ACIISI participates
						R. Increase the number of ACIISI personnel that participate in these working groups.
			6.5.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of programs promoting gender equality.
						R. Maintain/increase the number of programs of this type.
7.	Inclusive and non-sexist Institutional Communication.	Guarantee that all external and internal communication is carried out with inclusive language and free of content and/or images that include sexist stereotypes.	7.1.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of training pills disseminated aimed at gender awareness.
						R. Increase gender awareness.
			7.2.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Percentage of reviewed publications that do not contain inclusive language.
						R. Identify non-inclusive language in posts
			7.3.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of performances in tribute to scientific women
			R. Increase/maintain the number of performances honoring women scientists			
			7.4	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of mini-fairs held on women and girls in science
						R. Increase/maintain the number of this type of mini-fairs.
			7.5.	2022-2026	Head of ACIISI	Number of actions in which compliance with inclusive and non-sexist communication and advertising is verified.
						R. Increase/maintain compliance with this measure.

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10.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

The ACIISI is committed to monitoring and periodically reporting on the implementation of the GEP through the following actions:

- The ACIISI will carry out a six-monthly follow-up of the implementation of the measures defined in this plan.
- Guarantee of update of data registry that is visualized in the dashboard. Every 6 months.
- Periodic checks of the value of the indicators to assess the scope of the pre-set objectives. In case of deviation, how to establish adequate mechanisms to compensate it.
- Preparation of annual monitoring and evaluation report.

The people responsible for monitoring and evaluating the gender equality plan of the ACIISI are the members of the institutional equality commission and the person in charge of the allocation and monitoring of human and financial resources is the Head of the ACIISI Area.

- Antonio López, Head of ACIISI Area.
- Guzmán Palacios Arazuri, Head of the R&D Support Service.
- Patricia Oramas Gallar, Head of Section of the ACIISI Coordination Area.
- Javier Roo, Responsible for R&D&I Projects.
- Patricia Jiménez López, Senior Technician ACIISI.
- Guendolina Martín Díaz. Responsible for communication.
- Carmen Sánchez López. Head of Business.
- Carmen Alonso. Computer technique.
- Asunción Jiménez. General Director of Labor (GC).
- Teresa Barroso. General Sec. Technical TF.

10.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

This document will be distributed as follows:

- It will be published on the institution's website. The published Gender Equality Plan must be signed by senior management.
- Awareness training will be implemented, addressing the issues of unconscious bias and/or other specific issues.
- Actions will be carried out to disseminate the Gender Equality Plan in institutional communication, both online and through the organization of public events inviting external agents and attendance at congresses or relevant events.

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Gender Equality Plan

Regional Fund of Science and Technology
(FRCT)

11. FRCT Gender Equality Plan

11.1 Introduction

The Gender Equality Plan (GEP) of the Regional Fund of Science and Technology (FRCT), Regional Government of Azores, is the most visible result of an organizational transformation unleashed by the H2020 project ATHENA – "Implementing gender equality plans to unlock the research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe."

Equality and non-discrimination are guiding and regulating principles of modern open and democratic societies and are inextricably linked to the demands of equity and diversity. Since 1948, "equal rights of men and women" have been enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and gender discrimination has been condemned. More recently, the European Union's Charter of Fundamental Rights states that "equality between men and women must be guaranteed in all areas, including employment, work, and pay." In addition, the principle of equality "shall not prevent the maintenance or adoption of measures providing specific benefits for the underrepresented sex." (cf. art. 23.º). The international political and legal roadmap for the promotion and defence of Gender Equality (GE) also includes the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, the Millennium Development Goals, and, since 2015, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, the fifth of which addresses GE and women's empowerment.

In compliance with Portugal's regulatory framework, the Autonomous Region of the Azores has its own bodies for designing, implementing, and evaluating public policies promoting GE and the prevention of violence against women. In this context, GE has been enshrined as a fundamental principle in the Portuguese legal system since the last Constitution of the Portuguese Republic in 1976. Over the past several decades, public policies for GE have been implemented in accordance with National Equality Plans, and since 2018, in-depth within the new National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination – Portugal + equal (ENIND).

There are numerous positive repercussions of the recognition and appreciation of women in Portuguese and Azorean society, particularly in the fields of Research and Innovation (R&I), such as the attainment of decision-making positions in Higher Education Institutions (HEI) and the performance of traditionally male government functions. However, subtle or difficult-to-deconstruct barriers continue to hinder the lives and careers of women in scientific fields.

FRCT is an autonomous administrative, financial, and patrimonial body responsible for coordinating actions and managing financial resources available for scientific and technological research from regional, European, and international programs. In terms

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of integration of GE, despite not having a formal GE policy, the organization has consistently fought for the recognition of women's roles in research, employing approximately 60 per cent of women and implementing specific measures to support women, such as closing the pay gap for pregnant women on maternity leave.

Consequently, the current GEP represents FRCT's commitment to raising awareness of the issue of GE, dismantling unconscious biases related to the topic and altering behaviours and situations that promote inequality or discrimination. In addition to the organizational culture and the significance of promoting R&I in scientific and technological fields in a European Union outermost region as the Azores, it reflects the dedication to the Science and Technology System of the Azores (SCTA) to combine the dissemination of knowledge with social innovation via a spillover effect.

The FRCT's GEP will enter into force in June 2022 and remain in effect until December 2025, encompassing the years 2022-2025. It includes a general objective and six priority areas to which specific objectives and concrete actions are linked, both in terms of confirming the seriousness of the GE concerns and detecting gaps and bias. The six priority areas are Work-Life Balance and Organizational Culture, Gender Balance in Leadership and Decision-Making, GE in Recruitment and Career Progression, Integration of the Gender Dimension into Research and Teaching Content, Measures against Gender-Based Violence, including Sexual Harassment and Inclusive Institutional Communication.

In light of this, the establishment of the present GEP is a critical step toward the implementation and monitoring of the institution's pro-equality initiatives, as well as an indication of the FRCT's stance on this vitally important matter.

11.2 Development process and GEP management

The current GEP was developed under the ATHENA project, funded by the H2020 programme, the EU's research and innovation funding programme 2014-2020. It is the result of a solid foundation for the development of an appropriate GEP for the institution, which began in early 2021 with an initial internal Gender Equality Audit (GEA), involving the entire organization's staff (the Board of Directors and Employees). The objective of this audit was to determine the extent to which FRCT promotes GE internally within its organizational, managerial, and internal work structures, and whether these factors contribute to GE within the organization.

In addition to quantitative and qualitative indicators, the GEA of the FRCT included two participatory approaches, focus groups and staff surveys. Three focus groups of collective reflection on GE were conducted, and FRCT staff responded to a 47-question anonymous comprehensive staff survey. Both approaches allowed for valuable reflection on GE issues, first in the context of the FRCT and then in the context of broader social challenges. In addition, these methodologies allowed for a

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critical perspective on GE in general and on the specific scope of GE in traditionally male-dominated research and scientific professions.

The ATHENA responsible team from FRCT collaborated closely with gender experts from the University of the Azores, specifically the Centre for Humanities Studies (CEHu), for the development of the GEA and GEP.

As a strategic document, the FRCT's GEP will engage the entire organization, as it requires the support and official commitment of the FRCT's Directive Board, as well as the active engagement of the entire organization, which consists of selected members of the GEPI Committee, the Communication manager and a human resources representative. On an external level, FRCT is supported by the Regional Directorate for the Promotion of Equality and Social Inclusion (DRPIIS) from the Azores Government and the team of gender experts from the University of the Azores.

A Gender Equality Plan Implementation (GEPI) Committee was established with ten members who will play the primary role in the implementation of the GEP within FRCT, with responsibilities relating to the specific goals and actions to be carried out. In this sense, the members of the Committee are key actors for the ATHENA project and especially for FRCT, as they will transmit co-produced knowledge on GE and facilitate and promote the institutional change through the implementation of the GEP.

Furthermore, the GEPI Committee affirms FRCT's political, social, human, material and financial commitment to GE, non-discrimination, equity, and diversity, which are tenets of an equitable, supportive, and inclusive workplace.

11.3 Diagnosis

The findings of the process of diagnosis are the result of a design based on a combination of research methodologies and diverse data collection techniques implemented throughout the year 2021, developed by the Institute for Research in Social Communication at the Slovak Academy of Sciences, ATHENA partner.

The specificity of the FRCT was determined through the use of two major participatory techniques, namely focus groups and a staff survey. The process of diagnosis and data collection was adapted by FRCT's characteristics. Its small size, with only 21 staff members (18 participated in the focus groups and 15 responded to the staff survey), the predominance of women. In addition, FRCT's simple hierarchy organization, absence of middle decision-making positions, it has only a Board of Directors, which consists of the President and two other members, and Employees, for a variety of different tasks.

11.3.1 Focus Groups

Concerning the focus groups and the initial approach, the results indicated that all groups agreed that there is no gender discrimination in the organization, no disparities

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in salary or workload and that men and women are treated equally. In addition, there was the agreement that more women are employed by the FRCT because they demonstrate the necessary skills and merit during the public hiring process. Despite widespread claims that there is no gender disparity in the distribution of projects, the traditional pattern of women working primarily in social fields and men in natural sciences and engineering was observed.

In the second approach, some concerns arose, namely the broader context of a society in which gender inequality persists and the perception of greater pressure on women, particularly mothers, who must work harder to demonstrate their capacity and efficiency, particularly in research and scientific careers and when they achieve positions of authority. Also, some comments emphasized that the organization's highest position has always been held by a man. Furthermore, it was stated that women in leadership face exposure-based discrimination. In other words, women's leadership is frequently criticized, and achieving a position of authority, as a woman, is regarded as an "extraordinary achievement."

Concerning work-life balance and according to women, the difficulties of reconciling work and family life, particularly for mothers, were highlighted, as it can be difficult for women to balance work and motherhood under precarious employment conditions. Contributions to the current GEP included implementing inclusive or gender-neutral language, adopting flexible schedules and adjusting deadlines and results, and increasing the number of women in leadership positions.

11.3.2 Staff Survey

Concerning the staff survey methodology, fifteen FRCT employees responded to the questionnaire, accounting for 71% of the FRCT workforce. Despite the small sample size and certain limitations, the qualitative analysis permitted the identification of some GE issues. On the one hand, it illustrated how men and women perceive the problem's multiple dimensions differently. On the other hand, the disparity in women's attitudes toward the subject and the pursuit of truly equitable answers. The qualitative analysis revealed crucial information for identifying the predominant gender bias and identifying the GEP's priority areas.

Even though the disparity is not statistically significant, the traditional pattern of the majority of women performing administrative duties as opposed to technical ones continues at the FRCT. Surprisingly, 67% of women at the FRCT have a background in Natural Sciences, while 33% have a background in Social Sciences. Men continue to follow the traditional pattern of training in Engineering, Natural Sciences, and Computer Science.

Regarding the traditional correlation between scientific activity and men (which excludes women from science), there are clear differences between women's assertive responses and men's more reserved or neutral stances. Additionally, the

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perception that the mechanisms for electing individuals to positions of authority are not equal and fair.

It is significant that women's responses reveal greater assertiveness regarding the significance of GE and the identification of inequalities and discrimination norms. In contrast, male responses reveal a lack of interest in GE issues.

11.4 Objectives

The primary objective of the FRCT's GEP is to establish a foundation for promoting, enhancing, ensuring, and achieving gender equality, assuming the commitment to integrate the gender dimension into its institutional strategy and proposing the development of a medium-term action plan between 2022 and 2025.

The aforementioned European, national, and institutional policies determine the general objectives of this plan's implementation. In section 5, table 1, the six general goals of the FRCT's GEP and their mapping to the specified areas of intervention are outlined in an effort to achieve the respective goals.

In accordance with the "Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans," in addition to the five recommended content-related (thematic) areas that organizations may wish to consider in their GEP, FRCT acknowledged the need to adopt a sixth area concerning institutional communication. The identified areas of intervention covered by this GEP are:

- Action area 1: Work-life balance and organizational culture;
- Action area 2: Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
- Action area 3: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
- Action area 4: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content;
- Action area 5: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment;
- Action area 6: Institutional Communication.

For each of the six identified areas, six specific objectives and twelve measures have been outlined. The specific objectives are directly related to the areas of action following:

- Objective 1: Ensure that the organization of working time takes into account the need to conciliate professional, family and personal life, particularly for those with family responsibilities, including support for men in caring for their children;
- Objective 2: Promote training programs as a key element to help women to develop skills in accessing management and decision-making roles;
- Objective 3: Guarantee the principle of equality and non-discrimination between women and men in recruitment and career progression;
- Objective 4: Ensure women's participation and representation in project definition and access to research funding;

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- Objective 5: To prevent and combat harassment at work and other forms of harm to the physical or moral integrity, freedom and dignity of male and female employees;
- Objective 6: To use inclusive language that is gender-neutral or refers to both genders, and to acquire tools to utilise inclusive language and gender-neutral visual communication.

11.5 Actions

This section assumes special relevance for the action plan to promote GE. On the basis of the six previously established thematic areas, six specific objectives were defined. In turn, each objective will be developed through a series of actions, resulting in a total of 12 measures, which are listed and described below, aggregated per objective.

Action Area 1

Objective 1.1

Action 1.1.: Goal-oriented work and fixed working hours exemption

Organising the work activities of each employee with their coordinator through regular meetings, allowing the implementation of a goal-oriented work paradigm and flexible working hours. Development and implementation of internal procedures (record or memorandum of meetings).

Action 1.2: Hybrid work model (combination of office-based working with remote days)

Organising the work activities of each employee with their coordinator through regular meetings, allowing a hybrid work model to be implemented. Development and implementation of internal procedures (record or memorandum of meetings).

Action Area 2

Objective 2.1

Action 2.1.1: Team Building activities between managers and employees

Two annual internal events with activities designed to engage and motivate teams to deconstruct gender stereotypes regarding leadership positions. Creation of analysis sheets and assessment records.

Action 2.1.2: Leadership and coaching programs for women and men

Leadership and coaching programs for women and men designed to develop skills in accessing management and decision-making positions. Creation of analysis sheets and curricular assessment records.

Action Area 3

Objective 3.1

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[Action 3.1.1: Promote Gender-neutral recruitment and hiring to implement job-shadowing program. \(Original Idea: Sabanci University - HEI - Turkey\)](#)

This is an innovative mentorship program that matches a mentee, a woman interested in a managerial job, with a top management representative, whether he or she is a male or a female. After a few introductory sessions, the mentee can "job shadow" the mentor and take on some of the mentor's usual activities for a set/short length of time. Formalization of its achievement and success via certification or letter of recommendation.

[Action 3.1.2: Recognition of domestic and family care skills in the Curriculum Vitae of candidates](#)

Implementation of a holistic evaluation of the candidates' curriculum vitae, valuing dimensions and competencies that are not typically considered and that usually penalize women. All recruitment processes should include a clear definition of domestic and caring skills, their length, and the respective ponderation to in recruitment process evaluations.

[Action Area 4](#)

Objective 4.1

[Action 4.1.1: Sponsorships, grants, awards for women researchers](#)

Creation of the annual award "Women in Science", a financial incentive, in collaboration with the Regional Directorate of Equal Opportunities (DRIO), to highlight and promote women in Science.

[Action 4.1.2: Public events/workshops to integrate the gender dimension into research \(e.g.: 'International Day of Women and Girls in Science' and 'International Women's Day'\)](#)

In collaboration with the DRPIIS, the creation of an event to highlight and promote women in science. A dedicated event with lectures for women who work in a highly specialized research field has the potential to raise the profile of both the women researchers and the topics on which they work.

[Action Area 5](#)

Objective 5.1

[Action 5.1.1: Sexual harassment surveys and campaign for prevention and combating sexual harassment](#)

This measure entails creating and implementing a sexual harassment survey within the organization to highlight the level of awareness and information regarding the concept. The results will guide the most appropriate campaign. Dissemination campaigns will be created with strong awareness messages.

[Action 5.1.2: Establishment of a confidential virtual space for reporting cases of discrimination or harassment of any kind.](#)

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This measure consists of establishing a confidential virtual space for reporting cases of discrimination or harassment of any kind at work.

[Action 5.1.3: Gender-based violence awareness event](#)

Organization of an internal lecture event with qualified gender experts and technicians from relevant institutions in the field of gender violence.

Action Area 6

Objective 6.1

[Action 6.1.1: Adopt gender sensitive Language and gender-neutral visual communication in internal and external communication](#)

This measure entails the creation of guidelines for gender sensitive and inclusive language, as well as gender-neutral visual communication to be used in internal and external official communication. All employees will be trained on how to apply these guidelines effectively and adapt them to all internal and external communications.

Table 25. Actions for the FRCT's GEP

Content area	Specific objective	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment
Work-life balance and organizational culture	Objective 1.1. Ensure that the organization of working time takes into account the need to conciliate professional, family and personal life, particularly for those with family responsibilities, including support for men in caring for their children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action 1.1.1. Goal-oriented work and fixed working hours exemption • Action 1.1.2. Hybrid work model (combination of office-based working with remote days) 	2022-2025	FRCT Directive Board members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each employee has access to goal-oriented work paradigm and a flexible work schedule. • Each employee has access to hybrid work.
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Objective 2.1. Promote training programs as a key element to help women to develop skills in accessing management and decision-making roles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action 2.1.1. Team Building activities between managers and employees • Action 2.1.2. Leadership and coaching programs for women and men 	2022-2025 2022-2025	Communication manager FRCT Directive Board members and a specially designed team of gender experts from the University of the Azores	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each employee can take part in team-building activities with managers and coworkers, which will increase the level of motivation at work and allow the deconstruction of gender stereotypes • Each employee and civil society can take part in leadership training and coaching programs for women and men, in which skills in accessing management and decision-making roles will be developed and accessed by collecting and comparing data before and after the event.
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	Objective 3.1. Guarantee the principle of equality and non-discrimination between women and men in recruitment and career	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action 3.1.1. Promote Gender neutral recruitment and hiring to implement job-shadowing program. 	2022-2025	Communication manager FRCT Directive Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mentor-mentee relationship is strengthened, and the exchange of information and skill (business intelligence) between the two is enhanced.

Content area	Specific objective	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment
	progression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action 3.1.2. Recognition of domestic and family care skills in the Curriculum Vitae of candidates 		members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the recruitment process, women and men are recognised for their domestic and family care skills in their Curriculum Vitae.
Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Objective 4.1. Ensure women's participation and representation in project definition and access to research funding.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action 4.1.1. Sponsorships, grants, awards for women researchers. Action 4.1.2. Public events/workshops to integrate the gender dimension into research (e.g.: 'International Day of Women and Girls in Science' and 'International Women's Day') 	2022-2025	FRCT and DRPIIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The levels of visibility and participation of women in Science increase, as well as the awareness of the importance of Gender Equality in Research and Innovation. The levels of visibility and participation of women in Science increase, as well as the awareness of the importance of Gender Equality in Research and Innovation.
Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	Objective 5.1. To prevent and combat harassment at work and other forms of harm to the physical or moral integrity, freedom and dignity of male and female employees.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action 5.1.1. Sexual Harassment Surveys and Campaign for prevention and combating sexual harassment. Action 5.1.2. Establishment of a confidential virtual space for reporting cases of 	2022-2025	<p>Team of gender experts from the University of the Azores and Communication Officer</p> <p>FRCT Directive Board and selected members from GEPI Committee</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of the concept of sexual harassment will be accessed and information will be provided to raise awareness and better identify these situations. Victims of harassment at work are supported. Sexual harassment at work is a

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Content area	Specific objective	Action	Start/end date	Responsibility	Impact assessment
		<p>discrimination or harassment of any kind.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action 5.1.3. Gender-based violence awareness event. 		FRCT Directive Board and gender experts qualified in the respective field	topic that employees are aware of.
Inclusive Institutional Communication	Objective 6.1. To use inclusive language that is gender-neutral or refers to both genders, and to acquire tools to utilize inclusive language and gender-neutral visual communication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action 6.1.1. Adopt gender sensitive Language and gender neutral visual communication in internal and external communication 	2022-2025	FRCT Directive Board and gender experts from the University of the Azores	All members of the institution use an inclusive language and gender-neutral visual communication in internal and external communication.

11.6 GEP monitoring, reporting and assessment

The monitoring work should summarize the implementation and evaluation of the GEP throughout its entirety. During the implementation of the GEP, the accomplishments, progress, and obstacles will be monitored and analyzed.

The final evaluation of the GEP's outputs, outcomes, and potential impacts, as well as the project's outputs, will take into account the progress made since the evaluation of the implementation, going beyond its conclusion through the periodic presentation of institutional reports.

The data collection for the monitoring report will include the five priority areas recommended by the European Commission accompanied by the sixth area that was claimed by the GEPI Committee, and which reflects the most critical areas for GE in the research and academia.

Monitoring instruments are those that permit assessing the impact of FRCT objectives and measures after their application period. They consist of specific indicators for evaluating the GEP's impact, a schedule of assessment sessions, and the drafting of related assessment reports. The latter should document the accomplishments attained.

The FRCT GEPI Committee will conduct annual monitoring and reporting of the collected data. The annual report should contribute to a review of the GEP's goals and objectives by its leadership and stakeholders. The review should allow the FRCT to comprehend progress, determine where activities are having an effect, and pinpoint where obstacles persist.

The monitoring results will be used to initiate an internal discussion on GE. How did the circumstance evolve? What succeeded? What didn't work? Why? What factors contributed to the success or failure? Is it necessary to establish more specific objectives or expand the measures? These issues should be discussed within the GEPI Committee and used to develop a strategy for communicating with the institution's members.

The objectives of the GEP monitoring can be presented in a table (the following is an example).

RESULTS	MEASUREMENT		ACHIEVEMENT			RELEVANCE	TIMEFRAME
Final result	Quantity measures	Quality measures	Available knowledge, new skills	Available resources	Time constraints	Mission and vision Legal requirements	----
Specific results							

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How to fill the table

Result: a brief description of the results of the work that must be done so that it is clear and observable.

Measurement: include quantitative measurements (for example, by fixing a percentage or frequency) and/or qualitative measurements (for example, in terms of accuracy or fulfilment with legal regulation). It is essential to identify how the impact of the different measures adopted in the GEP will be assessed in terms of achieving the objective.

Achievement: the objectives should be fixed considering the possibility of success in achieving such an objective given the time frame, opportunity, and resources available, including the budget.

Relevance: the objectives should be aligned with the institution's mission and vision as well as any legal requirement.

Timeframe: the objectives must include a specific timeframe or due date for their completion. A standard and recommended timeframe for objectives are 4 years.

The necessary information for the periodical monitoring will be shared by the FRCT GEPI Committee.

The FRCT GEPI Committee aims at creating and sustaining top management commitment, the involvement of the organization and the establishment of data collection procedures, which allow for a gender analysis of the *status quo* regarding top management commitment. The availability of data will be described in detail. These descriptions will be updated in a narrative form (description of changes, supporting or hindering factors). It is assumed that this will lead to a more detailed understanding of gender discrepancies, career barriers or excluding factors for specific groups of women.

Furthermore, the monitoring should also include information on the FRCT Gender Equality Committee especially any changes in its composition or activities.

The plan assumes the transversality of the gender perspective, which is derived from the European Strategy for Gender Equality 2020-2025 and the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination 2018-2030, ENIND. Since, this is the first plan, it is believed that this timeframe is adequate for the implementation of a set of key actions whose novelty and transformative nature require a medium-term strategy. On the other hand, the plan is dynamic, meaning it is subject to change based on the evolution and conclusion of the activities or actions it contains.

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11.7 Dissemination strategy of the GEP

Following the “Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans”, the GEP should follow the mandatory requirements below:

- Be published on the FRCT's public website and signed by the executive management. To demonstrate its commitment to GE and enables proper accountability against the plan's goals and objectives by the organization's staff, partners, stakeholders, and the broader community. And demonstrate a good practice for other Governmental entities.
- The FRCT GEPI Committee should organise trainings to raise awareness of unconscious bias to comprehend the nature of unconscious bias and how it may impact our judgment and decision-making. Encourage participants to consider the ideas of submission and dominance in light of their own historical, cultural, and philosophical prejudices.
- Be actively communicated within the institution, as well as widely distributed and conveyed throughout the organization, to demonstrate the support of the leadership for the strategy. All staff members at all organizational levels are responsible for delivering the GEP's commitments and actions, and they will be held accountable for the GEP's implementation within their domains.
- Regularly revise the publications regarding the results. This will be accomplished via annual monitoring and concluding reports. Depending on the organizational structure, the FRCT GEPI Committee will also involve stakeholders in meetings or provide them with regular updates.
- The FRCT GEPI Committee will keep other interested parties apprised of the progress of organizational change, and may also organize a meeting to present and discuss the results of the analysis (e.g., after the final evaluation of the GEP).
- The FRCT Communication manager will also define target policy at the regional or national level, professional associations, or other institutional partners of the organization.
- The dissemination strategy of the GEP requires the internal and external publication of monitoring results in different forms (e.g., a printed report and website) and a discursive format (e.g., a presentation or workshop). The monitoring results might also be used for presenting the FRCT as a gender-sensitive organization, demonstrate progress and gender equality initiatives and contribute to a national/regional gender equality discourse. A combination of internal and external strategies and formats may also be used.